

Inherit

Capacity Building Programme for Cultural Heritage/ D6.1

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Authors (ICLEI European Secretariat):

Dr. Cristina Garzillo, Elizabeth Thomas, Gioele Racca, Komal Potdar, Dr. Małgorzata Ćwikła, Telmo Jiménez Irizar

INHERIT Pilots & Contributors:

- REGEA: Petra Vučetić Osonjački, Nikolina Brckan Jakšić
- BOUYGUES: Xavier Gauvin, Sandrine Fauquet, Emmanuelle Riol
- ELLET: Elias Sakellaris, Vasiliki Pougkakioti
- RPR: Aija Zučika, Agris Kamenders, Ilze Ozola
- FASADA: Magdalena Dzik-Bogucka, Rafał Łukaszewski, Marek Giluń
- CARTIF: María Esteban Ferrer, Pedro Martín Leronés
- UU: Asso. Prof. Heracles Polatidis
- IBB: Dr. Özden Coşkun Öner, Dr. Hilmi Gökhan Kutlu

INHERIT Learning Partners:

- Zero Waste Europe (Slovenia): Andrej Fideršek, Katja Saje and Nina Vidic (Mismo Collective)
- HeritACT Consortium team: Eva Vlachaki, Katherine Liapi, Myrto Staratzi, Ian Christidis, Maria Kastani, Martha Stroumpou, Tim Bruder, Dzina Skuratovic
- The Cyprus Institute (Cyprus): Asso. Prof. George Artopoulos
- Institut Iskriwa (Slovenia): Mateja Softić, Matej Jereb Sedej
- University of Bologna (Italy): Adj. Prof. Alessia Zampini
- ULTEAM, Arte Charpentier (France): Camila Scalisi, Godefroy Saint Georges, Raquel MILAGRES

Reviewers:

- ISSO: Dirk de Wit
- REGEA: Ivana Pečnik

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Project Coordinator	Stamatia Rizou SINGULARLOGIC ANONYMI ETAIREIA PLIROFORIAKON SYSTIMATON KAI EFARMOGON PLIROFORIKIS (SLG) srizou@singularlogic.eu
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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	4
List of Figures	6
List of Tables	7
Abbreviations and Acronyms	8
Executive Summary	10
Acknowledgements	12
1. Introduction	13
1.1 Introduction to the INHERIT Project	13
1.1.1 INHERIT Services	14
1.1.2 INHERIT Pilots	15
1.1.3 INHERIT Pilots and Proposed Services	16
1.2 Significance of the Project	17
1.2.1 Need for Sustainable, Inclusive, and Resource-Efficient Cultural Heritage Solutions	17
1.2.2 Integration of Technical Expertise with Cultural and Societal Perspectives	18
2. Capacity Building Programme	20
2.1 Context	20
2.2 Method and Approach	21
2.2.1 Task A: Synergies and Peer-Learning	21
2.2.2 Task B: INHERIT E-Learning Modules and Webinars	22
2.2.3 Task C: INHERIT Pilots’ Journals for Future-Oriented Reflection and Monitoring	22
2.3 Target Groups and Audience	23
2.4 Task Cycle and Milestones	23
2.5 Expected Outcomes	24
3. Task A: Peer Learning Scheme: Conceptualisation to Implementation 25	
3.1 Phase 1: Needs Assessment of the INHERIT Pilots	27
3.1.1 Needs Assessments of INHERIT Pilots	27
3.2 Phase 2: Conceptualisation and Launch of Peer Learning Scheme	29
3.2.1 New European Bauhaus and its Connection to the Peer Learning Scheme	29
3.2.2 Themes Adopted in the Peer Learning Scheme	29
3.3 Phase 3: Introduction of Learning Partners and Matchmaking with Pilots	31
3.3.1 Call for Learning Partners	31
3.3.2 Selection of Learning Partners	32
3.3.3 Evaluation of Proposed Case Studies and Matchmaking with Pilots	36
3.3.4 Design of Documentation Forms for the Peer Learning Study Visits	39

3.4 Phase 4: Implementation of Peer Learning Study Visits and Synthesis of Documentation Forms	39
3.4.1 Pilot 1: City Administration Headquarters – Jastrebarsko, Croatia; Coordinator: REGEA	40
3.4.2 Pilot 2: Cité du Goût - Noisiel, France; Coordinator: BOUYGUES	46
3.4.3 Pilot 3: ELLET building in Tripodon street - Athens, Greece; Coordinator: ELLET	55
3.4.4 Pilot 4: Ave Sol Concert Hall - Riga, Latvia; Coordinator: RPR	62
3.4.5 Pilot 5: Social Residential Building in Gdynia, Poland; Coordinator: FASADA	71
3.4.6 Pilot 6: Monastery 'Ntra. Sra. del Prado' - Valladolid, Spain; Coordinator: CARTIF	78
3.4.7 Pilot 7: City of Visby, UNESCO World Heritage Site - Gotland, Sweden; Coordinator: UU	86
3.4.8 Pilot 8: Ahmet Piriştina İzmir City Archive and Museum (APIKAM) - İzmir, Türkiye; Coordinator: IBB.....	93
3.5 Results and Key Takeaways of the Peer Learning Scheme	102
3.5.1 Design and Planning of the Peer Learning Scheme	102
3.5.2 Implementation.....	102
3.5.3 Peer Learning and Networking	103
3.5.4 Challenges and Learnings.....	103
4. Task B: E-learning Modules	105
4.1 Method	105
4.2 Implementation	106
4.2.1 Mentoring Scheme: Scope and Audience of the E-learning Modules.....	106
4.2.2 Technical and Soft Skills in Cultural Heritage.....	109
4.2.3 Pairing Needs and Project Outputs.....	112
4.3 Next Steps	113
5. Task C: INHERIT Living Journals	115
5.1 Method	115
5.2 Implementation	116
5.2.1 Achievements.....	116
5.2.2 Challenges	118
5.3 Lessons Learned and Next Steps	119
6. Key Takeaways from the INHERIT Capacity Building Programme	121
7. Bibliography	123
8. Annexes	125
8.1 Annex A: Call for Learning Partners and Application Form	125
8.2 Annex B: Assessment of Relevance and Matchmaking Process for all Learning Partners and Pilots	131
8.3 Annex C: Documentation Format for Peer Learning Study Visit	142
8.4 Annex D: Documentation of the Persona Workshop	148

List of Figures

Figure 1: The four main categories of INHERIT services13

Figure 2: The four phases of the peer learning scheme25

Figure 3: The outline and timeline of the task of the Peer Learning Scheme26

Figure 4: Pillars of the New European Bauhaus.....29

Figure 5: Themes of the peer learning scheme adopted from INHERIT’s project objectives30

Figure 6: Location of the INHERIT Learning Partners: 1. Zero Waste House, Žalec, Slovenia; 2: University of Patras: HeritACT, Patras, Greece; 3: The Cyprus Institute: Paphos Gate, Nicosia, Cyprus; 4:Institut Iskriava: Old Ironworks Project, Ravne na Koroškem, Slovenia; 5: University of Bologna: Baraccano Historical Complex, Bologna, Italy; 6: Arte Charpentier: ULTEAM (Cisco Headquarters), Paris, France33

Figure 7: Themes represented in each of the proposed case studies by Learning Partners.....36

Figure 8: An overall analysis of the relevance of proposed case studies to each pilot, based on the matchmaking of services.....38

Figure 9: L- View of the Zalej House; R- Installations for Energy Efficiency at the site, Photovoltaics, and Glamping dome.....45

Figure 10: L-Community garden; C- Energy saver installations; R- Reused roofing materials for circularity.....45

Figure 11: Chronological layers of the historic building46

Figure 12: L- First mansion 1820; R- During demolition53

Figure 13: ULTEAM.....54

Figure 14: L- Old, new and top floor; R- The court of honour54

Figure 15: Dormitory building. Not renovated yet (under site description)61

Figure 16: L- Guided tour by project architect; R- Museum (part of the building that is not renovated) with the collection of old machinery.61

Figure 17: Historic manor currently undergoing renovation.....70

Figure 18: L- Outside view of the main building - The New Centre Rog. Industrial heritage building, C. The renovation is nearly complete, featuring a modern wooden extension that complements the historic building. R - Space for workshops/laboratories and exhibitions. Space for studies and lectures.....70

Figure 19: L- Visit to the site where the case study building is located; C- View from the street. R- "CYPRUS INSULA" exhibition – presentation of AR/VR technology used to reconstruct a model of the former appearance of a now-destroyed airport.....77

Figure 20: L- Paphos Gate – visit to the project site that implemented AR/VR technology; R- Visit to the Cyprus Institute – demonstration of a VR environment based on the Paphos Gate model.....77

Figure 21: L & R-Tour of the Baraccano complex, situated in the Santo Stefano district of Bologna85

Figure 22: L- INHERIT’s Presentation; R- Walking in historic neighbourhood85

Figure 23: L- UU Presentation; R- Old Olive mill site exploration with HeritACT team.....92

Figure 24: L- The oldtown square subject to the Eleusis pilot implementation; R- Historic Old Canteen – a one-storey industrial canteen by the sea.....101

Figure 25: L- IBB presentation with team; C- Walking to the industrial heritage site; R- HeritACT Eleusis pilot presentation of temporary structures from recycled materials101

Figure 26: Mapping of SSH skills and technical sciences skills identified by project partners.107

Figure 27: Mapping of professionals working in CH and professionals who could enhance resource efficiency in CH.....107

Figure 28: The ‘personas’ illustration developed for the exercise to urge the participants to give diverse inputs; Credits: Agnieszka Ćwikła.....108

Figure 29: Overall outcome of all the skills voted after the mentoring calls were conducted.109

Figure 30: Outcomes of the ‘Bringing together technical and soft skills for the e-learning programme’ workshop.....110

Figure 31: Results of voting conducted on hard skills and soft skills.....111

List of Tables

Table 1: INHERIT Services for all pilots17

Table 2: Task Cycle of the Capacity Building Programme23

Table 3: Outcome of the Needs Assessment Exercise led by ICLEI27

Table 4: Services relevant to the INHERIT project as per the proposed case studies of the Learning Partners.....37

Table 5: Skills mapped throughout the duration of the Mentoring Scheme up until the date of the Valladolid workshop.....112

Table 6: Learning modules and learning units.....113

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
3D	Three-dimensional
ABF	Architectes des Bâtiments de France
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APIKAM	Ahmet Piriştina İzmir City Archive and Museum
AR/VR	Augmented Reality / Virtual Reality
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BIPV	Building-integrated Photovoltaics
BOUYGUES	BOUYGUES Immobilier SA
BREEAM	Buildings Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Methodology
CARTIF	Foundation CARTIF
CH	Cultural Heritage
CNC	Computer Numerical Control
D	Deliverable
DSS	Decision Support System
DRAC	Direction Régionale des Affaires Culturelles
E.g.	Exempli gratia (For example)
ELLET	ELLINIKI ETAIREIA Society for the Environment and CH
EU	European Union
FASADA	Przedsiębiorstwo Robót Elewacyjnych Fasada Sp. z o.o.
GA	Grant Agreement
GIS	Geographic Information System
Groupama	Groupama Immobilier
H-BIM	Heritage Building Information Modelling
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IBB	Izmir Metropolitan Municipality
ICLEI	ICLEI European Secretariat
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
IoT	Internet of Things
IPCE	Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España
ISSO	Stichting ISSO
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MSF	Multi-Stakeholder Forum
NEB	New European Bauhaus
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
P	Pilot
PMR	Personne à Mobilité Réduite (Persons with reduced mobility)
PV	Photovoltaics
REGEA	Regional Energy Agency
RES	Renewable Energy Source
ROI	Return on Investment
RPR	Riga Planning Region
S	Service
SIJ	Slovenska Industrija Jekla (Slovenian Steel Industry)
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Analysis/Assessment

SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TCO	Thermal Comfort Optimisation
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UU	Uppsala University
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The overall vision of INHERIT is to create a systematic methodology, accompanied by leading-edge Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), such as Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI) and (big) data analytics, and associated social/behavioural practices, towards sustainable, inclusive and resource-efficient Cultural Heritage (CH) solutions, towards sustainable, inclusive, stakeholders participation, achieved through progress monitoring, self-reflection activities, peer-learning study visits, and the provision of online learning materials to facilitate access to the project results.

The capacity-building steps extend beyond the application of innovative technology, focusing on gaps in implementation and integration in practice and policy. Paying special attention to make the best use of available resources, which include human, technological, financial, and administrative resources, the capacity-building programme is designed with an acknowledgement of the gaps and challenges, as well as the means to exploit learning and skill-upgradation opportunities. As the project seeks to adapt to 'next-generation solutions', it also brings the need to upgrade the skills and knowledge of next-generation managers, heritage custodians, and stakeholders.

Capacity building is essential to empower stakeholders with the knowledge and competencies required to sustain, scale up, and replicate innovative practices, while also ensuring long-term ownership of the outcomes. This is envisioned through three main activities: **1) A peer learning scheme** which creates a shared space for the exchange of knowledge, experiences, fostering mutual support, and accelerating the transfer of good practices across regions and disciplines; **2) E-learning modules** where the INHERIT generated knowledge is capitalised and disseminated granting an easier entry point to project results for possible replicators, and **3) Periodic journals** or, in other words, reflective reports designed for the INHERIT pilot partners to document and share their progress, challenges, and insights. Together, they strengthen collaborative networks, encourage innovation through shared insights, and help align diverse stakeholders around common goals for the sustainability of cultural heritage. This deliverable presents all three activities for the Capacity Building Programme for Cultural Heritage, documenting methods and outcomes, but focuses primarily on the peer-learning scheme.

For the peer-learning scheme undertaken with INHERIT pilots, external Learning Partners were inducted into the programme. These Learning Partners were selected and inducted through a dedicated call, which sought practices and case studies as demonstration sites that match the interests and needs of the pilots. The case studies of Zero Waste House (Slovenia), Paphos Gate (Cyprus), Green Tensegrity Installations in the Neighbourhoods of Eleusis (Greece), Old Ironworks Project (Slovenia), Baraccano Historical Complex (Italy), and ULTEAM (Cisco Headquarters) (France) were included in the peer learning programme and visited by the eight INHERIT pilots, hosted by our generous and expert Learning Partners: Zero Waste Žalec, The Cyprus Institute, HeritACT project led by University of Patras, Institut Iskriwa, University of Bologna, and Arte Charpentier, respectively. The INHERIT Pilots-partner organisations, namely, REGEA, BOUYGUES, ELLET, RPR, FASADA, CARTIF, UU, and IBB visited these sites with representatives from their respective organisations, as well as

with the associated local authorities. The peer learning activities were thus not limited to the project partners but also extended to local partners, enabling long-term learning, knowledge transfer, and collaboration.

The e-learning modules, currently under development, are designed to collect and organize the knowledge generated throughout the project, providing easy online access for a diverse array of stakeholders. Each package is tailored to specific personas and addresses the skills identified as most relevant during workshops, including gaps in competencies highlighted by the project's activities. Tools, methods, and project results are being collected under the three modules, namely: 1) Smart planning and management for CH buildings; 2) Technical competences for next-generation solutions in CH buildings; 3) Beautiful, sustainable, and inclusive CH buildings.

The INHERIT Journals are a tool for pilot partners to collect and share experiences, support learning, and facilitate self-reflection and exchange. The journals also help highlight how pilot activities align with the project's objectives and New European Bauhaus (NEB) values, allowing partners to adjust their trajectory, if necessary, plan upcoming activities, and reflect on the broader impact on communities and cultural heritage. The format of the Journals, initially planned on a monthly basis, evolved and adapted to the needs of partners and the project phases, as this activity is expected to run until the end of the project in early 2027.

In conclusion, the INHERIT capacity building programme offers a comprehensive framework that addresses the needs of pilots through peer learning, online modules, and documented knowledge. All these elements together strengthen competencies and foster collaboration, ensuring that innovative solutions for cultural heritage buildings are scalable, replicable, and, ultimately, sustainable in the long run.

This report is intended for practitioners, experts, and local actors working in the field of heritage conservation who are keen on adapting and integrating INHERIT's methodology and solutions.

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We also thank our INHERIT Pilot coordinators: REGEA, BOUYGUES, ELLET, RPR, FASADA, CARTIF, UU, and IBB, who played an instrumental role in executing the activities of peer learning, e-learning workshops, from engaging in consultations to executing the study visits with their associated local actors and providing a thorough documentation of the study visit. Special thanks to BOUYGUES and CARTIF, who also supported the task of inducting Learning Partners through their extensive networks.

This exercise offered many valuable lessons. It was a pro bono scheme with no financial benefits, requiring the Partners to invest time and effort in planning the agenda and hosting the INHERIT pilots. Although the peer learning and partnership activity was undertaken without the provision of financial incentives, the success of its execution carries an important message: knowledge and learning transcend constraints and flourish through collaboration and a network. Most importantly, it demonstrated that learning and the sharing of knowledge have lasting benefits. They strengthen professional networks, enhance technological expertise through exchange, and broaden horizons through the flow of ideas and information.

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction to the INHERIT Project

The introduction and integration of technological innovation have been driving a shift in how cultural heritage is approached, both in its restoration and long-term preservation. Building on this momentum, the EU-funded project **INHERIT: Next Generation Solutions for Sustainable, Inclusive, Resource-efficient, and Resilient Cultural Heritage** was launched with the aim of generating strategies and pilots for sustainable, inclusive, resource-efficient, and resilient Cultural Heritage (Hereafter CH). With the objective of addressing challenges concerning the preservation, restoration, and management of CH buildings, it also aims to further foster the ethics and goals of the European Green Deal and the New European Bauhaus (Hereafter NEB), while preserving the buildings' CH value.

The overall vision of INHERIT is to create a systematic methodology, accompanied by leading-edge Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), such as Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI) and (big) data analytics, and associated social/behavioural practices, towards sustainable, inclusive and resource-efficient CH solutions. INHERIT will enable socially innovative and economically viable interventions at different urban levels (buildings, city/ neighbourhood), covering all relevant aspects of the heritage-built environment's life cycle across four areas with eleven technological solutions:

- Data collection and sharing
- Design and renovation
- Monitoring, operation, and management
- Preservation and maintenance

Figure 1: The four main categories of INHERIT services

The next sections present the services and pilots, concluding with an overview of which service is included in each pilot.

1.1.1 INHERIT Services

Data collection and sharing tools:

- **S0: Building Smartification: Heritage buildings Smartification & Data Exchange Platform**

INHERIT proposes a Smartification and Data Exchange Platform for heritage buildings. The platform integrates components, including sensors and monitoring systems, to collect and share data about the heritage building's condition and performance. These components are then integrated with data analytics and Machine Learning algorithms to analyze and interpret the collected data.

Design and renovation services:

- **S01: AR/VR Interfaces: Interactive screen use, Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction**

AR-based maintenance and renovation is tested to reduce maintenance and renovation time as well as to improve work quality. AR-based human-machine interaction supports on-the-job training, while VR-based pre-intervention planning is used to evaluate a part of the demo sites.

- **S02: DREEM: Modelling and simulation environment**

The building's modelling is performed by Dynamic high-Resolution dEmand-sidE Management (DREEM). Modelling exercises evaluate the performance of different conventional measures in terms of their long-term energy savings. Moreover, energy technology packages are simulated and compared in terms of energy performance.

- **S03: MCDA: Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning**

Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) methods and robustness analysis frameworks are applied to identify optimal renovation strategies. The impact of different renovation packages is assessed, supporting stakeholders in the decision-making process to achieve optimal financing.

Monitoring, operation, and management services

- **S04: IEQ: Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) and thermal comfort optimisation**

Data-driven models measure and quantify thermal comfort while balancing visual, acoustic comfort, and indoor air quality. The service ensures users' feelings of well-being in indoor spaces.

- **S05: Forecasting and Management: Energy forecasting and intelligent management**

Artificial intelligence (AI) data-driven tools and machine learning/deep learning (ML/DL) models are leveraged for consumption forecasting, energy profiling, and performance monitoring and benchmarking. New optimisation algorithms are also being tested.

- **S06: Digital Twin: Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring and management**

INHERIT designs and implements a Digital Twin for heritage facilities that integrates the Heritage Building Information Models (H-BIM) with real-time monitoring data and energy

models. It helps identify energy inefficiencies, comfort issues, and preventive maintenance needs.

- **S07: Insight and Patterns: Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns**

A tool for monitoring visitors has been developed. The service promotes comfort and safety for visitors in cases of emergency evacuation, while preserving accessibility and inclusiveness. The service relies on sensors and indoor cameras.

Preservation and maintenance services

- **S08: Spatial Information: Preventive maintenance with H-BIM**

The data derived from the inspection of cultural heritage buildings are combined into an H-BIM collaborative model. A spatial information structure then allows the exploration and analysis of (re)use interventions in various scenarios upon a multidimensional analysis.

- **S09: Geographic Information System: GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance**

INHERIT provides a clustering GIS (Geographic Information System) service that uses AI to analyse and classify images of cultural heritage buildings. This enables the digital mapping of cultural heritage sites and uses spatial analysis techniques to group similar buildings.

- **S10: Climate Scenarios: Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios**

The most relevant impacts affecting cultural heritage buildings, according to the most prominent climate hazards, are assessed. Relevant indicators from the assessment and monitoring framework are then calculated to prevent damages.

1.1.2 INHERIT Pilots

The abovementioned solutions are tested in eight pilots from eight different countries with the aim of executing the project objectives in the following historic buildings:

Pilot 1: City Administration Headquarters - Jastrebarsko, Croatia; Partner: REGEA

The City Administration Headquarters of Jastrebarsko is located in an area protected by the Cultural Heritage Regulation. The structure was built in a classical architectural style, typical of the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th centuries, with pronounced profiles and ornaments on the main street façade.

Pilot 2: Cité du goût - Noisiel, France; Partner: BOUYGUES

Located in Noisiel, near Paris, this former industrial complex, now a listed building, will undergo a major transformation. Spanning approximately 34,000 m², the site will be redeveloped into a dynamic mixed-use space called “La Cité du goût”.

The project will include family housing, a student residence, a graduate school, a hotel, and cultural venues around gastronomy.

Pilot 3: ELLET building in Tripodon street - Athens, Greece; Partner: ELLET

The ELLET building is located on Tripodon Street, right under Athens' Acropolis. Tripodon Street was once the centre of the city's political and cultural life, and it was home to many of the city's important public buildings, including the Agora (marketplace) and the Acropolis. The ELLET building dates back to the early 19th century and has two floors. The ground floor is used for seminars and events. The upstairs floor hosts offices.

Pilot 4: Ave Sol Concert Hall - Riga, Latvia; Partner: RPR

The Ave Sol concert hall is part of the historical centre of Riga. Built between 1780 and 1785 as St. Peter and Pavel Church, the building was then restored and reconstructed between 1980 and 1987. It was used as a church until 1940, when the territory of Latvia was occupied by the Red Army, and military units were located in the Citadel. In 1977, the building was handed over to the Riga Culture administration to establish a concert hall.

Pilot 5: Social Residential Building in Gdynia - Gdynia, Poland; Partner: FASADA

The social residential building in Gdynia was built in 1928. Owned by the City of Gdynia, it is managed by the Municipal Register of Monuments, under the supervision of the Municipal Conservator of Cultural Heritage. The building needs renovation to minimise the use of energy and improve management systems.

Pilot 6: Monastery 'Ntra. Sra. del Prado' - Valladolid, Spain; Sweden; Partner: CARTIF

The monastery is located near the Pisuerga River and next to the Parliament in Valladolid. The building was declared a national, historical, and artistic monument in 1877. In the 1980s, a complete restoration was carried out, converting the old monastery into the offices of the Castilla y Leon Regional Government. The building currently serves as the headquarters of the Ministry of Culture, Tourism, and Sports, as well as the Ministry of Education.

Pilot 7: City of Visby, UNESCO World Heritage Site - Gotland, Sweden; Partner: UU

This whole historic district is a UNESCO World Heritage Site. Visby is a unique example of a northern European medieval walled trading town that is well-preserved. Thanks to access to district heating, the Visby pilot provides an opportunity to balance demand-side solutions with green supply-side ones.

Pilot 8: Ahmet Piriştina İzmir City Archive and Museum (APİKAM) - İzmir, Türkiye; Partner: IBB

APİKAM has significant historical value, as it is the first fire station built by İzmir Metropolitan Municipality following the Great Fire of İzmir in 1922. The building consists of three floors and hosts municipality offices, a museum exhibition hall, two seminar halls for 140+ people, a city archive research hall, İzmir National Library Foundation, a local newspaper archive, and a book-café in the annexe. With all these functions, the building has the capacity to attract over 50,000 visitors annually.

1.1.3 INHERIT Pilots and Proposed Services

The table below shows the services proposed for each of the eight INHERIT pilot sites, indicating where specific services are being tested.

Table 1: INHERIT Services for all pilots

INHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	INHERIT Pilots							
			Pilot 1: REGEA: Jastrebarsko, Croatia	Pilot 2: BOUYGUES: Noisiel, France	Pilot 3: ELLET: Athens, Greece	Pilot 4: RPR: Riga, Latvia	Pilot 5: FASADA: Gdynia, Poland	Pilot 6: CARTIF: Valladolid, Spain	Pilot 7: UU: Visby, Gotland, Sweden	Pilot 8: IBB: Izmir, Turkey
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1	-	-	-	-	✓	✓		-
	Modelling & simulation environment	S.2	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	✓	✓
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Monitoring, Management operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimization	S.4	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-	-
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5	✓	-	✓	-	-	-	✓	-
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	✓	-
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓

1.2 Significance of the Project

1.2.1 Need for Sustainable, Inclusive, and Resource-Efficient Cultural Heritage Solutions

Historic buildings across European cities, towns, and villages are considered hallmarks of their cultural heritage and a unique reflection of their social identity. However, currently, about 35% of the EU's buildings are over 50 years old, and almost 75% of the building stock is energy inefficient.

With climate change posing an increasingly urgent threat to the environment, including historic buildings, it becomes necessary to adopt an improved approach to all refurbishment actions in CH buildings. In this context, resource efficiency refers to the ability to use materials, energy, and financial resources in a way that minimizes waste, reduces environmental impact, and prolongs the lifespan of existing structures. For cultural heritage buildings, this means prioritizing low-impact materials, reducing operational energy demand, optimizing maintenance cycles, and ensuring that interventions preserve as much of the original fabric as possible, thereby maximizing the effective use of existing embodied energy. Moreover, the renovation of existing buildings has the potential to lead to significant energy savings, possibly reducing the EU's total energy consumption by 5-6% and lowering CO₂ emissions by about 5% ([European Commission, 2019](#)). Furthermore, [3ENCULT](#), an EU Seventh Framework Programme project, posited that in order for historic buildings to survive, they would have to be maintained as a living space to ensure their sustained functionality. Optimal energy-efficient measures in built heritage would contribute to its structural protection, increase users' comfort, and reduce energy demand - potentially lowering the risk of energy poverty.

INHERIT's holistic approach is sustainable, inclusive, and resource-efficient CH solutions that promote energy efficiency, sustainability, inclusiveness, and resource efficiency. This is further guided by NEB principles, which emphasize that CH need to adapt to contemporary challenges, using a life-centred and human-centred perspective following the three pillars of sustainability, inclusion, and beauty. Mainstreaming these measures requires targeted policies for energy efficiency and integration of renewable energies, and the adaptive reuse of historic buildings can be a driver for circularity in the context of built environments; although decision-makers and practitioners may lack knowledge of its environmental benefits, capacities, as well as the tools necessary to enable this socio-technological transition. INHERIT aims to bridge this gap by employing a multi-stakeholder approach to co-planning renovation and creating an evidence base of the requisite tools and solutions to optimise and scale the management of CH buildings. The capacity building programme outlined in this report contributes further to the mainstreaming and replicability of these tools and solutions. It aims to include reflection on resources needed for various CH sites, the sense and meaning of CH, and the capability to change the way of working towards more circular, renewable supply chains.

1.2.2 Integration of Technical Expertise with Cultural and Societal Perspectives

The need for integration of technical expertise with cultural and societal perspectives arises directly from the objectives and methodology of INHERIT; the project looks beyond CH buildings as long-standing, physical structures alone, but seeks to deeply embed the CH stock within the local context of its socio-cultural environment in the long term. Ensuring the multifaceted preservation and restoration of these sites requires the adoption of scientific and technological innovations that are enriched with societal perspectives and driven by a collaboratively designed approach.

INHERIT's technical methodology conducts digitally based and heritage-friendly inspections, providing cost-effective and viable solutions for work on historic buildings. Eleven ICT-based services are applied to eight pilot cultural heritage sites for data collection and to support the renovation,

preservation, management, and monitoring of the buildings. Retrofit and green technologies are key focal points, providing energy-efficient solutions that align with the EU's climate neutrality goals. At the same time, these solutions would not reach the desired outcomes of enhancing social accessibility and inclusiveness in CH sites if implemented in isolation from social and cultural considerations. To enable this, INHERIT's tailor-made research and co-creation approach, which incorporates stakeholder feedback throughout the project's lifetime, potentially creates new adaptive models of engagement and sets the stage for transdisciplinary collaboration.

The amalgamation of insights from the technical experts of the project consortium - across information technology, smart energy performance, Augmented Reality/Virtual Reality (AR/VR), design and preservation, CH management, along with the experts on co-creation, stakeholder engagement, NEB values, and the social sciences and humanities (SSH), places INHERIT in an ideal position to contribute innovative technological solutions that are technologically robust, user-centred, socially inclusive, and culturally sensitive in the European context. The project's capacity-building programme, through study visits, e-learning materials, and periodic reflexive reports, aims to make these solutions accessible and easily replicable, bridging the gap between technical expertise and socio-cultural sensitivity to address the diverse needs of stakeholders, including heritage managers, building owners, technology providers, and others.

The following chapters of this report first elaborate on the INHERIT capacity building programme as a whole - its context, approach, target audience, and expected outcomes (Chapter 2) - then examine its individual components in detail. These include the peer-learning scheme carried out through on-site study visits (Chapter 3), the ongoing development of e-learning material (Chapter 4), and the periodic journals produced throughout the project (Chapter 5), which support both reflection and practical application of the previous components. Finally, the report concludes with a summary of the key takeaways. (Chapter 6).

2. Capacity Building Programme

The capacity building programme in INHERIT is grounded in the understanding that cultural heritage, both tangible and intangible, represents a reservoir of creativity, well-being, identity, and knowledge that can support current and future challenges. As the historic building stock is heterogeneous and requires differentiated renovation strategies and targeted policies, strengthening capacities is essential for mainstreaming energy efficiency, sustainability, inclusivity, and resource efficiency while preserving cultural heritage value. Guided by European standards and NEB policy frameworks, the programme responds to the need for integrated, people-centred, and evidence-based approaches that balance energy performance with heritage preservation, supported by knowledge codification, dissemination, and peer learning.

This chapter outlines how INHERIT addresses these needs through its capacity-building programme. It first presents the method and approach, followed by the three core tasks: peer-learning study visits, e-learning modules and webinars, and pilots' reflective journals, which together form the structure of the learning scheme. It then introduces the target groups engaged in the programme and concludes with the expected outcomes, highlighting how INHERIT strengthens skills, confidence, and knowledge to support sustainable cultural heritage across diverse European contexts.

2.1 Context

Cultural heritage, both tangible and intangible, can be understood as a reservoir of creativity, well-being, identity, and knowledge that is useful in overcoming present and future challenges. The cultural value attributed to our traditional and historic buildings reflects our identity as communities and individuals, playing a crucial role in both urban and rural domains. The historic building stock is heterogeneous, comprising buildings from different time periods, constructed with various materials and in diverse ways, and adhering to diverse architectural ideals. This situation highlights the need for differentiated renovation strategies and targeted policies throughout the life cycle of the heritage-built environment, promoting energy efficiency, sustainability, inclusivity, and resource efficiency while preserving the cultural heritage value.

European standards and **NEB policy frameworks** addressing the preservation and restoration of cultural heritage emphasise the importance of approaches that balance energy performance and use with heritage preservation, focusing on sustainability, aesthetics, and inclusion. **The European Framework for Action on Cultural Heritage** emphasises that the trajectory towards a future-oriented, people-centred approach to cultural heritage requires integrated EU policies, evidence-based decision-making, and multi-stakeholder cooperation to design and implement effective programmes. Case studies from **Build Up** and **HiBERAtlas** offer insights into the implementation of technologies, methodologies, and tools, as well as research on energy efficiency in historic buildings. They provide an overview of real-life outcomes, lessons learned, and best practices.

The pivot towards these areas of focus across cultural heritage sites in the EU, while mainstreaming next-generation solutions for cultural heritage buildings, requires practitioners to bridge technological innovation with cultural sensitivity and social engagement. The nascent stages of this pivot require strengthening capacities to mainstream this approach, driven by knowledge codification, dissemination, and peer learning. INHERIT seeks to prioritise this by creating a capacity-building programme addressing heritage operators and stakeholders to support sustainable CH with particular focus on the NEB community and projects, and will work on policy recommendations towards sustainable heritage. This includes heritage managers and building operators, technology providers in the construction sector, public authorities, research organisations, and citizens. to support sustainable CH with particular focus on NEB community and projects, and will work on policy recommendations towards sustainable heritage. Through its project design, INHERIT integrates the social, scientific, and technological dimensions of cultural heritage preservation. It also recognizes their reciprocal interactions, which form the foundation of its capacity-building content. The knowledge disseminated builds on a repository of technical expertise in next-generation solutions for cultural heritage buildings, as well as success stories.

Through the peer-learning exchanges taking place across the eight pilots, the objective is to:

- strengthen the confidence of local cultural-heritage operators and their stakeholders through dedicated, innovative capacity-building programmes
- develop e-learning modules and webinars in which generated knowledge can be tested, capitalised, and disseminated for potential replicators
- prepare the outcomes for upscaling, exploitation, and policy recommendations; and
- contribute to the development of standards for heritage buildings

The project's wide geographical coverage aims to support its replicability in different socio-economic, cultural, and political contexts, thereby maximising the impact of INHERIT across Europe.

2.2 Method and Approach

Within the INHERIT project, one of the core objectives focuses on capacity building, policy support, and standardisation. The capacity building activities for project partners and other stakeholders include progress monitoring, self-reflection exercises, peer-learning study visits, and the development of online learning materials to ensure broad access to project results. This deliverable brings together these elements as part of the INHERIT learning scheme and capacity-building programme, which is organised into three tasks described below.

2.2.1 Task A: Synergies and Peer-Learning

Eight study visits were organised to selected project sites, hosted by Learning Partners who have demonstrated experience in CH preservation and transformation, as well as in applying NEB values on the ground. Following a Call for Learning Partners, an exhaustive needs assessment and a matchmaking exercise were conducted, and the pilots were paired with the most suitable partners. The INHERIT pilots visited one site each to explore the innovative cultural heritage conservation projects proposed by the Learning Partners. These projects, as case studies, were related to the three core themes identified along the lines of human- and life-centred approaches and NEB

principles, serving as examples of circular and renewable practices. During the visit, each pilot documented the case study based on factual information provided by the Learning Partners and reflected on the adaptability and lessons learnt in the process for their own site. In this manner, the study visit ensured exposure to a new case and provided a platform for reflection and knowledge exchange. The documentation forms are synthesised to provide a model for capacity building and peer learning exchange facilitation.

2.2.2 Task B: INHERIT E-Learning Modules and Webinars

As a next step to disseminate the learnings from the study visits and the peer learning scheme and further promote the knowledge produced in-house, a dedicated INHERIT e-learning curriculum will be developed on CH conservation. This will include concepts, methodologies, instruments, and case study examples - tailored to pilot stakeholders and wider audiences.

As a first step towards designing these e-learning modules, a workshop was carried out in two stages. The first stage included a 'personas exercise,' which gathered information through role-play and imagination from pilots and stakeholders to gauge the various situations where training, capacity building, and peer learning are required. This information was then distilled into needs and upvoting. In a second stage, this exercise was further refined through an in-person workshop designed to integrate both soft and technical skills for the e-learning programme. To this end, consortium partners identified relevant skills, which were later divided into the topics of the three e-learning modules, respectively covering:

- Smart planning and management for CH buildings
- Technical competences for next-generation solutions in CH buildings
- Beautiful, sustainable, and inclusive CH buildings
- Each module launch will be accompanied by a webinar

2.2.3 Task C: INHERIT Pilots' Journals for Future-Oriented Reflection and Monitoring

In parallel, pilot partners have periodically completed reflective reports to document and share their progress, challenges, and insights. The aim of the journals is to capture future-oriented steps, record experiences, and reflect the lessons learned from the process. This tool supports learning and serves self-reflection and exchange. It also helps monitor and highlight how pilot partner activities align with the project's objectives, the NEB values, and the broader impact on communities and heritage towards an open, accessible, inclusive, resilient, and low-emission CH. Since the project began, the pilots have updated the journals on a monthly basis. In the second year of the project, the journals are updated every three months to capture the ongoing interventions more effectively, focusing on tangible transformations in social, environmental, economic, or cultural dimensions. Finally, the journals also provide a platform for sharing community updates, tracking changes in the involvement and participation of local stakeholders, emerging dynamics, events held, and outreach activities.

2.3 Target Groups and Audience

The capacity building programme is primarily designed for the eight INHERIT pilots and their selected cultural heritage sites, located in Croatia, France, Greece, Latvia, Poland, Spain, Sweden, and Türkiye. The institutions associated with these pilots, namely, REGEA, BOUYGUES, ELLET, RPR, FASADA, CARTIF, UU, and IBB are the beneficiaries of the activities and the available funds for this task. Through this project funding, study visits to the case studies of the Learning partners are possible. Along with the representatives of the pilot institutions, in some cases, the local authorities associated with them have also travelled, which further marks the success of this task, as it is not limited to only the project's beneficiaries. The e-learning webinars are open events for all practitioners, targeting experts in project management, next-generation solutions, technology, and adaptation to cultural and historic buildings, as well as the broader network of NEB initiatives.

2.4 Task Cycle and Milestones

The capacity-building programme spans the entire project duration, with various tasks interlinked and tied to key milestones. The following outlines the overall cycle of the task, including its connections to other tasks within the project and with other partners.

Table 2: Task Cycle of the Capacity Building Programme

INHERIT Capacity Building, Policy Support and Standardisation															
Tasks and activities	Project timeline and duration														
	Oct 2023	Dec 2023	Mar 2024	June 2024	Sept 2024	Dec 2024	Mar 2025	June 2025	Sept 2025	Dec 2025	Mar 2026	June 2026	Sept 2026	Dec 2026	Mar 2027
	M 01	M 03	M 06	M 09	M 12	M 15	M 18	M 21	M 24	M 27	M 30	M 33	M 36	M 39	M 42

T 6.1: INHERIT learning scheme and capacity building programme

2.5 Expected Outcomes

The outcome of the capacity building programme in INHERIT can be described as the creation of a structured, scalable, and replicable framework for enhancing the skills, confidence, and knowledge of cultural heritage managers and their stakeholders. Concretely, it delivers:

- **Empowered local actors:** Operators and stakeholders of the pilot sites gain knowledge and technical capacity through peer learning, mentoring, and innovative training methods
- **Expanding networks:** Through interactions with external practitioners and institutions, there is an opportunity to grow and expand professional networks for future collaborations
- **Knowledge resources:** E-learning modules, webinars, and other digital tools make the knowledge generated accessible, promote interoperability and replication opportunities, both within the project as well as external users
- **Replication and upscaling:** By systematising the lessons learned, the programme prepares outcomes that can be replicated in other CH contexts, aligned with policy recommendations and broader European standards

INHERIT's aim is to develop a capacity-building programme for the durable yet flexible transformation and energy resilience of communities built around CH assets, supplemented by policy recommendations for a sustainable built environment, and coupled with policy dialogue to enhance the stakeholder forum and bring it to the EU level.

In short, the outcome is not limited to one-time training but also involves the establishment of an enduring capacity-building ecosystem that links local practice, peer exchange, digital learning, and policy alignment, ensuring that historic buildings become models of sustainability, resilience, accessibility, and inclusiveness. This creates a foundation that extends well beyond the pilot sites, embedding the NEB values into cultural heritage practices across Europe.

3. Task A: Peer Learning Scheme: Conceptualisation to Implementation

Peer learning and knowledge exchange form the essence of the INHERIT community and its vision. The project’s peer learning scheme was conceptualised with the objective of fostering knowledge sharing through a capacity-building programme for cultural heritage managers and stakeholders. Through curated study visits, insights into next-generation solutions to improve the energy and resource consumption, climate resilience, accessibility, and inclusiveness of historic buildings across eleven of INHERIT’s services were showcased. The following key stakeholders played a critical role in this bilateral learning exchange, namely:

- **Learning Partners:** Sector experts who have successfully delivered and/or are continuing the process to attain the goals of NEB, directly or indirectly through their respective projects across the EU.
- **Pilots:** Representatives of the eight pilot sites that would serve as a testbed for INHERIT’s solutions.

The programme was active for 23 months (January 2024 to November 2025) and carried out in four phases. The phases included conceptualisation, assessment of needs, a call for Learning Partners, matchmaking and consultations, study visits, and documentation and synthesis of results. The following sections provide an overview of the activities undertaken in four phases and their objectives, as well as the methods adopted to achieve the task’s goals.

Figure 2: The four phases of the peer learning scheme

Figure 3: The outline and timeline of the task of the Peer Learning Scheme

3.1 Phase 1: Needs Assessment of the INHERIT Pilots

3.1.1 Needs Assessments of INHERIT Pilots

INHERIT’s focus on mainstreaming the capacities of cultural heritage managers and stakeholders in the pilot projects required a clear understanding of the knowledge they could contribute. It was equally important to identify their learning preferences in relation to the services they would test and the areas where they might need additional support. This step ensured that the learning schemes were curated in a manner that is targeted to the needs of the pilots, enabling relevant skill-sharing across technical, managerial, and NEB elements. ICLEI led the workshop with INHERIT Pilots for a needs assessment exercise, which further supported the evaluation and matchmaking phase, wherein Learning Partners were assigned to pilots that shared similar themes/philosophies, as well as those that could best support the needs of the pilot sites.

The workshop provided an introduction to the peer learning scheme, its objectives, and the plan of action. The pilots were then consulted together, where they added their wishes and needs to the project. The inputs were then collated in a matrix and categorized into four main categories: technical needs, managerial needs, NEB-related information, and case studies. Since the project is based on the use of next-generation technology, all pilots expressed a desire to learn about technology through peer learning. Needs were also observed in some cases, particularly in the managerial and NEB-related aspects.

It was noted that the needs and learning objectives of the pilots were primarily technical, largely centred around gaining insights into the resource optimization and next-generation solutions for cultural heritage buildings, while also preserving their cultural heritage. The pilots also expressed interest in learning from examples of similar solutions that have been replicated in other sites. This exercise largely enabled ICLEI to better understand the needs of the pilots and match them with Learning Partners who could offer insights on these areas in their respective case study sites.

Table 3: Outcome of the Needs Assessment Exercise led by ICLEI

Pilot	Needs/ expectations from the Peer learning scheme	Type of Requirement			
		Technical	Managerial	NEB-related	Examples
Pilot 1: REGEA: Jastrebarsko, Croatia	How to ensure cultural heritage improvements/renovation while preserving the heritage, yet at the same time ensure improvements and serve modern-day purposes		✓	✓	
	Bringing the purpose of the building/area to the community			✓	
	Advanced technology use	✓			
	Similar example of a large-scale approach- area, not just a building				✓

Pilot	Needs/ expectations from the Peer learning scheme	Type of Requirement			
		Technical	Managerial	NEB-related	Examples
Pilot 2: BOUYGUES: Noisiel, France	How to transform a CH building into a cost-effective manner for final investors?	✓			
	How to take into account different current regulations (energy, Carbon, accessibility, biodiversity) in relation to cultural regulation?			✓	
	How to reach high energy efficiency while being limited by the "cultural heritage" of the building	✓			
Pilot 3: ELLET: Athens, Greece	Finding ways to better integrate NEB values into our NGO's actions			✓	✓
	Learn how to better operate the building from an energy perspective	✓			
	How to use advanced technology to monitor the energy performance of the building	✓	✓		
	To optimise the energy performance of the building while maintaining its cultural identity	✓		✓	
Pilot 4: RPR: Riga, Latvia	How to manage a site if there are two owners for a building		✓		
	Improve energy efficiency in CH, taking into consideration all the restrictions to change windows, doors, etc.	✓			
	How to save CH if it is intensively used every day by visitors and other stakeholders.			✓	
	How to create a common understanding about building management if there are several stakeholders involved with different opinions.		✓		
	How to use Renewable Energy Sources RES in CH? What kind of innovative solutions are available for RES in CH?	✓			
Pilot 5: FASADA: Gdynia, Poland	Which technologies can bring the greatest benefits to resource efficiency?	✓			
	How to compromise between users' needs and conservation constraints			✓	
	How VR/AR technology can support and facilitate renovation	✓			
	How to get an H-BIM useful and affordable	✓			
Pilot 6: CARTIF: Valladolid, Spain	How to get an H-BIM useful and affordable	✓			
	How to face preventive conservation digitally	✓			
Pilot 7: UU: Visby, Gotland, Sweden	What type of digital tools can be used?	✓			
	Energy consumption monitoring techniques	✓			
	What type of practices exist out there to shift energy loads	✓			
Pilot 8: IBB: Izmir, Turkey	Create opportunities for a more stimulating exchange of ideas				✓
	Need for support in finding the most suitable energy-efficient solution for the building	✓			
	Get ideas for more efficient operation of the building	✓			
	Getting more acquainted with NEB and its values.				✓
	Gaining new perspectives on the multifunctional programme of the pilot.	✓	✓		

3.2 Phase 2: Conceptualisation and Launch of Peer Learning Scheme

3.2.1 New European Bauhaus and its Connection to the Peer Learning Scheme

At its core, INHERIT's Peer Learning Scheme aimed to stimulate and facilitate synergies and peer learning between eight pilots and NEB-related projects on the preservation and transformation of Cultural Heritage (CH) and related areas. This was a crucial phase, as it laid the foundation for mainstreaming solutions related to the preservation and restoration of CH, and further supporting their replicability and scalability. NEB connects the EU Green Deal to our living spaces and experiences, calling for the adaptation of its principles and objectives into an accessible, culturally rich, and people-oriented initiative. It promotes the creation of attractive, sustainable, and inclusive spaces across Europe through its three pillars: sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics (Refer to Figure 4). However, the adoption of these NEB pillars to promote a 'think-do tank' that simultaneously manifests a design lab and an accelerator requires interdisciplinary learning, channelled through networking and knowledge sharing.

Figure 4: Pillars of the New European Bauhaus

3.2.2 Themes Adopted in the Peer Learning Scheme

A central aspect of the Learning Scheme was that each of the study visits hosted by the Learning Partner was assigned to **one or more of the following INHERIT themes**, which formed the basis of the exercise. Pilots and Learning Partners that were aligned on thematic ideologies were paired together to ensure maximal synergy and cross-learning. Figure 5 gives an overview of the themes of the task.

Figure 5: Themes of the peer learning scheme adopted from INHERIT’s project objectives

3.2.1.1 Theme 1: Human-Centred and Life-Centred Approaches to Cultural Heritage

This theme focuses on sustainable interventions in the cultural heritage building stock, employing two essential approaches. The human-centred approach focuses primarily on the aspects of participation and engagement of communities, local regeneration, and social innovation. It also assesses and addresses the socio-economic impacts of the interventions and facilitates accessibility through ergonomic principles (E.g., barrier-free access, elderly-friendly). The life-centred approaches cater to nature-based solutions coupled with interventions in historic buildings. These provide opportunities to integrate environmentally sustainable elements into the preservation of cultural heritage and access to associated mutual benefits (E.g., introducing terrace gardens, façade gardens, and indoor vegetal patches), as well as the use of eco-friendly and natural materials for retrofitting, among others. The case studies surrounding these interventions may highlight one or more issues related to the preservation of material authenticity, minimising negative impacts due to the introduction of vegetation, alteration, or loss of heritage values, addressing challenges of regulations, and matters of heritage preservation.

3.2.1.2 Theme 2: Resource Efficiency and Circularity

Resource efficiency and circularity in cultural heritage, aligned with the principles of the NEB, involve optimising resource use and promoting a circular economy within heritage preservation. This entails minimising waste, maximising material lifespan, and embracing sustainable practices throughout the lifecycle of cultural heritage assets. By integrating these principles, conservation efforts can reduce environmental impact, conserve resources, and promote the sustainable management of cultural heritage in line with the ethos of the NEB. Resource efficiency and circularity may address one or more goals, including developing a novel framework for inspecting, monitoring, and assessing CH, as well as creating tailor-made, cost-effective solutions. They also relate to design

choices involving durable, locally sourced, low-impact materials, and flexibility achieved through modular construction techniques, adaptable interior layouts, and future-proofing measures such as wiring and infrastructure for renewable energy systems. In addition, they address the life cycle cost (LCC) of interventions by minimising waste generation and maximising material reuse and recycling.

3.2.1.3 Theme 3: Capacity for Innovation and Transdisciplinary and Contemporary Approaches

Technological innovation in historic conservation involves the application of cutting-edge technology to enhance preservation efforts and effectively employ innovative technology through transdisciplinary approaches for conservation practices. This entails acquiring expertise in new tools and methods, integrating technology into conservation practices, fostering a culture of experimentation, and collaborating to share knowledge and resources. By enhancing their innovation capacity, professionals can maximise the benefits of technology to address challenges and ensure the sustainable preservation of cultural heritage. Furthermore, the capacity for social innovations is relevant, including bottom-up initiatives, empowering new governance models, co-creation, and co-implementation of change.

3.3 Phase 3: Introduction of Learning Partners and Matchmaking with Pilots

3.3.1 Call for Learning Partners

Refer to Annex A: Call for Learning Partners and Application Form

Once the needs of the pilot partners were identified, ICLEI initiated the Call for Learning Partners, an application that invited practitioners, institutions, and organisations to share their work and participate in a non-monetary learning scheme. The learning scheme aimed to engage capacity development programmes and foster knowledge exchange, cooperation, or collaboration to enhance learning outcomes through partnerships among professionals, institutions, and organisations. An important prerequisite for the application process for the Learning Partners to host study visits was to align with the following criteria. This would enable a structured learning process that would be best suited to the needs of the pilots.

- **Project Status:** Completed projects and/or ongoing projects or research along the lines of the pilot cases.
- **Case Typology:** Public buildings having uses such as administrative offices, museums and archives, concert halls, commercial buildings, and/or residential buildings, social housing, and/or adaptive reuse projects.
- **Geographical Representation:** Members of the EU.
- **Type of entities applying:** Projects in relation to the NEB movement, which includes but is not restricted to winning and participating entries. Beyond this, architecture and engineering professionals, experts, researchers, institutions deal with and having expertise and delivered successful projects. These projects may include historic preservation, adaptive reuse, cross-

cutting technology and energy efficiency, digital tools and technologies and relevant skills and expertise in cultural heritage and institutions dealing with and having expertise and delivering going projects along the lines of the pilot cases.

- **Project Characteristics:** Addressing one or more core values of the NEB values – sustainability, aesthetics, inclusiveness, and working principles - participatory process, multi-level engagement, and a transdisciplinary approach.
- **Thematic and NEB relevance:** The application process required the Learning Partners to rank the themes that aligned the most with their case studies, and further, to which these preferences were matched against the pilots whose sites reflected similar thematic foci. This was a critical step in identifying the Learning Partners who would be best suited for INHERIT's peer learning exchange, which aims to disseminate key insights on INHERIT's solutions. It also ensured the pairing of Learning Partners and pilots based on thematic synergy, fostering a targeted learning experience, most with their case studies, and further, to match these preferences.

The culmination of the learning scheme included the Pilots, including representatives at the local and regional levels, to assimilate and reflect upon the insights obtained in the study visits by implementing project activities in their respective pilots.

3.3.2 Selection of Learning Partners

Among the applications received, six organisations were selected as Learning Partners for the INHERIT bilateral peer-learning scheme (Refer Figure 6). These projects demonstrated a remarkable commitment to preserving cultural heritage while embracing the NEB principles of sustainability, inclusivity, and aesthetics, integrating technological innovation and community engagement. It was also imperative that the project sites of the selected partners matched the profile of the historic buildings and/or sites of the INHERIT pilots, while also demonstrating experience in the application of one or more services as proposed in INHERIT. Their work not only showcases innovative approaches to preserving heritage but also exemplifies how historic buildings can serve as beacons of sustainable development, aligned with the goals of the European Green Deal and NEB initiatives. The expertise of the partners across the following criteria played a key role in their selection:

- **Adaptive reuse and refurbishment** of historic buildings.
- Enhancing **energy efficiency** and the use of monitoring tools in preservation.
- Employing advanced technologies like **H-BIM, digital twins, and AR/VR** for monitoring and managing cultural heritage sites.
- Engaging **stakeholders and communities** in sustainable transformation and the circular economy in cultural heritage projects.

Since the process of selecting and inducting the Learning Partners spanned over twelve months, and given certain situations, INHERIT pilots CARTIF and BOUYGUES generously supported the peer learning scheme by introducing Learning Partners that best suited their requirements and resource availability.

Figure 6: Location of the INHERIT Learning Partners: 1. Zero Waste House, Žalec, Slovenia; 2. University of Patras: HeritACT, Patras, Greece; 3. The Cyprus Institute: Paphos Gate, Nicosia, Cyprus; 4:Institut Iskriva: Old Ironworks Project, Ravne na Koroškem, Slovenia; 5: University of Bologna: Baraccano Historical Complex, Bologna, Italy; 6: Arte Charpentier: ULTEAM (Cisco Headquarters), Paris, France

The following section provides an overview of the Learning Partners and their proposed case study for the peer learning scheme.

3.3.2.1 Learning Partner 1: Zero Waste Žalec: Zero Waste House, Žalec, Slovenia

The Zero Waste House is an NEB Award winner. The project includes a journal of renovation with all the interventions detailed and presented in a guidebook form aimed primarily at investors (with no background in architecture or construction). Another aspect, which, due to the lack of time and available technical personnel, never materialised, was the creation of a material passport. This project offers an opportunity to create a material passport retrospectively, based on the photos taken and knowledge gained during the renovation. The process can be applied to other similar buildings to determine whether a building is worth renovating or, in alternative scenarios, to help estimate the amount of reusable material available within the existing building stock in the event of selective demolition. The case study is intended to act as a foundation upon which various uses of ICTs can be identified. The idea is to derive simplified versions of professional ICTs that may help citizens and beginner investors with limited architectural knowledge in estimating the value of building materials embedded in the existing building stock and recognising the potential interventions for renovation. The case study does not intend to build a working software tool, as this is beyond the scope of current capabilities; however, we aim to identify important parameters that should be acknowledged when designing such a tool.

3.3.2.2 Learning Partner 2: HeritACT project, Eleusis, Greece; led by University of Patras

Project HeritACT's holistic methodology of cultural practices aligns with the key challenges of INHERIT: "Sustainability, inclusiveness, and stakeholder engagement" and "Smartification and data exchange", encompassing the NEB initiative. Eleusis, a HeritACT pilot, is one of the five most important sacred cities of antiquity. Eleusis was transformed from the 19th century onwards into the productive engine of Greece and one of its largest industrial centres. Peer-learning participants will have the opportunity to visit the Green Tensegrity Installations in the neighbourhoods of Eleusis. This system is characterised by two levels of innovation: a) an Innovative construction system (tensegrity). This system will enable the on-site rapid assembly of structures from detachable, prefabricated, and pre-assembled modules. b) Water Management System. In the green wall system that is being developed, atmospheric humidity will be collected using bio-receptive membranes. This solution establishes a framework for the co-production of highly innovative public space installations, including self-sustaining green walls and public-space shading systems. Also, participants will be introduced to a small-scale innovative pavilion structure that will be placed in a public space in one of the neighbourhoods and will function as a local landmark structure that advertises and attracts urban activities (music performances, art and crafts exhibits, lectures, urban games, and various workshops). Lastly, there will be physical and virtual exhibitions of the participating communities at one site, where the visitors will be able to experience both the physical exhibition and, with the use of the appropriate devices, the artefacts that are virtually placed in the Eleourgio.

3.3.2.3 Learning Partner 3: The Cyprus Institute: Paphos Gate, Nicosia, Cyprus

Paphos Gate presents a rich historical palimpsest of Nicosia's architectural fabric, featuring examples from nearly all periods of the city's history. Respecting this unique character, a walk through the archaeological site was created through an innovative, interdisciplinary process of inclusive co-design. This process engaged experts from the fields of architecture, urban planning, history, and archaeology, as well as the competent officials of the relevant bodies (Nicosia Municipality and Department of Antiquities) and citizens of Nicosia. They were invited to offer their ideas and opinions on the management plan of the site by co-designing a walking platform in a virtual environment. Through this awarded innovative method, participants had the opportunity to virtually visit different historical periods of the Paphos Gate, as if they had a time machine that allowed them to explore this important area of Nicosia and its transformation in time.

3.3.2.4 Learning Partner 4: Institut Iskriva: Old Ironworks Project, Ravne na Korškem, Slovenia

The Old Ironworks project in Ravne na Koroškem, Slovenia, aims to revitalise the historic ironworks site, known as Stara Železarna. This initiative aligns with the goals of social, economic, and environmental sustainability, as well as the NEB principles of beauty, sustainability, and inclusivity. The project involves renovating the Old Ironworks buildings, preserving their historical integrity while modernising them for contemporary use. These buildings will serve as multifunctional spaces for cultural activities, educational programmes, and community events, fostering social innovation

and local regeneration. More than 40 stakeholders, including residents, businesses, and the steel factory SIJ, are actively involved, ensuring broad community engagement. Emphasising sustainable practices, the project uses innovative solutions to enhance the site's environmental quality and provide communal spaces for residents and visitors. An example of this is the use of excess heat from SIJ's steel production to heat the site, demonstrating a commitment to circularity and responsible steel production. The project also incorporates recycled steel and traditional materials, emphasising durability and sustainability. Art also plays a significant role, with installations like Forma Viva – permanent outdoor steel sculptures that utilise steel to create a unique artistic environment reflecting the site's industrial heritage. Specialised tourism products, such as educational camps and creative events, leverage the region's rich industrial heritage. These attract visitors, educate them about the site's historical and cultural significance, and boost the local economy through sustainable tourism. These interventions collectively contribute to preserving cultural heritage, fostering community engagement, and promoting sustainable development, making the Old Ironworks project a model for similar initiatives.

3.3.2.5 Learning Partner 5: University of Bologna: Baraccano Historical Complex, Bologna, Italy

The Baraccano complex, situated in the Santo Stefano district of Bologna, is a historically significant area that features religious and civic buildings, including the Sanctuary of Santa Maria del Baraccano and the former Conservatorio delle Putte. Originating in the 15th century, the complex was created to support and educate disadvantaged young women. Architecturally, it features notable elements, such as the “Voltone del Baraccano” (1497), and is part of Bologna’s UNESCO-listed portico system. In recent years, the Baraccano has been transformed into a vibrant community space, now home to the “Casa delle Associazioni”, which hosts a diverse range of cultural, social, and educational activities. This transformation demonstrates how historic structures can be reactivated to serve modern community needs while preserving their heritage value. Equally important is the regeneration of the surrounding neighbourhood. Considered a marginal area of Bologna, largely abandoned just a decade ago, the district is now undergoing a process of urban renewal. Public and private efforts have improved infrastructure, public spaces, and social cohesion, turning it into a more inclusive and dynamic part of the city. This dual significance (heritage conservation, according to the Carta del Rischio, and urban revitalisation) makes the Baraccano complex a key case study for INHERIT, as this project promotes innovative, sustainable, and inclusive approaches to rehabilitating historic buildings.

3.3.2.6 Learning Partner 6: Arte Charpentier: ULTEAM (Cisco Headquarters), Paris, France

ULTEAM is a project to refurbish an office complex comprising a Haussmann-style building and a building dating from the 1950s. Just a stone's throw from the Champs-Élysées, the Hôtel Particulier, dating back to 1820, with its main courtyard, mouldings, high ceilings, and paintings, forms the heart of the project, which brings together history and contemporary architecture. In 1870, Haussmann-style annexes were added, followed by a third concrete extension in 1950, with non-aligned floor levels, and a fourth extension in 1963. This Cisco project involves the refurbishment of a former townhouse into an office building, located in the prestigious 8th arrondissement of Paris.

3.3.3 Evaluation of Proposed Case Studies and Matchmaking with Pilots

Refer to Annex B: Matchmaking Process for all Learning Partners and Pilots

The process began by collecting and reviewing the services available at the Learning Partners’ sites to understand what was offered. Then, matchmaking was done based on thematic alignment, so applicants were linked with pilots most relevant to their focus. The preferences of applicants for specific pilots were also taken into consideration. Each application was then checked for its relevance to the pilot services, with applicants’ services compared to the INHERIT services to be tested. Finally, the process ended with the final matchmaking to create well-aligned and effective partnerships. The following sections provide an overview of the services offered by the Learning Partners, their relevance to the themes of the learning scheme, and the results of the matchmaking process, where each INHERIT pilot was matched with at least one learning partner. The final decision of the peer learning visit was made democratically by the pilots based on their assessment of the exercise. Each pilot was then matched with a learning partner, and consultations for the visit followed.

3.3.3.1 Theme Distribution for the Proposed Case Studies from the Learning Partners

Based on the relevance of the themes to the proposed case study, each applicant was required to rate its relevance rating (1- Low, 2- Medium, 3- High). Figure 7 shows the overall distribution of themes across the proposed case studies. This approach also ensured a balanced diversity within the learning scheme.

Figure 7: Themes represented in each of the proposed case studies by Learning Partners

3.3.3.2 Matrix of Services Adopted at Proposed Case Studies by Learning Partners

A matrix was prepared regarding the INHERIT services and the applications received by the Learning Partners (Refer Table 4). This formed the basis of the evaluation and matchmaking exercise carried out further.

Table 4: Services relevant to the INHERIT project as per the proposed case studies of the Learning Partners

INHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	Learning Partners						
			Partner 1: Zero Waste House - Žalec, Slovenia	Partner 2: Green Tensegrity Installations - HeritACT/ University of Patras - Greece	Partner 3: Paphos Gate - The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus	Partner 4: Old IronWorks - Institut Iskriva, Slovenia	Partner 5: Baraccano Historical Complex - University of Bologna, Italy	Partner 6: Cisco Headquarters - ULTEAM, Arte Charpentier, France	
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0	-	-	✓	✓	✓	-	
	Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1	-	✓	✓	✓	-	-
		Modelling & simulation environment	S.2	-	-	-	-	-	✓
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	✓	-	✓	-	✓	
Monitoring, management, operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	S.4	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5	-	✓	-	-	-	-	
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7	-	-	-	✓	-	-	
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8	✓	-	✓	-	✓	-	
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9	-	-	-	-	✓	-	
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10	✓	-	-	-	-	-	

3.3.3.3 Relevance of the Case Studies to the Services of Each Pilot

Based on the matchmaking of services, each learning partner was assigned to the most relevant INHERIT pilot with one or more services that matched. The options of potential peer visits were then shared with each of the match pilots, with the selection being a democratic process. Figure 8 shows how each learning partner and case study matched with more than one INHERIT pilot, and the final selection and decision of peer learning visits done by the pilots.

Figure 8: An overall analysis of the relevance of proposed case studies to each pilot, based on the matchmaking of services.

3.3.4 Design of Documentation Forms for the Peer Learning Study Visits

Refer to Annex C: Format of Documentation form

The documentation form was designed to capture the experience of the pilots visiting the case study. It served a dual purpose: to record the interventions observed at the site visited and to document reflections on learning and their potential application to the INHERIT pilot sites. In this manner, through visits and consultations with the Learning Partners, the documentation form ensured that peer learning and exchange were fruitful and captured the learnings and exchanges in a uniform format. Since INHERIT focuses on methods and technology, as well as NEB principles, these sections were created similarly for the pilots to populate information. To ensure a fair and transparent process, the documentation form was vetted and agreed upon by the Learning Partners. The documentation forms used textual descriptions, ratings of themes and NEB pillars, as well as ratings of the services demonstrated and their application to the pilot site. Photographic documentation was also expected during the visit.

Ranking of themes and NEB pillars is ranked from high (5) to low (1) relevance:

- Relevance of the themes demonstrated in the case to the pilot

- Which NEB Pillars are addressed by this case study?

3.4 Phase 4: Implementation of Peer Learning Study Visits and Synthesis of Documentation Forms

The INHERIT pilots were hosted by the Learning Partners and visited the study site together with the team members. The documentation form was completed by the pilots during and after the visit, based on the discussions and observations made during the visit. The sections below give a synthesis of the survey documentation provided by the pilots following the visit. These descriptions highlight the unique focus of each site, including innovative technology and conservation practices, community-based initiatives, innovative models of service delivery, and collaborative approaches

that combine social, environmental, and health-related goals. Together, the study visits provided pilots with practical opportunities to observe, reflect on, and adapt relevant strategies to their own contexts and projects. Given the matchmaking and preference of the Pilots, two Learning Partners were visited by two INHERIT Pilots each, namely: HeritACT’s pilot Eleusis was visited by UU and IBB and Old Ironworks Project at Ravne na Koroškem was visited by ELLET and RPR; while REGEA visited Zero Waste House in Žalec, BOUYGUES visited the Cisco Headquarters, FASADA visited Paphos Gate and CARTIF visited the Baraccano historical complex.

3.4.1 Pilot 1: City Administration Headquarters – Jastrebarsko, Croatia; Coordinator: REGEA

Site Visited:	Zero Waste House in Žalec
Learning Partner:	Zero Waste Žalec
More information:	http://www.zerowastezalec.com/
Location:	Žalec, Slovenia Velenjska cesta 6, Žalec, Slovenia
Site Features:	Building Type: Residence (Currently a practical demonstration site) Building Age: 170 years old

3.4.1.1 General Overview

Site Description

Includes details across building type, purpose, age, materials used, any unique features, challenges faced, and the owner’s needs

The Zero Waste House in Žalec, Slovenia, is a 170-year-old building that has been transformed into a practical demonstration site, promoting sustainable living and circular economy principles. Designed and managed by local environmental advocates, the initiative showcases a variety of zero-waste practices, including composting, material reuse, water conservation, and energy efficiency. Built mostly from natural materials such as wood, clay, and hemp, the renovation emphasised minimal intervention, generating as little waste as possible and reusing leftover materials directly on-site. Beyond its physical transformation, the house serves as an educational hub, offering workshops and community events to raise awareness and encourage behavioural change. It reflects a holistic approach to sustainable living, combining low-impact architecture with everyday habits that reduce waste.

The project also faced challenges, including the difficulty of finding contractors, the high costs of materials, and the lack of suitable technologies, which, for example, necessitated visual inspection to estimate the state of the wood. Despite these hurdles, the Zero Waste House gained recognition at the European level, winning the NEB Rising Stars prize in 2021. Today, it stands as a strong local model for how communities can transition toward more sustainable and responsible lifestyles.

Themes Addressed

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective themes, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness

5 - Most Relevant ; 1 - Least Relevant

THEME 1: Human-centred and life-centred approaches to Cultural Heritage

The emphasis on community involvement and the human dimension of sustainability strongly resonates with REGEA’s work in Jastrebarsko. Although the pilot building is public, not residential, the idea of integrating shared outdoor spaces (like a community garden) and engaging older residents or vulnerable groups is highly transferable.

THEME 2: Resource efficiency and circularity

This theme is highly relevant, given the REGEA’s aim to improve energy efficiency and reduce material waste during renovation. Practices like on-site reuse of materials, natural insulation, and designing for material circularity could be adapted in Jastrebarsko with appropriate planning and stakeholder support.

THEME 3: Capacity for innovative, transdisciplinary, and contemporary approaches

While some innovations, such as PV systems and heat pumps, can be technically applied, the pilot requires a more institutional and conservative approach due to its public function and heritage value. Still, the glamping dome as a creative tourism function sparked ideas for temporary structures/events at the site.

Which NEB Pillars are addressed by this case study?

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective NEB pillars, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness

5 - Most Relevant ; 1 - Least Relevant

Pillar 1: Sustainability

Solutions such as insulation, heat pumps, and natural water filtration demonstrate low-impact, sustainable approaches relevant to heritage renovation in Jastrebarsko.

Pillar 2: Inclusion

Community engagement, especially through the community garden and workshops (e.g. an elderly neighbour (Famika) who works in the community garden in the yard), shows how inclusiveness can be fostered in both public and private heritage spaces and designing for material circularity could be adapted in Jastrebarsko with appropriate planning and stakeholder support.

Pillar 3: Aesthetic/ Beauty

The use of permaculture and natural aesthetics contributes to a pleasant and context-sensitive appearance that aligns well with the heritage setting.

Steps of the case’s execution that were most inspiring and relevant to the pilot

Further includes the level of difficulty with regard to its applicability to the pilot

Circular and Community-centred Focus: Several steps were particularly inspiring throughout the execution of the case, including the minimalist intervention philosophy, reusing old or leftover materials, and repurposing building components rather than replacing them. These strategies are cost-effective and environmentally sound. While full replication is limited due to public regulations and procurement rules, the mindset of circularity and phased improvements could be integrated into the Croatian pilot.

The strong connection with the local community and low-tech, yet impactful, solutions were especially relevant and potentially applicable.

3.4.1.2 Applicability of Methods, Tools and Services to INHERIT Pilots

Pilot-wise Technology Learning and Applicability

Overview and Applicability of Technologies to the INHERIT Pilots

Service Type: Preservation & maintenance services	
Service No.: S8 - Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	
Service Observed:	BIM was applied in the adjacent heritage building to visualise structural needs and plan preservation works, particularly to address age-related degradation. This was demonstrated through a conversation with involved architects.
Applicability to the pilot:	This technology could support REGEA’s work in Jastrebarsko, particularly in visualizing renovation phases and facilitating preventive maintenance in a public heritage building. However, the use of H-BIM would be considered moderately difficult in the pilot due to the need for technical expertise and initial software/hardware investment. The application of BIM (H-BIM) would require adjustments to meet the scale and institutional requirements of a public building. The model could include layered historical data, material wear tracking, and space management for multifunctional civic use. Integration with existing municipal systems and staff training would be necessary; however, it could greatly enhance planning accuracy and long-term maintenance strategies.

What are the Resources Required for the Successful Implementation of Services?

Needs of the pilot partners to apply the relevant service types to their respective pilots, which includes challenges, modifications required, or areas where the technology could enhance the overall process

Service Type: Preservation & maintenance services

Service No.: S8 - Preventive maintenance with H-BIM

Economic Resources: Required for software licensing and possible outsourcing of modelling.

Technical Resources: Skilled professionals needed to operate H-BIM platforms.

Human Resources: Trained personnel to maintain and update H-BIM data.

Governmental Support: Crucial for integrating H-BIM into procurement and planning processes.

Other: Institutional readiness and awareness-raising about digital conservation benefits.

3.4.1.3 Assessment of Services' Outcomes and Further Applications

Includes assessment of the efficiency, expected outcomes and measurements to prove the KPIs of the tools/technology used in the case study, and additional applications of the technology that deliver comparable outcomes and efficiency

Service Type: Preservation & maintenance services

Service No.: S8 - Preventive maintenance with H-BIM

Focus on Low-tech Renovation Techniques: As explained by the Learning Partners, no advanced IT tools or digital technologies were used in the renovation of the Zero Waste House. The methodology focused on manual craftsmanship, reuse of available materials, and traditional construction techniques. Despite the lack of quantifiable KPIs or digital monitoring, the project achieved a high level of material circularity, reduced waste output, and strong community participation. In the nearby protected house where BIM was used, the primary benefit was seen in visualising the structure and damage, which supported better planning decisions. The outcomes were primarily qualitative, yet they demonstrated sustainable and locally driven success in renovation.

3.4.1.4 Stakeholder Participation and Engagement

Overview of Stakeholder Roles in the Project Case Study

Gives an overview of the stakeholders involved in the case study project

The project brought together the owner who initiated the Zero Waste House concept, architects working on the renovation of a neighbouring heritage property, and a craftsman responsible for carrying out construction work on the adjacent building. A local resident also took part, contributing to the community garden and social activities on site.

Challenges Encountered across Stakeholder Consultation, Planning, and Execution of the Project

Includes issues related to communication, collaboration, decision-making, or other factors that affected the project's progress

Planning Phase: The project's informal and bottom-up nature made it flexible, but it lacked formal frameworks. This could pose coordination difficulties if scaled or institutionalised.

Execution Phase: Limited technical resources and reliance on personal networks can hinder scalability. In addition, balancing expert input (e.g., architects) with available budget and manual labour was an ongoing challenge.

Mechanisms Undertaken to Ensure Effective Stakeholder Participation during the above Phases

Includes strategies or approaches used to engage stakeholders and ensure their input was considered throughout the project

Strong Community Engagement: The Zero Waste House has community engagement at the heart of its model. Andrej, the owner, has organised various workshops and educational events in the yard to involve local people and share knowledge. The community garden serves not only as a sustainability practice but also as a social space, particularly appreciated by elderly residents like Fanika. The inclusion of family members and local architects in the adjacent house project reflects grassroots, participatory approach that combines traditional knowledge with modern conservation tools.

Stakeholder Engagement Issues and Relevant Case Study Learnings and Key Takeaways

Gives a documentation of the challenges faced by the learning partner

Case Study Learnings: During the study visit, it was noted that no digital or IT technologies were used during the renovation of the Zero Waste House itself. The approach was intentionally low-tech, focusing on natural materials and manual craftsmanship. However, the hosts recently started renovating an adjacent protected heritage house (built in the late 1800s), where Building Information Modelling (BIM) has been introduced to support design and planning.

Lessons Learned and Looking Beyond

Includes overall learnings from the study visits as it relates to the pilots, and additional resources from the pilots as it relates to the case study across methodology, technology, context, and outcomes

Relevant Learnings and Key Takeaways: The Zero Waste House demonstrates how informal, community-led initiatives can contribute to cultural heritage and sustainability. In Jastrebarsko, more structured forms of engagement are required, but inspiration can be drawn from the openness, educational initiatives, and integration of everyday users. REGEA will consider including public gardening elements, informal meetups, or citizen-led workshops in future phases to foster community ownership.

Additional Applications with comparable outcomes or efficiency: There are several examples of similar uses of BIM in heritage contexts, such as the "[INCEPTION](#)" project, which demonstrates 3D capturing and semantic enrichment for cultural heritage. These resources may provide a reference for adapting similar practices to the pilot in Jastrebarsko.

Additional Resources: A comparable initiative is the "Hiša Zelenih Rešitev" (House of Green Solutions) in Slovenia, which promotes sustainable renovation through community-driven models in a similar manner. Also, the INCEPTION project showcases heritage building documentation and digital enrichment via 3D and BIM.

3.4.1.5 Photographs from the study visit

Figure 9: L- View of the Zalej House; R- Installations for Energy Efficiency at the site, Photovoltaics, and Glamping dome

Figure 10: L-Community garden; C- Energy saver installations; R- Reused roofing materials for circularity

3.4.2 Pilot 2: Cité du Goût - Noisiel, France; Coordinator: BOUYGUES

Site Visited:	Cisco Headquarters - Rue Washington- Paris - France
Learning Partner:	ULTEAM, Arte-Charpentier
More information:	https://www.arte-charpentier.com/en/
Location:	8th Arrondissement, Paris
Site Features:	Building Area: 6,000 m ² (after refurbishment)

3.4.2.1 General Overview

Site Description

Includes details across building type, purpose, age, materials used, any unique features, challenges faced, and the owner's needs.

ULTEAM is a project to refurbish an office complex comprising a Haussmann-style building and a building dating from the 1950s. Just a stone's throw from the Champs-Élysées, the Hôtel Particulier, dating back to 1820, with its main courtyard, mouldings, high ceilings, and paintings, forms the heart of the project, which brings together history and contemporary architecture. In 1870, Haussmann-style annexes were added, followed by a third concrete extension in 1950, with non-aligned floor levels, and a fourth extension in 1963. This Cisco project involves the refurbishment of this former townhouse into an office building, located in the prestigious 8th arrondissement of Paris.

Figure 11: Chronological layers of the historic building

The players, objectives, and initial constraints were defined early in the process. The owner/investor, Groupama Immobilier, aimed to increase the property's economic value by renovating it to position it at the top end of the market, thereby enabling higher rental prices and reinforcing its prestige. Groupama Immobilier is recognised for its expertise in adding value to this type of asset and in finding suitable clients. Other objectives included densifying and increasing the usable floor area by 10%, from 5,500 m² to 6,000 m², improving profitability, and creating an additional floor. A constraint was the presence of the former occupier, the Chinese Consulate: as the building was considered foreign territory, diagnostic visits, carried out one to two years before the consulate left, were very complex and required authorisations months in advance.

Although the building itself was unlisted, its garden was listed as a protected green space. Moreover, a historical and documentary study by GRAHAL highlighted elements deemed “remarkable.” This study was strongly insisted upon by the Commission du Vieux Paris, the City of Paris, and the Architectes des Bâtiments de France (ABF). While not strictly compulsory, the process was considered politically mandatory and provided inspiration and material for the architect in charge of the renovation. Another challenge was the discovery of an unauthorised glass roof, added by the Chinese Consulate without authorisation, which covered the courtyard of honour. This had to be removed as it contravened the Local Urban Plan, and the courtyard was vacated.

Measures undertaken towards the refurbishment of the site:

- A partial conversion of the underground car park into an auditorium was carried out, with the condition that the excavation depth be limited to avoid incurring an archaeological tax.
- The project also enabled the building to be raised to a total of five stores above ground level. To remain tax-exempt, no more than 50% of the existing floors could be destroyed. The load-bearing capacity for the elevation was a major consideration, necessitating a sounding campaign to assess the support. A lightweight metal framework was chosen, allowing for large spans with fewer columns and eliminating the need for additional concrete.
- Other measures included the removal of rendering to reveal the stone walls, the opening up of the interior courtyard with a transparent reception hall (after removal of the veranda in line with the Local Urban Plan), and the renovation of the paintwork, which Groupama decided to undertake to maintain the building’s upmarket positioning despite the cost.
- A new façade was created for the additional floors of the 1820 townhouse, incorporating metallic mesh and full-height glazing. Originally envisaged in bronze, the mesh was ultimately built in powder-coated aluminum for cost reasons, with a colour described as “golden death,” chosen for its ability to blend harmoniously with Parisian stone buildings. The decision was finalised after rendering tests. Beyond aesthetics, the mesh also played an energy role, acting as a sunshade to limit solar gain and improve summer comfort.

Themes Addressed

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective themes, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness
5 - Most Relevant 1 - Least Relevant

THEME 1: Human-centred and life-centred approaches to Cultural Heritage

The ULTEAM project focuses on preserving the historic value of the building by retaining all the remarkable elements of the old heritage and removing the later additions to the 1st building that have deteriorated its value. For this reason, part of the renovation involved removing the damage caused by the original mansion (1820) to restore the original spirit. This included making the interior courtyard visible from the road, enhancing the rear garden (jardin à la française), and renovating the interior paintings and frescoes. The historic district of Paris, located near the Arc de Triomphe and the Champs-Élysées, is an area with numerous listed monuments and is highly attractive to the business community. Enhancing the value of this historic heritage is therefore an economically profitable operation, making it easy to find tenants at a good price.

THEME 2: Resource efficiency and circularity

This criterion was not a priority for this operation, given the heterogeneity of materials and architectural style. It is authorised and was decided to restore the coherence of the 1st building and the large-scale destruction of the buildings added later. However, despite the possibility of destroying 50% of the existing floors, the walls of heritage value have been preserved. The integration of renewable energies was not a priority, despite being studied, due to its unprofitable cost. Sustainable materials such as aluminium were introduced for the joinery, although the carbon footprint was unfavourable.

THEME 3: Capacity for innovative, transdisciplinary, and contemporary approaches

The transdisciplinary approach focused on the mandatory dialogue with the various stakeholders, including the building owner, whose primary objective was the economic profitability of the operation, and the administrative and cultural bodies, given the building's location within a classified site and the presence of a protected green space. However, the process of execution followed a "classic" approach: dialogue and exchange, consultation meetings between professional actors, and representatives of administrative or cultural institutions. As the building was private, the public or the neighbourhood was not invited to these discussions. No digital tools were used to facilitate the dialogue. The architectural firm confirmed that a classic tangible 3D model remains the best tool for exchanging and explaining the designer's intentions. Generative AI did not exist at the time of the work in 2020. However, in the future, AI could be used to generate images.

Which NEB Pillars are Addressed by this Case Study?

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective NEB pillars, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness
5 - Most Relevant 1 - Least Relevant

Pillar 1: Sustainability

Sustainability has been taken into account by using materials with a very long lifespan (aluminium and glass), although the carbon footprint is not favourable.

Pillar 2: Inclusion

Accessibility was clearly addressed from a regulatory perspective, as the project involved transforming a private mansion into an office building for lease to companies. Therefore, it was necessary to comply with the Labour Code and to incorporate ramps or elevators. This was successfully implemented, as it involved an asset transformation that required the demolition of floor slabs or parts of the building without heritage value. Thus, it was entirely feasible to comply with accessibility regulations.

While the case is interesting, BOUYGUES' pilot will not have quite the same context, due to the conversion of offices into housing. In this scenario, there is a need to negotiate exemptions from the regulations, as not all housing units can be made accessible due to the disproportionate additional cost this would entail, given that economic viability is a prohibitive constraint.

Pillar 3: Aesthetic/ Beauty

The main issue was to preserve the building's aesthetic and historical heritage and create a high-end, high-rent building in a world-renowned historic district.

In the case of the Noisiel pilot, this will be less the case, given its location outside Paris. Finding investors could be challenging, as homes would have to be resold to private individuals.

Steps of the Case’s Execution that were Most Inspiring and Relevant to the Pilot

Further includes the level of difficulty with regard to its applicability to the pilot

Reconciling Differing Stakeholder Priorities: It was important to balance the economic profitability of the transformation, as requested by the building owner-investor (Groupama), and the demands of both the ABF (Architectes des Bâtiments de France) and the Commission du Vieux Paris. These latter bodies prioritized adherence to architectural and preservation constraints, as well as compliance with administrative rules (Local Urban Plan). Therefore, it was necessary to find clever solutions for low-cost valorisation. For BOUYGUES, achieving an economic balance is more challenging because housing units are being created, and future private owners will not be able to bear the additional renovation costs associated with historical heritage. Finding a compromise on what to preserve, what to demolish, and what to transform, as well as determining the best uses (housing, offices, retail, etc.), was key.

Mechanisms undertaken to enable integration of varying stakeholder priorities included a consultation meeting organized with representatives from the Ministry of Culture (DRAC), the ABF, the City of Paris, Arte Charpentier, and the Commission du Vieux Paris. A 3D physical model created by Arte Charpentier helped convey the project's objective, which led to approval for the project's sketch. Arte Charpentier also presented hand-drawn sketches to illustrate the integration of new interfaces (e.g., how windows would be placed on stone cornices). Thus, the non-use of digital tools (a classic 3D physical model) worked well with the stakeholders.

3.4.2.2 Applicability of Methods, Tools and Services to INHERIT Pilots

Pilot-wise Technology Learning and Applicability

Overview and Applicability of Technologies to the INHERIT Pilots

Service Type: Design & renovation services	
Service No.: S2 - Modelling and simulation environment	
Service Observed:	Energy simulations have been carried out to comply with Thermal Regulation RT2012, but this remains a classic process.
Applicability to the pilot:	Relevant, however, is that the pilot already typically uses tools to carry out energy simulations. The application is easy, unless it has to be applied to a very large surface area (all the surfaces of a building)

Service Type: Design & renovation services	
Service No.: S2 - Modelling and simulation environment	
Service Observed:	Energy simulations have been carried out to comply with Thermal Regulation RT2012, but this remains a classic process.
Applicability to the pilot:	Same as above

Service Type: Design & renovation services	
Service No.: S3 - Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	
Service Observed:	By iteration, the energy study office was able to select the best solutions, but it was fairly easy to comply with RT2012. There were also some remarkable features that were non-negotiable in terms of preservation. The subsequent demolition of low-value building extensions also made it possible to free oneself from certain constraints and to build new with the advantages of new (energy efficiency, comfort for occupants, compliance with accessibility standards).
Applicability to the pilot:	Very relevant for making better and faster decisions on the major options to be retained. However, the economic criterion is paramount and therefore requires a good estimate of the cost of each measure.

Service Type: Monitoring, operation & management services	
Service No.: S4 - IEQ and thermal comfort optimization	
Service Observed:	For a well-located office building in Paris, rents are high, which means that a lot can be invested in renovation and usage of top-of-the-range quality materials and equipment. This allows future employees to benefit from quality and comfort (large bay windows, brightness, air conditioning, large spaces, natural ventilation, transparency, quality interior materials).
Applicability to the pilot:	The applicability of this is easy with the right sensors, however to obtain certifications like BREEAM, there are already a large number of comfort criteria to be met - which is dependent on the amount of financial resources that can be allocated to it.

Overall, no specific digital solution was used for ULTEAM and it's similar for Noisiel. The 2 projects are very similar in the context, the goals and the constraints (private client is looking for rentability first). The Learning Partner (Arte Charpentier) doesn't seem to believe that digital tools would make it easier to work with stakeholders at the design stage. Being able to walk around a real model, touching it and physically standing around it together is still a simple and effective consultation technique.

What are the Resources Required for the Successful Implementation of Services?

Needs of the pilot partners to apply the relevant service types to their respective pilots, which includes challenges, modifications required, or areas where the technology could enhance the overall process

Service Type: Design and Renovation Services

Service No.: S2 - Modelling and simulation environment

- **Economic Resources:** Have a fast modelling and data capture technique (for large buildings) to ensure cost-effectiveness

- **Technical Resources:** Pre-established simulation scenarios (e.g. different techniques for reducing energy consumption, different energy price scenarios)

Service Type: Design and Renovation Services

Service No.: S3 - Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning

- **Economic Resources:** Saves time if the tool can calculate the results of applying the various measures (effect on economic profitability + carbon value + comfort, etc.).
- **Technical Resources:** Have multi-criteria results to compare different packages of measures that would be applied (e.g. if measure 4+6+8 is applied, being able to compare that with 8+9+12)

3.4.2.3 Assessment of Services' Outcomes and Further Applications

Includes assessment of the efficiency, expected outcomes and measurements to prove the KPIs of the tools/technology used in the case study, and additional applications of the technology that deliver comparable outcomes and efficiency

No figures have been given on the results of the operation, as it has been "sold" to the investor Groupama Immobilier, which rents the building to a tenant. However, the fact that several labels and certifications have been obtained proves that the tests (such as comfort and energy efficiency) have been met.

3.4.2.4 Stakeholder Participation and Engagement

Overview of Stakeholder Roles in the Project Case Study

Gives an overview of the stakeholders involved in the case study project

The project involved several key actors with distinct roles. Municipal authorities oversaw compliance with the local urban plan and broader administrative requirements. The client brought expertise in research and simulation modelling, aiming to increase the project's financial and heritage value. Official heritage architects focused on ensuring visual coherence between historic and new elements, while a heritage commission offered politically influential opinions on interventions affecting the city's built fabric. The architectural firm contributed its design, landscape, and interior architecture skills, preparing the project's physical model and visual materials.

Challenges Encountered across Stakeholder Consultation, Planning and Execution of the Project

Includes issues related to communication, collaboration, decision-making, or other factors that affected the project's progress

Planning Phase: The learning partner encountered issues with mismatched priorities, necessitating compromises. The project also had to factor in additional costs that may be added.

Execution Phase: There was no appeal against planning permission.

Mechanisms Undertaken to Ensure Effective Stakeholder Participation during the above Phases

Includes strategies or approaches used to engage stakeholders and ensure their input was considered throughout the project

- **Stakeholder Participation:** While there was no need to mobilise the stakeholders, their participation was mandatory as they represented essential checkpoints in the process. Exchanges took place via meetings, video calls, and email for document submissions. There was no dialogue with the neighbourhood, as it was a private operation.
- **Heavy Rehabilitation - Balancing History and Future:** The aspect of heavy rehabilitation, involving demolitions and restructurings of certain parts of the building, was extensively discussed and worked on with all project stakeholders (Client, City, ABF). This was done to find the best compromise between respecting the building's history and ensuring its continuity for years to come.
- **Architectural Proposals and Negotiations:** As part of stakeholder discussions, Arte Charpentier presented a proposal with the aim of lighting the building and making it more transparent and opening up the interior courtyard. The proposal also included many windows and glazing to increase light and create additional floors.
- **Project Consultation and Validation:** A consultation meeting was organised with representatives from the Ministry of Culture (DRAC), the ABF, the City of Paris, Arte Charpentier, and the Commission du Vieux Paris. A 3D physical model, created by Arte Charpentier, was presented and greatly helped in conveying the project's objective. This consultation led to a green light for the project's sketch. Arte Charpentier also presented hand-drawn sketches to illustrate the integration of new interfaces (e.g., how windows would be placed on stone cornices). Initially, the ABF favoured "solid" elements (walls with few windows) to preserve the original walls and maintain the consistency between the existing and new parts of the building. For the creation of new floors, a **ground floor plus five stories (R+5)** were planned. This required negotiation. Arte Charpentier's clever solution was to present the 5th and final floor as an atypical, entirely glass-enclosed space called the **"Nuage" (Cloud)**. Initially rejected, this addition was eventually accepted by the ABF. The "Nuage" offers a 360° view of Paris, including the Eiffel Tower.

Stakeholder Engagement Issues and Relevant Case Study Learnings and Key Takeaways

Gives a documentation of the challenges faced by the learning partner

Relevant Learnings and Key Takeaways: A key learning was that the dialogue between stakeholders will depend on the economic context, the degree of urgency of the project, the stakeholders involved, and the degree of compromise they are willing to accept.

In the case of the pilot in Noisiel, the economic outcome is challenging, as there are no investors for the entire project (comprising 10 buildings in total), which complicates the situation further. To make it easier to find investors, the costs of conversion need to be limited, which means limiting the preservation of the heritage and limiting work on it since financial resources are very limited. A favourable economic situation gives more room for manoeuvre in preserving historic heritage.

Lessons Learned and Looking Beyond

Includes overall learnings from the study visits as it relates to the pilots, and additional resources from the pilots as it relates to the case study across methodology, technology, context, and outcomes

Further Insights Gained: The pilot identified the following key takeaways from the study visit, in relation to its thematic focus:

- **Heritage & Energy:** The main theme addressed was the preservation of the building's aesthetic and historical heritage, while energy efficiency and comfort were of secondary importance. Thermal regulations followed RT 2012 and specifically the RT for existing buildings, an approach involving component-by-component changes with lower requirements for overall energy efficiency and total building consumption. For example, summer comfort and carbon footprint were not included, unlike the current RE2020, making energy renovation simpler. Measures included no internal insulation on the townhouse (to preserve the frescoes and avoid losing rentable floor space), no external insulation, a change to double glazing, and reliance on natural ventilation, allowing users to open the windows. Despite this, air conditioning was installed for summer comfort, and the building achieved BREEAM Excellent certification.
- **Circularity & Accessibility:** Circular economy and resource conservation were not a priority; the aim was to retain at least 50% of the floor area in order to save tax on the project and to preserve outstanding features. Accessibility (PMR) was also not a major issue; however, since the building was not listed, it was possible to create lifts or ramps, and the building was made fully accessible after renovation.

3.4.2.5 Photographs from the study visit

Figure 12: L- First mansion 1820; R- During demolition

Figure 13: ULTEAM

Figure 14: L- Old, new and top floor; R- The court of honour

3.4.3 Pilot 3: ELLET building in Tripodon street - Athens, Greece; Coordinator: ELLET

Site Visited:	Old Ironworks Project, Ravne na Koroškem, Slovenia
Learning Partner:	Institut Iskriava
More information:	http://iskriava.net/
Location:	Ravne na Koroškem, Slovenia
Site Features:	Koroški pokrajinski muzej, Muzej Ravne na Koroškem

3.4.3.1 General Overview

Site Description

Includes details across building type, purpose, age, materials used, any unique features, challenges faced, and the owner's needs

The Old Ironworks Project site visited by the ELLET pilot was an industrial complex, constructed at the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th century. In 2002, the Ravne Steel Factory transferred the area to the Municipality of Ravne for preservation as a steelmaking museum. Made primarily of brick, stone, and iron, the building showcases unique features such as vaulted ceilings, traditional masonry, and preserved industrial elements. One of the rare authentic industrial complexes from this era in Slovenia and beyond, it is uniquely situated within a preserved historical and still-functioning area of the ironmaking and steel industry. The 5,000 m² site features the edging forge, a former factory workers' dormitory with a laundry room, a former chemical laboratory, and an old oil storage facility, now housing a traditional blacksmith workshop. The two-storey residential building, dating back to 1870-1875, retains its original appearance.

Themes Addressed

*Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective themes, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness
5 - Most Relevant ; 1 - Least Relevant*

THEME 1: Human-centred and life-centred approaches to Cultural Heritage

The participatory design process ensured that local voices shaped the renovation plans and fostered community engagement among 40+ stakeholders, including residents, businesses, and the steel factory. The success of the project revealed the importance of ensuring inclusivity and prioritising cultural preservation.

THEME 2: Resource efficiency and circularity

The reuse of the building's artefacts for the museum and the integration of excess heat from the steel factory nearby reflected the case's focus on circularity.

THEME 3: Capacity for innovative, transdisciplinary, and contemporary approaches

The museum's use of AR-VR to create an immersive experience of the iron and steel-making process demonstrated innovative capacities. Furthermore, the narrative of the history of the Old Ironworks - collaboratively designed by architects, engineers, and digital experts - made way for a holistic and effective approach to storytelling

Which NEB Pillars are addressed by this case study?

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective NEB pillars, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness

5 - Most Relevant ; 1 - Least Relevant

Pillar 1: Sustainability

The site demonstrates sustainability through economic self-sufficiency, which is relevant to ELLET, given its NGO operating model. While the pilot site and the case study are structurally and functionally different buildings, both face significant challenges in achieving high energy efficiency targets. The innovative usage of excess heat from SIJ's steel production to heat the site was a key takeaway, demonstrating a commitment to circularity and responsible steel production

Pillar 2: Inclusion

A commitment to inclusion was reflected in the project's involvement of local artisans and community members, showcasing a replicable engagement strategy. Additionally, the yard will be redesigned to ensure further accessibility.

Pillar 3: Aesthetic/ Beauty

The site's restoration work addressed architectural aesthetics and public perception, resulting in visual and functional harmony. The project also incorporated recycled steel and traditional materials, emphasising durability and sustainability. Art also plays a significant role, with possible installations such as Forma Viva, permanent outdoor steel sculptures that utilise steel to create a unique artistic environment reflecting the site's industrial heritage.

Steps of the Case's Execution that were Most Inspiring and Relevant to the Pilot

Further includes the level of difficulty with regard to its applicability to the pilot

- **Structured Approach to Renovation:** ELLET noted that this aspect particularly stood out, as the case initiated with analysis, followed by co-design, securing funding, and finally, full implementation.
- **Multistakeholder Involvement:** Successful engagement of 40+ stakeholders at local, regional, national, and international levels, leading to broad acceptance of the site's transformation - encouraged ELLET to engage a wider stakeholder network to raise interest for improving the building's energy efficiency, and encourage replication of efforts
- **Innovative Ideas for Energy Optimization:** While the case study's usage of excess heat from the nearby steel factory was not applicable to ELLET, it inspired exploration of alternative energy management strategies suited to the pilot's context.

3.4.3.2 Applicability of Methods, Tools, and Services to INHERIT Pilots

Pilot-wise Technology Learning and Applicability

Overview and Applicability of Technologies to the INHERIT Pilots

Service Type: Data Collection and Sharing	
Service No.: S1 - Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	
Service Observed:	NA

Applicability to the pilot:	Although not one of the pilot’s services, digital and visual technologies, such as AR overlays and interactive displays, could create an immersive experience at the ELLET building, highlighting its history and artefacts. This would require the installation of new infrastructure, the development of custom historical content, and integrating it with the building’s smart systems while preserving its heritage.
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Service Type: Design and Renovation Services	
Service No.: S3 - Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	
Service Observed:	The project envisioned three main areas of activity: Community and Culture, Knowledge and Creativity, and Tourism and Development, which served as the decision-making principles for the renovation planning.
Applicability to the pilot:	The three pillars used in Old Ironworks- Community and Culture, Knowledge and Creativity, and Tourism and Development - can serve as the core principles for the new renovation planning of the ELLET building on Tripodon Street. They would ensure that the project would not only restore the building’s physical structure but also reactivate it as a dynamic node for local engagement, learning, and reaching economic sustainability.

Service Type: Monitoring, Operation, and Management of Services	
Service No.: S4 - IEQ and thermal comfort optimization	
Service Observed:	The project site uses excess heat from SIJ’s steel production to heat, demonstrating a commitment to circularity and responsible steel production.
Applicability to the pilot:	Difficult to apply. The Old Ironworks project showcases the use of excess heat from the nearby steel factory, which cannot be replicated in our pilot case, as it is far away from industrial or production zones. It may be possible on a smaller scale, but further investigation is required. As the ELLET building is a historical structure located in the city centre, there is no indication of a nearby metallurgical plant or similar industrial process that would generate the significant amount of waste heat required for this type of system. Therefore, no modifications would make this specific application feasible for the ELLET building.

What are the Resources Required for the Successful Implementation of Services?

Needs of the pilot partners to apply the relevant service types to their respective pilots, which includes challenges, modifications required, or areas where the technology could enhance the overall process

Service Type: Design and Renovation Services
Service No.: S3 - Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning

- **Economic Resources:** A programming study of cultural activities needs to be funded, as well as a new structural renovation to support new educational and creative spaces.
- **Technical Resources:** A programming study of cultural activities and a new structural renovation to support new educational and creative spaces.
- **Human Resources:** Content development and interpretation specialists and heritage architects.

Service Type: Monitoring, Operation, and Management of Services

Service No.: S4 - IEQ and thermal comfort optimization

- **Economic Resources:** Not known
- **Technical Resources:** Energy experts need to investigate the area for a possible way to achieve circularity.
- **Human Resources:** Requires energy experts

3.4.3.3 Assessment of Services' Outcomes and Further Applications

Includes assessment of the efficiency, expected outcomes, and measurements to prove the KPIs of the tools/technology used in the case study, and additional applications of the technology that deliver comparable outcomes and efficiency

Service Type: Monitoring, Operation, and Management of Services

Service No.: S4 - IEQ and thermal comfort optimization

- **Beneficial Use of Waste Heat from Metallurgical Processes:** This energy solution uses waste heat from steel production for district heating and hot water. This significantly reduces energy consumption by recovering heat and minimising the need for natural gas. Environmentally, it substantially lowers CO2 emissions.
- **Cost Recovery:** Economically, the initial cost was quickly recovered through considerable annual savings. The project also supports the Sustainable Development Goals by preventing increased air, water, or soil pollution.
- **Additional Applications with comparable outcomes or efficiency:** Waste heat recovery for district heating has been primarily used for larger-scale constructions, namely data centres or commercial buildings. However, this could also be applied to heat a group of residences, including historical buildings like the ELLET building.

Service Type: Design and renovation services

Service No.: S1 - Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces or heritage building

- **Interactive Technology Usage:** While still under development, digital and visual technologies are planned for the museum would offer an immersive experience of iron and steel making
- **Additional Applications with comparable outcomes or efficiency:** AR tours could overlay digital information, historical reconstructions, or animated content onto physical artefacts or spaces, thus providing interactive narratives. Another application is that it supports gamification by integrating elements like challenges, quizzes, or scavenger hunts to make learning more interactive and enjoyable. An example of this is the Victoria and Albert Museum in London, which successfully used playful physical interaction in its "Digital Dragons" exhibition.

3.4.3.4 Stakeholder Participation and Engagement

Overview of Stakeholder Roles in the Project Case Study

Gives an overview of the stakeholders involved in the case study project

The project brought together a range of local actors. The municipality contributed funding and ensured that the work complied with heritage regulations. A nearby university supported the effort through research and simulation modelling. Architects guided the restoration design, while a citizens' group took part in the wider process. Craftspeople completed the traditional masonry repairs that grounded the project in local building practices.

Challenges Encountered across Stakeholder Consultation, Planning and Execution of the Project

Includes issues related to communication, collaboration, decision-making, or other factors that affected the project's progress

Planning Phase:

- **Cultural and Physical Isolation:** The Old Ironworks area was historically and physically separated from the rest of Ravne na Koroškem, which created difficulties in integrating it into the broader urban and social fabric
- **Stakeholder Coordination:** Although over 40 stakeholders at various levels (local to international) expressed interest, the initial engagement was mostly through individual calls and meetings.
- **Vision Reconciliation:** Aligning the project vision among the Municipality, Carinthian Regional Museum, and the Iskriva Institute required iterative consultations and adjustments.
- **Funding Strategy:** Developing a long-term funding and business model was necessary but challenging, requiring strategic foresight and stakeholder engagement.

Execution Phase:

- **Phased Implementation:** Due to the project's scope and limited resources, execution had to proceed in stages. This created dependencies and required ongoing adjustments to timelines and priorities. Unprecedented delays in permits and funding disbursement slowed progress.
- **Technical and Structural Limitations:** Many buildings were in poor condition. Renovation required careful restoration aligned with cultural heritage protection guidelines, which complicated the execution.
- **Balancing Heritage and Modern Use:** Adapting old industrial spaces (like the forge and laboratory) for new uses such as exhibitions, co-working, and events, as well as balancing modern technical upgrades with strict heritage rules further presented design, legal and technical hurdles.
- **Community Engagement:** Ensuring continued local community involvement and managing expectations during construction and limited access periods was an ongoing challenge.

Mechanisms Undertaken to Ensure Effective Stakeholder Participation during the above Phases

Includes strategies or approaches used to engage stakeholders and ensure their input was considered throughout the project

- **Multi-stakeholder engagement** at local, regional, national and international scales

- **Shared vision co-developed** through stakeholder input, with alignment from the project lead and key partner - the Carinthia Regional Museum. 50+ public and private organizations contributed to content creation, product development, marketing, and promotion.
- **Inclusive strategies** to ensure physical accessibility, involvement of vulnerable groups, and multidisciplinary collaboration across heritage, metallurgy, environmental protection, and the arts.
- **Stakeholder feedback** helped shape a multifunctional reuse concept for the industrial site, integrating innovative energy solutions and cultural elements. Their input also supported feasibility checks and the creation of a business plan extending to 2028.

Stakeholder Engagement Issues and Relevant Case Study Learnings and Key Takeaways

Gives a documentation of the challenges faced by the learning partner

Stakeholder Engagement Challenges: The ELLET building in Tripodon Street faces stakeholder engagement challenges, primarily due to its unique historical and administrative context. As a heritage site in the heart of Athens, balancing the involvement of public authorities, cultural heritage bodies, and local stakeholders while ensuring alignment with strict preservation regulations can be complex. Additionally, limited stakeholder awareness of energy efficiency opportunities in historical buildings has posed a barrier to broader engagement.

Relevant Learnings and Key Takeaways: Several valuable lessons emerged through the case, and a key takeaway is the benefit of early and structured stakeholder mapping and phased engagement, including individual outreach, workshops, and letters of intent, thereby fostering ownership and long-term commitment. The project also showed the importance of integrating cultural, educational, and economic objectives to appeal to diverse stakeholder interests. Applying these lessons could improve stakeholder involvement by initiating targeted consultations, highlighting the cultural and community value of energy improvements, and creating participatory platforms for shared planning. Expanding the narrative beyond technical upgrades to include cultural continuity and urban sustainability could also attract broader support.

Lessons Learned and Looking Beyond

Includes overall learnings from the study visits as it relates to the pilots, and additional resources from the pilots as it relates to the case study across methodology, technology, context, and outcomes

Further Insights Gained: Although not one of the services assigned to the pilot, it was noted that the digital and visual technologies, such as AR overlays and interactive displays, could create an immersive experience at the ELLET building, highlighting its history and artefacts. This would require installing new infrastructure, developing custom historical content, and integrating with the building's smart systems while preserving its heritage.

Challenges at Case-Study Site: The learning partner highlighted challenges in energy efficiency, structural preservation, and community access. The owner expressed a need for modernising operations while maintaining the building's cultural integrity. Advanced technologies and stakeholder collaboration played a key role in overcoming these challenges.

Additional Resources: Building on the insights gathered from the site visit, the pilot shared additional details of a site that aligned with the study visit and could support further learning:

Athens University Museum (Cleanthes Residence, Plaka)

- Overview: A historic 3-storey building (830 m²) subject to a deep energy retrofit under the [EU HAPPEN project](#). Relevance: common elements with ELLET's approach - integrates energy simulations, smart meters, lighting upgrades, and heat-pump systems, all under cultural heritage oversight.
- Stakeholder Engagement: Featured two online Living Labs involving policy makers, designers, and tech providers - an ideal model for participatory planning.

3.4.3.5 Photographs from the Study Visit

Figure 15: Dormitory building. Not renovated yet (under site description)

Figure 16: L- Guided tour by project architect; R- Museum (part of the building that is not renovated) with the collection of old machinery.

3.4.4 Pilot 4: Ave Sol Concert Hall - Riga, Latvia; Coordinator: RPR

Site Visited:	Old Ironworks Project, Ravne na Koroškem, Slovenia
Learning Partner:	Institut Iskriva
More information:	http://iskriva.net/
Location:	Ravne na Koroškem, Slovenia
Site Features:	Koroški pokrajinski muzej, Muzej Ravne na Koroškem

3.4.4.1 General Overview

Site Description

Includes details across building type, purpose, age, materials used, any unique features, challenges faced, and the owner's needs

The study visits focused on the municipality of Ravne na Koroškem, Slovenia, and the associated industrial and urban transformation initiatives. The primary site was the SIJ Metal Ravne steel production complex - one of Slovenia's oldest metallurgical facilities with a 400-year tradition, currently employing around 1,000 people. The production infrastructure comprises buildings and equipment of various ages and technical conditions, including heat treatment and rolling mills, which consume significant amounts of electricity and natural gas.

A unique feature of the site is the integration of industrial waste heat into the local district heating network, marking the first such project in Slovenia. The challenge faced was how to efficiently capture, transfer, and utilise excess heat from the furnace, considering non-continuous operations and fluctuating heat availability. This required close collaboration between the stakeholders.

Old Ironworks Museum area, part of the historical industrial complex, is undergoing transformation into a multifunctional cultural and innovation hub. The owner (municipality) aims to strike a balance between preserving industrial heritage and achieving green transition goals, promoting energy efficiency, and enhancing local quality of life. Transferred to the Municipality of Ravne in 2002, it now serves as a steelmaking museum. It includes the edging forge, a former dormitory with laundry facilities, a chemical laboratory, and a blacksmith workshop. The brick and iron buildings feature vaulted ceilings and preserved industrial elements. Key challenges included improving energy efficiency, ensuring structural preservation, and enhancing community access, all of which were addressed through stakeholder collaboration and the use of modern technologies, while maintaining cultural integrity.

Also visited in Ravne was a historic manor currently undergoing renovation. The renovation is nearly complete, featuring a modern wooden extension that complements the historic building. It was particularly interesting to observe how the old structure was harmoniously enhanced with contemporary architectural elements, exemplifying thoughtful heritage integration. In Ljubljana, two sites were explored. First, the New Center Rog, a renovated former factory, now serves as a social and creative hub that preserves its artisanal and production heritage while promoting craftsmanship, design, and applied arts. Second, a historic palace was visited where digital

technologies were demonstrated in the context of cultural heritage, showcasing innovative approaches to preservation, interpretation, and public engagement.

Themes Addressed

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective themes, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness

5 - Most Relevant, 1 - Least Relevant

THEME 1: Human-centred and life-centred approaches to Cultural Heritage

A key learning experience was the demonstration of how industrial and historical heritage can be revitalised through inclusive, community-driven approaches. The transformation of a steel industry site into a vibrant cultural and innovation space in Ravne showed how tradition can coexist with future-oriented development. The manor’s renovation illustrated how contemporary design can respectfully enhance historic structures. Ljubljana’s Centre Rog revealed the challenges of participatory planning, especially when project goals shift, underscoring the need for clear communication and inclusive dialogue. These examples were both inspiring and practically relevant for integrating cultural heritage into urban sustainability strategies.

THEME 2: Resource efficiency and circularity

While resource efficiency and circularity were not the central focus of most case studies, the example of waste heat recovery from SIJ Metal Ravne was a strong and practical demonstration of circular economy principles in action. This initiative demonstrated how industrial excess heat can be captured and reused in the local district heating system, reducing fossil fuel use, lowering emissions, and enhancing local energy resilience. In contrast, other examples, such as heritage building renovations and cultural reuse projects, paid less attention to energy efficiency or renewable integration. Nonetheless, these projects still offered potential for future energy improvements through enhanced building performance, the use of sustainable materials, or improved energy monitoring. The main takeaway is that even in culture-led projects, there are overlooked opportunities to embed circularity and resource efficiency - especially if identified early in the design phase.

THEME 3: Capacity for innovative, transdisciplinary, and contemporary approaches

The study visit offered valuable insights into how digital technologies can enrich the interpretation and communication of cultural heritage. This was particularly evident at Ljubljana Castle, where immersive tools and digital storytelling were used to present the building’s history in engaging and accessible ways. These approaches not only enhance the visitor experience but also make cultural content more inclusive and future-proof. The integration of new technologies within historical settings demonstrated how innovation and heritage can complement each other. While not all sites applied these tools, this example highlighted the potential of combining digital methods with preservation strategies - an approach that is increasingly relevant for sustainable heritage management and aligns well with our pilot’s goals.

Which NEB Pillars are addressed by this Case Study?

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective NEB pillars, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness

5 - Most Relevant; 1 - Least Relevant

Pillar 1: Sustainability

Several case studies, particularly the waste heat recovery project in Ravne and the broader transformation of the district heating system, clearly addressed sustainability through energy reuse, reduction of CO₂ emissions, and industrial symbiosis. While some heritage renovation projects lacked strong integration of renewable energy, the overall direction aligns with climate

and resource conservation goals. The potential for energy improvements in cultural spaces was acknowledged but not fully developed in all examples.

Pillar 2: Inclusion

The New Centre Rog in Ljubljana showcased how cultural spaces can be shaped through community participation, although it also highlighted the challenges of inclusive governance when visions change over time. The Old Ironworks project in Ravne, with over 40 partners, exemplifies how a multi-stakeholder, inclusive process can guide heritage transformation. These experiences are valuable for pilots aiming to involve diverse groups and build shared ownership.

Pillar 3: Aesthetic/ Beauty

The architectural dialogue between old and new, especially in the renovated manor house with a modern wooden extension and in Old Ironworks revitalisation, demonstrated thoughtful integration of historical identity with contemporary design.

Steps of the Case’s Execution that were Most Inspiring and Relevant to the Pilot

Further includes the level of difficulty with regard to its applicability to the pilot

- **Phase-wise approach to project execution:** One of the most inspiring parts was the step-by-step process - starting with analysis, then working together on the design, securing funding, and finally carrying out the project. This was clearly seen in the Old Ironworks renovation, where over 40 local, national, and international partners were involved, helping to build strong support for the project. Equally impressive was the municipality’s openness to new ideas and continuous learning, acting as a key enabler throughout the projects.
- **Innovative Circular Practices:** The use of excess heat from the nearby steel factory demonstrated an innovative circular economy solution. While this specific approach isn’t applicable to RPR’s pilot due to the lack of nearby industry, it inspired the exploration of alternative energy management strategies, particularly digital tools like those presented by Reduxi. Their AI-based system for real-time optimisation, dynamic tariffs, and device control offers a promising model.

At the Ave Sol Concert Hall pilot, there is already support for improving building energy performance. The visit confirmed that with the right process and partnerships, sustainable innovation in heritage contexts is both feasible and impactful.

3.4.4.2 Applicability of Methods, Tools and Services to INHERIT Pilots

Pilot-wise Technology Learning and Applicability

Overview and Applicability of Technologies to the INHERIT Pilots

Service Type: Data Collection and Sharing	
Service No.: S0 - Heritage Buildings’ Smartification and Data Exchange	
Service Observed:	Smartification was not a primary focus in most heritage sites, but examples like Reduxi’s system showed potential for integrating real-time data exchange for energy use. Data sharing between partners in Ravne (e.g., SIJ Metal and Petrol) enabled optimized energy flows.

Applicability to the pilot:	This service would need modification when applied to the pilot. Data-driven energy management was demonstrated through Reduxi's smart systems, though heritage sites lacked such integration. Smartification could greatly enhance energy monitoring in historic buildings.
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Service Type: Design & renovation services	
Service No.: S1 - Interactive screen use and AR-VR interfaces	
Service Observed:	At Ljubljana Castle, interactive digital tools were effectively utilised to enhance storytelling. However, no direct use of AR/VR was observed in design or construction contexts.
Applicability to the pilot:	This would be difficult to apply. Interactive screens were used at Ljubljana Castle for storytelling, but not for planning. AR/VR could help visualise the impacts of renovation in protected buildings.

Service Type: Design & renovation services	
Service No.: S2 - Modelling and simulation environment	
Service Observed:	Simulation tools were not directly demonstrated during the visit, but the structured renovation phases at Old Ironworks suggest modelling was likely part of early planning.
Applicability to the pilot:	Difficult. Though not directly shown, project phasing suggests use of modelling tools in design preparation. These tools would be valuable for assessing energy interventions in heritage buildings.

Service Type: Design & renovation services	
Service No.: S3 - Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	
Service Observed:	Although no digital tools were explicitly shown, stakeholder coordination and phased planning in Ravne indicate that structured decision-making frameworks were applied effectively.
Applicability to the pilot:	This would need modification when applied to the RPR's pilot. No digital tools were presented, but structured stakeholder-driven planning was evident in Ravne. A DSS could support renovation prioritisation.

Service Type: Monitoring, operation & management services	
Service No.: S5 - Energy forecasting and intelligent management	
Service Observed:	Reduxi's AI-based system showcased how intelligent forecasting and automated control can support smart energy use, particularly for buildings with PV or storage.
Applicability to the pilot:	Easy. Reduxi's platform demonstrated advanced forecasting and control. Could be integrated in renovated heritage buildings to optimise consumption. At Ave Sol Concert Hall, the smart energy management approach demonstrated by Reduxi could be applied to optimize heating and hot water systems in the concert hall, especially

	<p>with the planned integration of a heat pump. Real-time monitoring and control based on dynamic energy prices (e.g., Nord Pool) would help reduce operational costs and improve energy efficiency. To apply this technology, some modifications would be needed: the system must be adapted to the building’s heritage constraints (e.g., non-invasive sensor installation) and tailored to seasonal use patterns. A simplified interface for facility managers would also be necessary to support daily operations.</p>
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What are the Resources Required for the Successful Implementation of Services?

Needs of the pilot partners to apply the relevant service types to their respective pilots, which includes challenges, modifications required, or areas where the technology could enhance the overall process

Service Type: Data collection & sharing

Service No.: S0 - Heritage buildings smartification & data exchange

- **Economic Resources:** Implementing a smartification system with sensors and data exchange tools requires investment in reliable, minimally invasive hardware that is compatible with heritage protection guidelines. Funding is needed for integration into existing electrical systems and ongoing data management.
- **Governmental Support:** Support is essential for enabling data-sharing policies, installing sensors in public heritage buildings, and aligning with municipal-level energy strategies. Cooperation with the local authority ensures smoother permitting, especially for protected cultural sites

Service Type: Design & renovation services

Service No.: S2 - Modelling and simulation environment

- **Technical Resources:** Application of modelling tools will require building a detailed digital model, including envelope performance, internal gains, usage profiles, and HVAC system characteristics. Technical expertise is needed for accurate calibration and scenario testing.

Service Type: Design & Renovation Services

Service No.: S3 - Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning

- **Human Resources:** Developing and applying a Decision Support Tool for renovation prioritisation will require interdisciplinary collaboration: architects, engineers, energy modelers, and heritage specialists. Internal project teams will need training to interpret results and align technical outputs with conservation goals.
- **Governmental Support:** Institutional support helps embed renovation planning in long-term strategies. Local governments can also assist with stakeholder engagement and co-financing of retrofit measures.

Service Type: Monitoring, operation & management services

Service No.: S4 - IEQ and thermal comfort optimization

- **Technical Resources:** To monitor and optimise indoor environmental quality (IEQ), high-resolution sensors and control interfaces will be required. Technical solutions must be

compatible with historic architecture (e.g., discreet placement, wireless connectivity), and may require expert integration with the HVAC upgrade.

Service Type: Monitoring, operation & management services**Service No.: S5** - Energy forecasting and intelligent management

- **Economic Resources:** Implement intelligent energy management based on market prices (e.g. Nord Pool), financial resources are needed for software licenses, smart meters, and integration with the planned heat pump and HVAC systems. Return on investment is expected through long-term energy savings.
- **Other:** Integration with Nord Pool or national energy exchange platforms requires coordination with utilities or aggregators. Legal frameworks, energy contracts, and market participation rules must be clarified to enable dynamic pricing integration and flexibility services for cultural buildings.

Service Type: Preservation & maintenance services**Service No.: S9** - GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance

- **Human Resources:** A GIS-based platform for heritage maintenance requires skilled personnel to digitize and manage spatial data layers related to building condition, renovation phases, and utility infrastructure. Capacity building in GIS tools is needed for ongoing use.

3.4.4.3 Assessment of Services' Outcomes and Further Applications

Includes assessment of the efficiency, expected outcomes and measurements to prove the KPIs of the tools/technology used in the case study, and additional applications of the technology that deliver comparable outcomes and efficiency

Service Type: Monitoring, operation & management services**Service No.: S4** - IEQ and thermal comfort optimization

- **Energy Optimisation:** Based on information provided, the SIJ Metal Ravne waste heat recovery project was presented as a successful case with clear efficiency data. The system supplies approximately 7,100 MWh/year to the district heating network, accounting for 20% of the total heat demand, and reduces CO₂ emissions by 1,413 tonnes annually.
- **Cost Recovery:** The investment had a payback period of 2.2 years. digital and visual technologies are planned for the museum to offer an immersive experience of iron and steel making, though these are still under development.

Service Type: Monitoring, operation & management services**Service No.: S5** - Energy forecasting and intelligent management

- **Leveraging AI-based energy management:** Reduxi presented its AI-based energy management tool, which can achieve a good ROI by optimising heat and water use, with data collected in real time.
- **Additional Applications with comparable outcomes or efficiency:** Research shows AI operated heat pump systems can significantly improve performance by forecasting demand and adjusting operations dynamically. Another AI-based HVAC system in a commercial building reduced energy use. Digital twins provide a solid foundation to monitor and manage IEQ and climate-related risks.

3.4.4.4 Stakeholder Participation and Engagement

Overview of Stakeholder Roles in the Project Case Study

Gives an overview of the stakeholders involved in the case study project

The project brought together a range of local actors. The municipality contributed funding and ensured that the work complied with heritage regulations. A nearby university supported the effort through research and simulation modelling. Architects guided the restoration design, while a citizens' group took part in the wider process. Craftspeople completed the traditional masonry repairs that grounded the project in local building practices.

Challenges Encountered across Stakeholder Consultation, Planning and Execution of the Project

Includes issues related to communication, collaboration, decision-making, or other factors that affected the project's progress

Planning Phase:

- **Multistakeholder Alignment:** Aligning the interests of diverse stakeholders - from cultural institutions and municipal authorities to private companies and local communities- emerged as a challenge for the learning partner.

Execution Phase:

- **Coordination and Execution across Stakeholder Levels:** During implementation, coordination across multiple partners became complex, especially in managing timelines and responsibilities. Unexpected delays in permitting and funding disbursement slowed progress. Many buildings were in poor condition. Renovation required careful restoration aligned with cultural heritage protection guidelines, which complicated the execution.
- **Resource Strain:** For the municipality, project involvement brought additional workload, particularly in organising and hosting study visits and delegations. Excursion planning and visitor coordination required extra staff resources, often stretching limited local capacities. Balancing modern technical upgrades with strict heritage rules also presented legal and technical hurdles. Despite these issues, strong leadership and flexible collaboration helped maintain momentum and ensure progress.

Mechanisms Undertaken to Ensure Effective Stakeholder Participation during the above Phases

Includes strategies or approaches used to engage stakeholders and ensure their input was considered throughout the project

- **Stakeholder participation** was ensured through engagement at all levels, local to international. A shared vision was developed in collaboration with key partners, including the Carinthia Regional Museum. More than 50 organisations contributed to content, product development, and promotion.
- **Inclusive planning** involved vulnerable groups and ensured accessibility. Experts from various fields, including heritage, energy, environment, and the arts, collaborated to develop a multifunctional reuse concept. Stakeholder input also supported feasibility checks and contributed to the development of a long-term business plan through 2028.

Stakeholder Engagement Issues and Relevant Case Study Learnings and Key Takeaways

Gives a documentation of the challenges faced by the learning partner

Relevant Learnings and Key Takeaways: For RPR's pilot project in Riga, all stakeholders generally agree that the building needs renovation; however, the financing model remains unclear, which limits deeper engagement and long-term planning. At this stage, only partial modernisation and smartification of the building is possible. This case study demonstrates that early stakeholder involvement and transparent planning, particularly regarding funding, can foster trust and broader support. Applying this approach could help RPR clarify priorities and strengthen collaboration in its pilot.

Lessons Learned and Looking Beyond

Includes overall learnings from the study visits as it relates to the pilots, and additional resources from the pilots as it relates to the case study across methodology, technology, context, and outcomes

Additional Resources: In recent years, there has been a growing focus in Latvia on the restoration of cultural heritage, with increasing attention now also being given to industrial heritage, which had been neglected for a long time. While many projects concentrate on preserving historical architecture, fewer examples successfully introduce new, viable economic models into heritage buildings. However, such cases are becoming more common, both in publicly owned and privately managed properties. For example, Kuldīga, recently inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List, presents a compelling case for the integration of heritage management. Also revitalises industrial sites, such as former breweries, by combining cultural, economic, and tourism functions.

The Āgenskalns Market in Riga is another notable case, where a historic building has been restored and reactivated as a vibrant cultural and food space. The Kalnciema Quarter, a restored wooden building ensemble in Riga, showcases community and private initiative-led regeneration and multifunctional use, merging cultural, economic, and social values. Similarly, the Alūksne narrow-gauge railway station has been carefully restored, combining industrial heritage preservation with educational tourism and public engagement.

However, these projects also highlight a broader need for faster integration of digital technologies in heritage revitalisation. So far, the main focus remains on cultural and architectural restoration, while aspects such as smart building systems, energy optimisation, and digital visitor experiences receive less attention. Integrating these technologies requires significant additional resources and investment but is essential for long-term sustainability and relevance.

3.4.4.5 Photographs from the Study Visit

Figure 17: Historic manor currently undergoing renovation

Figure 18: L- Outside view of the main building - The New Centre Rog. Industrial heritage building, C. The renovation is nearly complete, featuring a modern wooden extension that complements the historic building. R - Space for workshops/laboratories and exhibitions. Space for studies and lectures.

3.4.5 Pilot 5: Social Residential Building in Gdynia, Poland; Coordinator: FASADA

Site Visited:	Paphos Gate, Cyprus
Learning Partner:	The Cyprus Institute
More information:	https://www.cyi.ac.cy/
Location:	Nicosia, Cyprus
Site Features:	Building Type: Military Barracks Building Construction Date: 1863

3.4.5.1 General Overview

Site Description

Includes details across building type, purpose, age, materials used, any unique features, challenges faced, and the owner's needs

The listed historic building is located near the medieval walls of Nicosia, adjacent to the Arab-Ahmet district. Built in 1863, it initially served as a British cavalry club before being converted into barracks for the Danish-Canadian military in Cyprus.

Its architecture blends colonial elements, such as a stone turret, gable roof, and pediments, with traditional Cypriot features like an inner courtyard and a porticoed entrance. The structure consists of load-bearing limestone walls, wooden partitions, adobe walls, and various interior finishes. A sloped roof and wooden floors add historical character.

To better understand the owners' needs, numerous meetings were held. However, the future users had a clear vision of their requirements, as the folklore museum currently operates in a different location, and its management was well aware of the spatial arrangements necessary for its functionality.

As part of the project, conferences were also organised for architects, specialists, and decision-makers to disseminate knowledge about the implemented solutions.

Themes Addressed

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective themes, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness

5 - Most Relevant ; 1 - Least Relevant

THEME 1: Human-centred and life-centred approaches to Cultural Heritage

The work undertaken in this case study focused primarily on ecological impacts rather than social engagement. The primary objective of the project was to adopt a holistic approach to the building's energy efficiency, incorporating both sustainable technological solutions and comprehensive energy performance. Stakeholder involvement primarily focused on understanding the needs of end-users, ensuring that the proposed solutions aligned with their expectations. Additionally, conferences were organised for specialists and authorities responsible for the building's future to promote the new approach to historic building renovations.

THEME 2: Resource efficiency and circularity

The solutions adopted in the project were based on an assessment of whether the intervention aligns with specific environmental sustainability principles. This includes minimising environmental pollution and indoor emissions, maximising the use of renewable resources, incorporating recyclable or reused materials, and selecting materials with low embodied energy whenever possible. At the same time, the solutions are designed to ensure minimal intervention, reversibility of the introduced changes, and compatibility of materials with the CH building.

THEME 3: Capacity for innovative, transdisciplinary, and contemporary approaches

The solutions applied in the case study emphasise the use of transdisciplinary approaches that enable a comprehensive understanding of the building. The implementation of the H-BIM model, AR/VR techniques, and energy analysis models forms the foundation of a modern approach to renovating CH buildings.

Which NEB Pillars are addressed by this Case Study?

*Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective NEB pillars, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness
5 - Most Relevant ; 1 - Least Relevant*

Pillar 1: Sustainability

The primary objective of the project was to conduct a detailed energy analysis of the building and propose solutions that enhance sustainable development and resource efficiency, while respecting the cultural heritage.

Pillar 2: Inclusion

The project did not place a strong emphasis on inclusivity and accessibility. However, the building's future function as a folklore museum and its location near the buffer zone contribute to its character as an open and welcoming space.

Pillar 3: Aesthetic/ Beauty

The proposed solutions emphasise preserving the historic form, including the integration of architectural styles that highlight the building's multicultural history and the removal of annexes without historical significance. Attention to detail and the use of minimally invasive interventions further underscore the importance of this theme.

Steps of the Case's Execution that were Most Inspiring and Relevant to the Pilot

Further includes the level of difficulty with regard to its applicability to the pilot

In the study visit participated FASADA and two invited representatives of the Energy Department of Municipality of Gdynia- (owner of Pilot 5).

The approach of the entire process was particularly interesting as it facilitates decision-makers in making rational choices that, while respecting heritage, allow for the optimal use of existing resources to support sustainable development. All the tools that enable presenting information about the building, such as H-BIM and the use of augmented reality, make this possible. The primary challenge for FASADA is conducting accurate energy analyses of the building, which is hindered by limited access to certain apartments, a lack of historical data on energy consumption in individual apartments, and the absence of information regarding equipment and lighting in inaccessible apartments.

3.4.5.2 Applicability of Methods, Tools and Services to INHERIT Pilots

Pilot-wise Technology Learning and Applicability

Overview and Applicability of Technologies to the INHERIT Pilots

Service Type: Design & renovation services Service No.: S1 - Interactive screen use and AR-VR interfaces for heritage building	
Service Observed:	AR technology was used to present the building after renovation, illustrating how the planned works and implemented smart solutions will impact its functionality, while preserving the historical value of the structure to the greatest extent possible. The technology was utilized to present the concept to decision-makers, facilitating the evaluation of the proposed actions.
Applicability to the pilot:	The tool implemented by FASADA is intended to present the visual aspect of renovation scenarios to stakeholders, including heritage conservators, building managers, and users. The goal is to persuade decision-makers to choose solutions that are the most energy-efficient, while simultaneously respecting cultural heritage. The application of the tool is made possible by the data collected so far, including the 3D scan and the BIM model. The tool is easy to use, although its implementation differs slightly from the approach used in the Cyprus site. A potential challenge may be collaboration with the local authorities.
Service Type: Preservation & maintenance services Service No.: S8 - Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	
Service Observed:	In this case study, the H-BIM model was developed to conduct energy analyses. It was exported to a gbXML file, and energy simulations were carried out using appropriate software for various scenarios. The definition of HBIM used in this project differs from that adopted in the INHERIT project - in our case, H-BIM serves as a source of information about the building's elements.
Applicability to the pilot:	In the pilot in Gdynia, the tool, serving as an information base in the form of a 3D model, has been used in a slightly different way. Energy simulations will be carried out within the framework of a Digital Twin model. The implementation will be relatively straightforward. However, limited access to certain areas and the lack of complete data may pose challenges.

What are the Resources Required for the Successful Implementation of Services?

Needs of the pilot partners to apply the relevant service types to their respective pilots, which includes challenges, modifications required, or areas where the technology could enhance the overall process

Service Type: Design and renovation**Service No.:** S1 - Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces

- **Economic Resources:** Funding for equipment and software
- **Technical Resources:** Computer equipment, AR/VR devices, accessories
- **Human Resources:** Pilot partner; Service provider
- **Governmental Support.:** Cooperation with the local government as the owner of the pilot building. Cooperation with the energy department of the city council. Cooperation with the office of the municipal heritage conservator.

Service Type: Preservation and maintenance**Service No.:** S8 - Preventive maintenance with H-BIM

- **Economic Resources:** Funding for equipment and software
- **Technical Resources:** Computer equipment
- **Human Resources:** Pilot partner; Service provider
- **Governmental Support.:** Cooperation with the local government as the owner of the pilot building. Cooperation with the energy department of the city council. Cooperation with the office of the municipal heritage conservator.

3.4.5.3 Assessment of Services' Outcomes and Further Applications

Includes assessment of the efficiency, expected outcomes and measurements to prove the KPIs of the tools/technology used in the case study, and additional applications of the technology that deliver comparable outcomes and efficiency

Service Type: Design & renovation services**Service No.:** S1 - Interactive screen use and AR-VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction

- **AR/VR for Clearer Insights:** The use of AR/VR technology allowed for a clearer presentation of the findings from the analyses carried out in the initial phases of the project. Presenting the results to decision-makers facilitated the selection of the optimal solution and supported the acquisition of funding for renovation.

Service Type: Preservation & maintenance services**Service No.:** S8 - Preventive maintenance with H-BIM

- **Efficiency Gains with Minimal Intervention:** The HBIM model and the derivative models used to assess the energy efficiency of various solutions helped identify options that minimise interference with the historical fabric of the building

3.4.5.4 Stakeholder Participation and Engagement

Overview of Stakeholder Roles in the Project Case Study

Gives an overview of the stakeholders involved in the case study project

The initiative involved municipal decision-makers who owned the building and oversaw key choices, together with the municipal heritage conservator responsible for determining the extent of cultural heritage protection. Future building managers from the local folklore museum contributed as

anticipated users of the restored space. Experts and architects also participated, drawing on the knowledge they acquired through a series of organised conferences.

Challenges Encountered across Stakeholder Consultation, Planning and Execution of the Project

Includes issues related to communication, collaboration, decision-making, or other factors that affected the project's progress

Planning Phase: One of the main challenges during the planning phase was the lack of unified communication among stakeholders. Each group participated in bilateral meetings, bringing its own agenda and expectations, without a shared understanding of the project's overall goals. This led to fragmented discussions and difficulties in aligning priorities. Moreover, trust had not yet been established, and stakeholders were initially hesitant to engage openly. The project team had to invest significant effort in demonstrating the mutual benefits of collaboration and ensuring that all parties felt their interests were being adequately considered. Another challenge was that many stakeholders had already developed internal plans for the use of the heritage building, which did not always align with the project's research-oriented and integrated approach.

Execution Phase: As the project moved into its implementation phase, the engagement of stakeholders across various levels became crucial. This included not only senior decision-makers, such as local authorities and museum directors, but also technical personnel like engineers and administrative staff. One of the key challenges was to convince these groups to revise and adapt their previously fixed plans based on the project's findings. This required careful negotiation and a willingness to be flexible on all sides. The project's strength lay in its solid methodology and the use of data-driven evidence, which proved persuasive in supporting decision-making. Eventually, the collaboration was formalised through a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), which helped ensure that the project's outcomes would influence future actions and renovation decisions.

Mechanisms Undertaken to Ensure Effective Stakeholder Participation during the above Phases

Includes strategies or approaches used to engage stakeholders and ensure their input was considered throughout the project

Ensuring Effective Stakeholder Participation: To enable this, multiple strategies were employed throughout the planning and implementation phases of the pilot. Key decision-makers from the municipality, heritage authorities, and end-users of the building (the Folklore Museum) were engaged in regular consultations. Interactive presentations using AR/VR technologies were organised to visualise renovation scenarios in an accessible and understandable way. This helped stakeholders provide informed feedback and actively participate in the decision-making process. Additionally, dedicated conferences and workshops were held to share knowledge with architects and specialists. Stakeholder input was considered when selecting the most energy-efficient and heritage-respecting renovation approach.

Stakeholder Engagement Issues and Relevant Case Study Learnings and Key Takeaways

Gives a documentation of the challenges faced by the learning partner

Stakeholder Engagement Challenges: One major issue faced by FASADA is the lack of willingness from most of the building's residents to actively participate in the process. Additionally, communication with the local heritage conservator has been limited, and bureaucratic procedures

have slowed down progress. In this regard, the Cyprus case study presents valuable lessons. Initially, the stakeholders also worked independently, with little coordination or shared vision. What helped overcome this was consistent communication, building trust, and presenting evidence-based benefits, such as data-driven simulations and analyses. This approach convinced stakeholders that the project could support their own goals. For FASADA's case, applying similar strategies, such as creating strong communication channels, clearly presenting the project's benefits to residents and institutions, and engaging early with key authorities, could help reduce resistance.

Relevant Learnings and Key Takeaways: In the case of the social residential building in Gdynia, each service has a slightly different scope of application. AR/VR technology will primarily be used as an accessible tool to present various renovation scenarios to both decision-makers and building users. The H-BIM model will primarily serve as a knowledge base for the technical condition and protection status of individual building elements, rather than as a foundation for energy analysis. That function, within the INHERIT project, is carried out by the BIM model used in the Digital Twin service. FASADA's belief is that this different distribution of roles between the tools significantly facilitates the transfer of building data, eliminating the need for non-standard solutions and additional software. From the perspective of the initial implementation phase, the solutions adopted in the INHERIT project appear simpler, more universal, and therefore easier to replicate. However, if similar challenges are encountered during implementation, FASADA has received detailed step-by-step documentation from the Learning Partners in Cyprus explaining how they solved issues related to data integrity in the models.

Lessons Learned and Looking Beyond

Includes overall learnings from the study visits as it relates to the pilots, and additional resources from the pilots as it relates to the case study across methodology, technology, context, and outcomes

Additional Applications with comparable outcomes or efficiency: The use of BIM models for energy analysis, creation of Digital Twins, or presentation of renovation scenarios is also seen in other European projects such as **BuildON**, **Matabuild**, **Ashvin**, **BIM-SPEED**, and **P2ENDURE**. In each of these projects, the definitions of services with similar names vary slightly depending on the context and project needs, indicating that the understanding and application of these tools are still evolving. This diversity allows for flexible adaptation to specific project requirements and local conditions.

3.4.4.5 Photographs from the Study Visit

Figure 19: L- Visit to the site where the case study building is located; C- View from the street. R- "CYPRUS INSULA" exhibition – presentation of AR/VR technology used to reconstruct a model of the former appearance of a now-destroyed airport

Figure 20: L- Paphos Gate – visit to the project site that implemented AR/VR technology; R- Visit to the Cyprus Institute – demonstration of a VR environment based on the Paphos Gate model

3.4.6 Pilot 6: Monastery ‘Ntra. Sra. del Prado’ - Valladolid, Spain; Coordinator: CARTIF

Site Visited:	Baraccano historical complex
Learning Partner:	University of Bologna (Italy)
More information:	https://www.unibo.it/en
Location:	Santo Stefano district of Bologna (Via del Baraccano, 40124 Bologna BO, Italy)
Site Features:	Building Type: Community space Building Origin: 15th century

3.4.6.1 General Overview

Site Description

Includes details across building type, purpose, age, materials used, any unique features, challenges faced, and the owner’s needs

The Baraccano complex, situated in the Santo Stefano district of Bologna, is a historically significant area that features religious and civic buildings, including the Sanctuary of Santa Maria del Baraccano and the former Conservatorio delle Putte. Originating in the 15th century, the complex was created to support and educate disadvantaged young women. Architecturally, it features notable elements, such as the “Voltone del Baraccano” (1497), and is part of Bologna’s UNESCO-listed portico system. In recent years, the Baraccano has been transformed into a vibrant community space, now home to the “Casa delle Associazioni”, which hosts a diverse range of cultural, social, and educational activities. This transformation demonstrates how historic structures can be reactivated to serve modern community needs while preserving their heritage value.

Equally important is the regeneration of the surrounding neighbourhood. Considered a marginal area of Bologna, largely abandoned just a decade ago, the district is now undergoing a process of urban renewal. Public and private efforts have improved infrastructure, public spaces, and social cohesion, turning it into a more inclusive and dynamic part of the city.

This dual significance (heritage conservation - according to the *Carta del Rischio* - and urban revitalization) makes the Baraccano complex a key case study for INHERIT, since this project promotes innovative, sustainable, and inclusive approaches to rehabilitating historic buildings.

Themes Addressed

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective themes, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness

5 - Most Relevant ; 1 - Least Relevant

THEME 1: Human-centred and life-centred approaches to Cultural Heritage

The Baraccano complex demonstrates exemplary community integration and urban regeneration through cultural heritage. This human-centred approach could be applied at the Monastery of Prado, where accessibility and inclusiveness are important but not core issues. Learning from Baraccano could help create a community engagement strategy

THEME 2: Resource efficiency and circularity

Baraccano showcases a successful model of adaptive reuse with attention to circularity. The reuse of materials and integration of low-impact technologies provide practical guidance for the Monastery of Prado's sustainable renovation plans.

THEME 3: Capacity for innovative, transdisciplinary, and contemporary approaches

The methodological framework at Baraccano integrates digital and risk-informed tools such as GIS, the *Carta del Rischio*, and H-BIM. This inspires the application of H-BIM and Digital Twin based strategies at the Monastery of Prado for scalable and real-time heritage management.

Which NEB Pillars are addressed by this Case Study?

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective NEB pillars, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness

5 - Most Relevant ; 1 - Least Relevant

Pillar 1: Sustainability

Baraccano integrates efficient resource use, adaptive reuse, and risk-informed maintenance. These strategies offer a practical model for sustainable conservation in complex urban settings like the Monastery of Prado.

Pillar 2: Inclusion

The multifunctional use of Baraccano fosters accessibility, community ownership, and inclusive cultural programming, providing a strong reference in case of transformation of the monastery of Prado into a cultural hub.

Pillar 3: Aesthetic/ Beauty

Baraccano's integration of historic architecture with contemporary use maintains visual harmony and enhances quality of life, a concept comparable in the architectural approach to the Monastery of Prado.

Steps of the Case's Execution that were Most Inspiring and Relevant to the Pilot

Further includes the level of difficulty with regard to its applicability to the pilot

Proactiveness towards Preventive Conservation: One of the most inspiring steps observed at Baraccano was the integration of preventive conservation into the broader urban and social regeneration process. Specifically, the early alignment of stakeholders (including the municipality, academic institutions, and civil society) enabled a shared long-term vision for adaptive reuse and proactive maintenance.

Leveraging Data-informed Tools: The use of tools like the Italian *Carta del Rischio*, combined with emerging GIS and H-BIM workflows, created a strategic framework that balances heritage values with functionality and resilience.

Applicability to Pilot: For the Monastery of Prado, this approach offers a valuable roadmap. The challenge in the future will be considering the level of inter-institutional collaboration and securing technical capacity early in the process. While the procedure is conceptually transferable, it requires adjustments to align with Spanish heritage protection laws, digital infrastructure gaps, and stakeholder dynamics. Therefore, although inspiring and operationally sound, these steps are difficult to apply without strong political support, technical expertise, and sustained investment.

3.4.6.2 Applicability of Methods, Tools and Services to INHERIT Pilots

Pilot-wise Technology Learning and Applicability

Overview and Applicability of Technologies to the INHERIT Pilots

Service Type: Data collection & sharing	
Service No.: S0 - Heritage buildings smartification & data exchange	
Service Observed:	Establishing an interoperable digital infrastructure from scratch in a highly protected heritage building is a real demand.
Service Type: Monitoring, operation & management services	
Service No.: S6 - Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring and management	
Service Observed:	Although not yet implemented, Baraccano discussed plans for integrating Digital Twins for real-time structural health monitoring.
Service Type: Preservation & maintenance services	
Service No.: S8 - Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	
Service Observed:	According to the needs and operation of GIS, Baraccano applies low-res H-BIM models integrated with risk mapping (<i>Carta del Rischio</i>) to guide maintenance. This enables proactive interventions and data-informed decisions to prevent long-term degradation. Working with H-BIM involves building-scale detail, capturing architectural, structural and material complexity. In contrast, GIS functions at an urban scale, where simplified building volumes suffice for spatial coordination. Bridging both systems is essential, as it connects detailed conservation with territorial planning.

What are the Resources Required for the Successful Implementation of Services?

Needs of the pilot partners to apply the relevant service types to their respective pilots, which includes challenges, modifications required, or areas where the technology could enhance the overall process

Service Type: Data collection & sharing

Service No.: S0 - Heritage buildings smartification & data exchange

- **Economic Resources:** Investment in data infrastructure including servers, digital archive systems, and software licenses for interoperable formats (e.g., IFC, XML).
- **Technical Resources:** Specialists in data architecture, digital heritage documentation, and standards for interoperability (e.g., CityGML, IFC).
- **Human Resources:** A coordination team to gather, organize, and maintain data exchange among conservation, monitoring, and planning tools.
- **Governmental Support:** Strategic alignment with regional digitalization policies and facilitation of access to municipal data and GIS portals.
- **Other:** Need for compliance with national and European regulations on cultural data use, as well as cybersecurity and privacy standards.

Service Type: Monitoring, operation & management services**Service No.:** S6 - Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring and management

- **Economic Resources:** High cost for sensor deployment (not sensors by themselves), but especially high for platform infrastructure.
- **Technical Resources:** Digital Twin specialists and infrastructure integration.
- **Human Resources:** High-expertise staff for system operation and maintenance.
- **Governmental Support:** Strategic support for piloting digital systems in protected heritage sites.

Service Type: Preservation & maintenance services**Service No.:** S8 - Preventive maintenance with H-BIM

- **Economic Resources:** Investment in software and scanning hardware.
- **Technical Resources:** H-BIM specialists familiar with conservation protocols.
- **Human Resources:** Team combining digital modelling and heritage expertise.
- **Governmental Support:** Institutional facilitation and integration with public data systems.

Service Type: Preservation & maintenance services**Service No.:** S9 - GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance

- **Economic Resources:** GIS system customization and database integration funding.
- **Technical Resources:** GIS professionals with heritage mapping experience.
- **Human Resources:** Field data collectors and database support team.
- **Governmental Support:** Coordination with urban planning and cultural heritage departments.

3.4.6.3 Assessment of Services' Outcomes and Further Applications

Includes assessment of the efficiency, expected outcomes and measurements to prove the KPIs of the tools/technology used in the case study, and additional applications of the technology that deliver comparable outcomes and efficiency

Service Type: Preservation & maintenance services**Service No.:** S8 - Preventive maintenance with H-BIM

Multi-layered Approach to Heritage Management: The assessment of tools and technologies implemented at Baraccano demonstrates a thoughtful and multi-layered approach to heritage management, with a strong emphasis on long-term sustainability. Central to this strategy is the application of H-BIM for preventive maintenance. Although the system is still under development, it facilitates structured documentation of architectural elements and condition assessments in line with Italy's Carta del Rischio. This approach supports risk-based prioritization of conservation efforts over time. GIS technologies complement this by situating building data within the broader urban context, thereby supporting informed decisions regarding public use and accessibility. Although a fully functional Digital Twin has yet to be realized, plans are in place to incorporate real-time monitoring capabilities in the future to enhance resilience.

Importantly, the work carried out by the University of Bologna has undergone review assessment by the Municipality of Bologna, which has confirmed the alignment of the implemented strategies with the defined KPIs, expected outcomes, and efficiency targets. This validation reinforces the

relevance and applicability of the chosen tools and methodologies in supporting sustainable heritage management.

Additional Applications with comparable outcomes or efficiency: There are several noteworthy technological initiatives that deliver comparable outcomes and efficiencies to those observed at Baraccano, particularly in the areas of H-BIM, preventive conservation, and multi-scale heritage data integration:

- European Directive 2014/24/EU: Mandatory adoption of BIM in public works across EU member states on public procurement, including those involving cultural heritage. This legislative framework requires the use of BIM to enhance transparency, efficiency, and sustainability in public sector construction. In the context of built cultural heritage, this directive catalyses the integration of HBIM into conservation practices. It encourages a more systematic, data-driven approach to documentation, maintenance, and intervention planning, thereby supporting the long-term preservation and informed stewardship of historical assets within the scope of publicly funded restoration and rehabilitation projects.
- ICCROM's Heritage Building Information Modelling Programme: Led by the International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property, this initiative explores the use of H-BIM for sustainable conservation planning and training. The Spanish contribution to this effort is particularly noteworthy, with the Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España (IPCE), under the Ministry of Culture, serving as the central body for coordinating and advancing national inputs within this international framework:

3.4.6.4 Stakeholder Participation and Engagement

Overview of Stakeholder Roles in the Project Case Study

Gives an overview of the stakeholders involved in the case study project

The project involved the local authority, which guided sustainable development and heritage-focused regeneration in the Baraccano area by aligning preservation with wider urban and social policies. A local hub for civic organisations also participated, contributing to the district's social and economic revitalisation by supporting community engagement, cultural exchange, and inclusive dialogue.

Challenges Encountered across Stakeholder Consultation, Planning, and Execution of the Project

Includes issues related to communication, collaboration, decision-making, or other factors that affected the project's progress

Planning Phase: Challenges arose from differing priorities and perspectives between the *Casa delle Associazioni* and the *Comune di Bologna*. While the *Casa* may emphasize grassroots needs, social inclusion, and cultural programming, the *Comune* focused more on regulatory compliance, infrastructure, and broader urban strategies. Misalignment in objectives could lead to delayed consensus, fragmented vision, or diluted planning outcomes, but solving communication gaps (especially by integrating formal and informal channels) resulted in avoiding a lack of transparency and increasing stakeholder trust.

Execution Phase: Issues of coordination and resource allocation often emerged. The hierarchical nature of municipal governance slowed decision-making, while community actors lacked the capacity to implement actions at the required scale. Additionally, conflicting timelines, limited

feedback loops, or insufficient mechanisms for shared monitoring hindered adaptability. These factors were mitigated to avoid risk weakening collaboration, reducing efficiency, and compromising the long-term impact of the revitalisation effort.

Mechanisms Undertaken to Ensure Effective Stakeholder Participation during the above Phases

Includes strategies or approaches used to engage stakeholders and ensure their input was considered throughout the project

- *Comune di Bologna*: Through targeted investments, regulatory frameworks, and support for community-driven initiatives, the *Comune* ensures that heritage assets are not only protected but also actively contribute to the well-being of local residents. By promoting inclusive access to historical spaces and facilitating partnerships (such as those involving the “Casa delle Associazioni” (see below) the municipality helps reinforce a shared sense of identity and belonging while improving living conditions, demonstrating how heritage conservation can serve as a catalyst for social and economic vitality in historic neighbourhoods.
- *Casa delle Associazioni*: By anchoring social activities within a historic setting, the *Casa* serves as a living example of how heritage spaces can be repurposed to meet contemporary needs while preserving their historical value. Its presence not only supports the development of local networks and grassroots initiatives but also contributes to a sense of belonging and collective identity. This reinforced sense of identity is directly linked to improved quality of life, as it encourages civic pride, promotes cultural continuity, and enhances the overall attractiveness and resilience of the neighbourhood for both inhabitants and visitors.

Stakeholder Engagement Issues and Relevant Case Study Learnings and Key Takeaways

Gives a documentation of the challenges faced by the learning partner

Stakeholder Engagement Challenges: The Monasterio del Prado in Spain and Baraccano in Italy are not directly comparable in terms of stakeholder engagement. Beyond the evident difference in scale, the two cases diverge significantly in their governance dynamics and participatory frameworks. In the case of the Monasterio del Prado, stakeholder involvement is limited exclusively to the Regional Government, which acts both as the building’s owner and the sole decision-making authority. Within the context of the INHERIT project, its role is strictly technical, focusing on defining and overseeing conservation actions without the participation of third parties, such as neighbourhood associations, individual citizens, or community groups. In contrast, Baraccano demonstrates a more complex and layered model of stakeholder engagement, involving municipal authorities, civic organizations, and the wider local community in both the planning and activation of heritage spaces. This distinction underscores the fundamentally different approaches adopted in each context regarding inclusivity, governance, and the integration of heritage into the social fabric.

Lessons Learned and Looking Beyond

Includes overall learnings from the study visits as it relates to the pilots, and additional resources from the pilots as it relates to the case study across methodology, technology, context, and outcomes

Further Insights Gained: Overall, Baraccano demonstrates that multiscale heritage technologies are most effective when they are both technically robust and institutionally supported. Their combined use sustains not only physical assets but also cultural and social continuity, making them a reference for application for CARTIF's work at the Monastery of Prado.

Additional Resources: There are no directly retrieved documents matching similar case studies to Baraccano in terms of H-BIM/GIS integration and civic engagement. However, two relevant examples are provided from broader knowledge that align with the methodology, technology, context, and outcomes seen in Baraccano:

The [OPENHERITAGE Project](#) (multiple EU Locations) was funded under Horizon 2020 and focused on adaptive reuse of heritage sites with inclusive governance models. A notable pilot was in Lisbon (Marvila), where a former wine warehouse was revitalised through a participatory model involving local communities, NGOs, and public authorities.

- **Relevance:** Very close to Baraccano in terms of stakeholder engagement, hybrid use of technology, and emphasis on cultural continuity.
- **Technology:** GIS-based mapping, digital engagement tools, participatory platforms.
- **Outcomes:** Stronger local identity, sustainable business models, and active community governance in heritage management.

As a notable point, Spain is currently making significant efforts to apply BIM to historic buildings, particularly for documentation and long-term planning purposes. These initiatives are primarily carried out through public procurement processes. A notable example is the recent tender launched by the Regional Government of Castilla y León for the digitisation of 101 cultural heritage assets (*Bienes de Interés Cultural*). However, due to the contractual nature and strategic sensitivity of these projects, access to the resulting BIM models and datasets is often restricted, making them unavailable publicly.

3.4.6.5 Photographs from the Study Visit

Figure 21: L & R-Tour of the Baraccano complex, situated in the Santo Stefano district of Bologna

Figure 22: L- INHERIT's Presentation; R- Walking in historic neighbourhood

3.4.7 Pilot 7: City of Visby, UNESCO World Heritage Site - Gotland, Sweden; Coordinator: UU

Site Visited:	Eleusis, Greece
Learning Partner:	HeritACT consortium, led by University of Patras
More information:	https://www.heritact.eu/
Location:	Eleusis, Greece
Site Features:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptive industrial reuse • Seafront cultural continuity

3.4.7.1 General Overview

Site Description

Includes details across building type, purpose, age, materials used, any unique features, challenges faced, and the owner's need

The HeritHUB is housed in Eleusis’s historic Old Canteen – a one-storey industrial canteen by the sea. Built in 1972 as a US Sixth Fleet facility, it was vacated after just two years and later became a beloved municipal canteen in the 1980s. Locals recall it as a summer meeting place (often paired with the adjacent open-air cinema). In 2023, as part of Eleusis’s European Capital of Culture legacy, the building underwent a full renovation to host cultural events. Today the Old Canteen is owned by the municipality (managed under Eleusis 2023 ECoC) and serves as the pilot’s main HeritHUB.

Building and use: Physically it is a simple industrial hall (concrete/steel frame) characteristic of 1970s service buildings. Inside, it is a single multi-purpose hall that accommodates art exhibitions, talks, educational programmes and community workshops. This reuse of a former industrial structure embodies the HeritACT pilot’s adaptive-reuse approach: it activates heritage space for contemporary community use. Unique features include its seafront location and connection to the old cinema, which together reinforce local memory. Challenges remain – some residents still remember it as a long-shuttered, inaccessible site – so the owner’s priority is making it an open, inclusive cultural hub that bridges Eleusis’s industrial past and its new role as a creative, community-driven city.

Themes Addressed

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective themes, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness

5 - Most Relevant ; 1 - Least Relevant

THEME 1: Human-centred and life-centred approaches to Cultural Heritage

The Eleusis pilot aligns very strongly with this theme. The methodology is rooted in co-recognition, co-envison and co-design activities, including surveys, workshops, and participatory design sessions with residents of all ages. This ensured that local voices shaped the pilot’s outcomes, from identifying cultural symbols (myth, industry, everyday life) to creating informed architectural and digital interventions. The visit showed how such methods transform cultural heritage into a living process, where accessibility, inclusion, and social innovation become integral parts of preservation and activation. That specific part is mostly relevant for the pilot in Sweden.

THEME 2: Resource efficiency and circularity

Resource efficiency is addressed through solutions like the “Green Tensegrity” and “temporary structures from recycled materials”, which prioritize low environmental impact and reuse of resources. While not the primary focus of the pilot, these interventions clearly demonstrate how circular economy principles can be embedded in heritage activation. The most impactful insight was that even small-scale, mobile installations can showcase sustainable practices and inspire broader urban regeneration

THEME 3: Capacity for innovative, transdisciplinary, and contemporary approaches

The pilot is inherently transdisciplinary, combining architecture, engineering, arts, and digital technologies. Solutions such as VR and AR, show how advanced tools can be integrated with cultural and social practices. The study visit highlighted how bringing together diverse expertise creates novel forms of cultural activation that are both technologically innovative and socially meaningful.

Which NEB Pillars are addressed by this case study?

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective NEB pillars, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness

5 – Most Relevant ; 1 – Least Relevant

Pillar 1: Sustainability

Sustainability is central to the Eleusis pilot. Solutions such as the Green Tensegrity, a small-scale pavilion, and temporary structures made from recycled materials embody environmentally responsible design, utilising durable and reusable materials. Activities also emphasized raising awareness of pollution and environmental challenges identified by the community. Together, these efforts promote ecological responsibility while minimising the project’s environmental impact.

Pillar 2: Inclusion

The pilot placed strong emphasis on accessibility and community participation. Through questionnaires, workshops, and co-design sessions, residents of different ages and backgrounds contributed to shaping the project. This inclusive methodology ensured that cultural diversity and local perspectives were reflected in both the process and the outcomes, strengthening ownership and social cohesion

Pillar 3: Aesthetic/ Beauty

The pilot combines technical innovation with creative cultural expression. Mobile furniture, and pavilion designs are not only functional but also visually engaging, enhancing the beauty of public space. While beauty is valued, it is approached as complementary to sustainability and inclusion, ensuring that visual appeal supports rather than overshadows community needs and identity.

Steps of the Case’s Execution that were Most Inspiring and Relevant to the Pilot

Further includes the level of difficulty with regard to its applicability to the pilot

The process of including local stakeholders and encouraging public participation was really inspiring and relevant for Visby. Eleusis used to be a purely industrial area, but now it has been transformed to a unique cultural centre.

While walking from one pilot building to another, the representative saw a poster and later on a similar graffiti on a school wall, saying: The motto ‘Eleusis, from misery to floweriness’. Upon discussing this with the HeritACT colleagues, it was realised that this had actually happened. Nevertheless, it could be materialised only with increased embracement of the local community that believed in the impossible! That, by working together, they could change the wind and make Eleusis the cultural capital of Europe! It was apparent that local people met regularly, exchanged ideas, planned, and then executed the plans in a continuous, co-participatory, and co-creation

exercise under real conditions. This collaborative effort yielded impressive results that could not have been achieved without the strong engagement of the local community. This is what we are also trying to achieve at Visby, and they found that the Eleusis example could be an excellent paradigm to follow.

3.4.7.2 Applicability of Methods, Tools and Services to INHERIT Pilots

Pilot-wise Technology Learning and Applicability

Overview and Applicability of Technologies to the INHERIT Pilots

Service Type: Data collection & sharing	
Service No.: S0 - Heritage buildings smartification & data exchange	
Service Observed:	During the visit, examples of how data could be collected and shared about Eleusis’s heritage environment were presented conceptually. While not exactly a smartification system, the pilot highlighted how participatory inputs and digital archives (e.g., virtual exhibition archives, AR, stop-motion animation for projection mapping) serve as data-sharing tools accessible to communities.
Applicability to the pilot:	It was found that the virtual exhibition archive and the data-sharing tools accessible to communities could be of use for the Visby pilot. There are actually already plans to include such services at Visby, and it is considered that the experience gained from the visit to the Eleusis pilot will enrich these plans.

Service Type: Design & renovation services	
Service No.: S1 - Interactive screen use and AR-VR interfaces for heritage building	
Service Observed:	During the visit, digital design tools were discussed conceptually rather than demonstrated hands-on. The Eleusis pilot integrates comparable approaches through the Virtual Exhibition Archive and AR-enriched interactions, which allow heritage content to be accessed and visualised in immersive ways. While not focused on building renovation per se, these tools show how interactive screens and AR/VR can be used to engage communities in reimagining cultural spaces and experiencing heritage in new formats
Applicability to the pilot:	Same as above

Service Type: Design & renovation services	
Service No.: S2 - Modelling and simulation environment	
Service Observed:	The modelling and simulation environment was partially demonstrated through architectural interventions’ renders in

	context. These provided a sense of how proposed structures (pavilion, tensegrity, temporary structures) would interact with the cityscape and cultural sites of Eleusis.
Applicability to the pilot:	It was observed that the participatory co-design and stakeholder engagement practices carried out at Eleusis could also act as part of a decision-making framework for the Visby pilot. Within the INHERIT framework of solutions, work is currently ongoing on co-designing the solutions available for the selected buildings. The usual questionnaires, workshops, and visual mock-ups that were used to formulate the priorities for solutions in Eleusis could be easily adopted in Sweden.

Service Type: Design & renovation services	
Service No.: S3 - Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	
Service Observed:	No formal decision-support software was demonstrated. Instead, participatory co-design and stakeholder engagement acted as a decision-making framework. Questionnaires, workshops, and visual mock-ups guided priorities for solutions in Eleusis, providing a socially informed basis for planning rather than an algorithmic tool.
Applicability to the pilot:	It was found that a certain adjusted size of the temporary structure that was observed could have an application to the pilot in Visby. Many cultural heritage public buildings in Visby are used mainly during the summer period, when there are many visitors, and a need arises for temporary structures to accommodate people and host events. To this end, it is considered that, likewise at Eleusis, quite some use could be made of the temporary structures exhibited.

3.4.7.3 Assessment of Services' Outcomes and Further Applications

Includes assessment of the efficiency, expected outcomes, and measurements to prove the KPIs of the tools/technology used in the case study, and additional applications of the technology that deliver comparable outcomes and efficiency

The Eleusis pilot demonstrated how participatory and technological tools can be combined to activate cultural heritage in a sustainable and inclusive way. The efficiency of the approach lies in its ability to mobilise diverse stakeholders - municipality, NGOs, residents, and external partners - to co-create both digital and physical solutions. Key tools included participatory questionnaires, co-design workshops, and digital visualisation techniques. These were effective in translating community insights into concrete design outputs that could be implemented in public spaces. Expected outcomes include the installation of small-scale architectural interventions (Green Tensegrity, pavilion, mobile furniture, temporary structures from recycled materials), complemented by digital layers (virtual exhibition archive, AR applications, projection mapping events). Together, these solutions aim to foster local identity, increase accessibility to heritage, and create inclusive spaces for cultural interaction.

KPIs can be measured through the number of participants engaged in co-creation activities, the diversity of community groups represented, the visibility of solutions in public spaces, attendance at cultural events, and the dissemination reach of hybrid sessions. These metrics demonstrate both social impact and the potential for replication in other heritage contexts.

3.4.7.4 Stakeholder Participation and Engagement

Overview of Stakeholder Roles in the Project Case Study

Gives an overview of the stakeholders involved in the case study project

A multidisciplinary team of architects, museologists, historians, anthropologists, and designers collaborated on the project. Their activities included coordinating design and projection mapping, leading the design of pavilions and temporary structures, engaging stakeholders and the local community, activating cultural heritage programs, and developing digital tools such as augmented reality and virtual archives. The team worked closely with municipal authorities to ensure alignment with local heritage and community priorities.

Challenges Encountered across Stakeholder Consultation, Planning and Execution of the Project

Includes issues related to communication, collaboration, decision-making, or other factors that affected the project's progress

Planning Phase: During the planning phase, one of the main challenges was mapping and coordinating a wide variety of stakeholders with diverse perspectives – ranging from municipal officials and cultural institutions to schools, artists, and residents. Ensuring that all groups were represented without overwhelming the process required careful prioritisation. Communication between technical experts and non-expert citizens sometimes created misunderstandings, as project terminology was not always easy to translate into everyday language. Furthermore, aligning project timelines with the availability of local schools and municipal bodies proved challenging, resulting in delays in scheduling participatory workshops.

Execution Phase: During implementation, the biggest challenge was ensuring broad and balanced participation. Youth groups were strongly engaged, but older residents and professionals proved more challenging to consistently involve, requiring additional outreach efforts. Another challenge was managing expectations: some stakeholders anticipated immediate physical results, while in reality, many solutions were still in the design phase. Hybrid communication (on-site vs. online) also posed coordination difficulties, as not all participants were equally comfortable with digital tools. Despite these hurdles, the pilot successfully maintained engagement by providing clear updates, utilising creative formats, and continually adapting methods to ensure inclusivity.

Mechanisms Undertaken to Ensure Effective Stakeholder Participation during the above Phases

Includes strategies or approaches used to engage stakeholders and ensure their input was considered throughout the project

- Stakeholder mapping and analysis: A stakeholder mapping exercise was done early to visualize all project stakeholders on a single roadmap. This provided insight into community needs and guided targeted outreach.

- Bottom-up participatory approach: The project used a co-production methodology so that community members actively shaped design decisions. Methods like interviews and workshops ensured stakeholders' perspectives were integrated.
- Diverse co-creation workshops: Workshops on design, art, architecture, and innovation engaged different community groups. These hands-on events enable citizens to collaboratively define project solutions and see their ideas brought to life.
- Inclusive engagement tools: Custom tools (e.g. AR/VR applications, the HeritACT toolkit) were used to involve a broad audience (youth, seniors, people with disabilities) and foster creativity.
- Ongoing feedback and evaluation: After each activity, participants provided input via surveys or interviews. Constant evaluation ensured equity and allowed the team to adjust activities to better meet community needs.

Stakeholder Engagement Issues and Relevant Case Study Learnings and Key Takeaways

Gives a documentation of the challenges faced by the learning partner. Includes overall learnings from the study visits as it relates to the pilots, and additional resources from the pilots as it relates to the case study across methodology, technology, context, and outcomes

In Sweden, many industries that have been abandoned are of interest from a city development and transformation perspective. Often, if former industrial buildings are suitable for other activities, they are used to create places and spaces for cultural purposes, such as museums like the Art Museum in Västerås. This museum is situated in the former ASEA (now ABB) industrial complex. An ongoing project is the city development that is taking place in Mölndal where a former papermill is transformed into a new city block. The old industrial buildings will be repurposed for cultural purposes, such as museums, theatres, and dance studios, and combined with other functions, including restaurants, shopping spaces, and more. The industrial feel, where water is a characteristic feature, is fundamental to the transformation now taking place. The developing project is named Forsåker.

3.4.7.5 Photographs from the Study Visit

Figure 23: L- UU Presentation; R- Old Olive mill site exploration with HeritACT team

3.4.8 Pilot 8: Ahmet Piriştina İzmir City Archive and Museum (APIKAM) - İzmir, Türkiye; Coordinator: IBB

Site Visited:	Eleusis, Greece
Learning Partner:	HeritACT consortium, led by University of Patras
More information:	https://www.heritact.eu/
Location:	Eleusis, Greece
Site Features:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptive industrial reuse • Seafront cultural continuity

3.4.8.1 General Overview

Site Description

Includes details across building type, purpose, age, materials used, any unique features, challenges faced, and the owner's needs

Site context: The HeritHUB is housed in Eleusis’s historic Old Canteen – a one-storey industrial canteen by the sea. Built in 1972 as a US Sixth Fleet facility, it was vacated after just two years and later became a beloved municipal canteen in the 1980s. Locals recall it as a summer meeting place (often paired with the adjacent open-air cinema). In 2023, as part of Eleusis’s European Capital of Culture legacy, the building was fully renovated to host cultural events. Today the Old Canteen is owned by the municipality (managed under Eleusis 2023 ECoC) and serves as the pilot’s main HeritHUB.

Building and use: Physically, it is a simple industrial hall (concrete/steel frame) characteristic of 1970s service buildings. Inside, it is a single multi-purpose hall that accommodates art exhibitions, talks, educational programmes, and community workshops. This reuse of a former industrial structure embodies the HeritACT pilot’s adaptive-reuse approach: it activates heritage space for contemporary community use. Unique features include its seafront location and connection to the old cinema, which together reinforce local memory. Challenges remain – some residents still remember it as a long-shuttered, inaccessible site – so the owner’s priority is making it an open, inclusive cultural hub that bridges Eleusis’s industrial past and its new role as a creative, community-driven city.

Themes Addressed

Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective themes, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness

5 - Most Relevant ; 1 - Least Relevant

THEME 1: Human-centred and life-centred approaches to Cultural Heritage

The Eleusis pilot aligns very strongly with this theme. The methodology is rooted in co-recognition, co-envision and co-design activities, including surveys, workshops, and participatory design sessions with residents of all ages. This ensured that local voices shaped the pilot’s outcomes, from identifying cultural symbols (myth, industry, everyday life) to creating informed architectural and digital interventions. The visit showed how such methods transform cultural heritage into a living

process, where accessibility, inclusion, and social innovation become integral parts of preservation and activation. This theme of the Eleusis project, which includes community engagement, accessibility, and nature-based solutions, is inspiring and relevant for Izmir’s pilot building APIKAM, with its multifunctional features appealing to a wide variety of visitor profiles.

THEME 2: Resource efficiency and circularity

Resource efficiency is addressed through solutions like the “Green Tensegrity” and “temporary structures from recycled materials”, which prioritize low environmental impact and reuse of resources. While not the primary focus of the pilot, these interventions clearly demonstrate how circular economy principles can be embedded in heritage activation. The most impactful insight was that even small-scale, mobile installations can showcase sustainable practices and inspire broader urban regeneration.

THEME 3: Capacity for innovative, transdisciplinary, and contemporary approaches

The pilot is inherently transdisciplinary, combining architecture, engineering, arts, and digital technologies. Solutions such as VR and AR, show how advanced tools can be integrated with cultural and social practices. The study visit highlighted how bringing together diverse expertise creates novel forms of cultural activation that are both technologically innovative and socially meaningful. Although no service is received on these issues at INHERIT, it is planned to work in this direction with academic advisors, since it is an important theme for the pilot.

Which NEB Pillars are addressed by this case study?

*Includes impactful learning experiences gained by the partners across the respective NEB pillars, while highlighting inspiring elements and practical usefulness
5 - Most Relevant ; 1 - Least Relevant*

Pillar 1: Sustainability

Sustainability is central to the Eleusis pilot. Solutions such as the Green Tensegrity, small-scale pavilion, and temporary structures from recycled materials embody environmentally responsible design, using durable and reusable materials. Activities also emphasized raising awareness of pollution and environmental challenges identified by the community. Together, these efforts promote ecological responsibility while reducing the project’s footprint.

Pillar 2: Inclusion

The pilot placed strong emphasis on accessibility and community participation. Through questionnaires, workshops, and co-design sessions, residents of different ages and backgrounds contributed to shaping the project. This inclusive methodology ensured that cultural diversity and local perspectives were reflected in both the process and the outcomes, strengthening ownership and social cohesion.

Pillar 3: Aesthetic/ Beauty

The pilot combines technical innovation with creative cultural expression. Mobile furniture, and pavilion designs are not only functional but also visually engaging, enhancing the beauty of public space. While beauty is valued, it is approached as complementary to sustainability and inclusion, ensuring that visual appeal supports rather than overshadows community needs and identity.

Steps of the Case’s Execution that were Most Inspiring and Relevant to the Pilot

Further includes the level of difficulty with regard to its applicability to the pilot

The APIKAM building, which is the pilot project, includes a courtyard space used within a public framework. One of the project goals within the INHERIT project is to increase the building's potential for various profiles of visitors. In this sense, the redesign of the courtyard is important. It is

considered that the urban furniture made from recycled materials used in the open space presented in the HeritACT project could inspire an application for the courtyard of the APIKAM building. The use of locally sourced materials in the furniture design and consideration for disadvantaged groups are viewed positively. In this context, the application is considered to incorporate NEB values. The production technology for urban furniture, namely 3D printing and CNC machines, is within the technical capabilities of the Izmir Metropolitan Municipality. This is another indication that this working method is feasible in the pilot project.

3.4.8.2 Applicability of Methods, Tools and Services to INHERIT Pilots

Pilot-wise Technology Learning and Applicability

Overview and Applicability of Technologies to the INHERIT Pilots

Service Type: Data collection & sharing	
Service No.: S0 - Heritage buildings smartification & data exchange	
Service Observed:	During the visit, examples of how data could be collected and shared about Eleusis’s heritage environment were presented conceptually. While not exactly a smartification system, the pilot emphasized how participatory inputs and digital archives (e.g., virtual exhibition archive, AR, stop-motion animation for projection mapping) function as data-sharing tools accessible to communities.
Applicability to the pilot:	While not exactly a smartification system, the HeritACT Eleusis pilot emphasized how participatory inputs and digital archives (e.g., virtual exhibition archive, AR, stop-motion animation for projection mapping) function as data-sharing tools accessible to communities. The original use of the APIKAM building as a fire station is significant in terms of urban memory. To ensure the continuity of its preservation by visitors, AR and stop-motion animation techniques can be used within the building to remind and inform users about this function

Service Type: Design and renovation services	
Service No.: S1 - Interactive screen use and AR-VR interfaces for heritage building	
Service Observed:	During the visit, digital design tools were discussed conceptually rather than demonstrated hands-on. The Eleusis pilot integrates comparable approaches through the Virtual Exhibition Archive and AR-enriched interactions, which allow heritage content to be accessed and visualised in immersive ways. While not focused on building renovation per se, these tools show how interactive screens and AR/VR can be used to engage communities in reimagining cultural spaces and experiencing heritage in new formats.

Applicability to the pilot:	<p>Eleusis pilot was not focused on AR/VR Technologies for building renovation. They used this technology for the engagement of communities in reimagining cultural spaces and experiencing heritage in new formats in public open spaces.</p> <p>AR-VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction technics can be used in the APIKAM building for raising the awareness of occupants and the visitors of our pilot. There are experts in Izmir Metropolitan Municipality who can create the visual materials for these kinds of technologies.</p>
<p>Service Type: Design and renovation services Service No.: S2 - Modelling and simulation environment</p>	
Service Observed:	<p>The modelling and simulation environment was partially demonstrated through architectural interventions' renders in context. These provided a sense of how proposed structures (pavilion, tensegrity, temporary structures) would interact with the cityscape and cultural sites of Eleusis.</p>
Applicability to the pilot:	<p>The modelling and simulation environment was partially demonstrated in Eleusis pilot. Also, modelling and simulation of APIKAM pilot is being prepared by service providers partially. Besides some academicians supports the modelling and simulation of APIKAM building within their academic research studies in their universities.</p>

<p>Service Type: Design and renovation services Service No.: S3 - Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning</p>	
Service Observed:	<p>No formal decision-support software was demonstrated. Instead, participatory co-design and stakeholder engagement acted as a decision-making framework. Questionnaires, workshops, and visual mock-ups guided priorities for solutions in Eleusis, providing a socially informed basis for planning rather than an algorithmic tool. This can be a difficult task.</p>
Applicability to the pilot:	<p>No formal decision-support software was demonstrated. Decision-support software is being prepared by service providers.</p>

Expected outcomes of Eleusis include the installation of Green Tensegrity, pavilion, mobile furniture, temporary structures from recycled materials, complemented by digital layers which are created using participatory methods.

By adopting sustainable, innovative, inclusive, and economical methods, the use of the APIKAM building courtyard can be diversified, the heat island effect can be mitigated, and the diversity of building users can be increased by adding extensions to the courtyard, as in the Eleusis example. To

increase participation, the design of these additions can be achieved through collective intelligence and design via social labs or lab projects to be conducted within the scope of the INHERIT project. The unique fire station function of the APIKAM structure and original materials used in the building and courtyard can guide the design of urban furniture and similar additions to be designed in this area.

What are the Resources Required for the Successful Implementation of Services?

Needs of the pilot partners to apply the relevant service types to their respective pilots, which includes challenges, modifications required, or areas where the technology could enhance the overall process

Service Type: Design and renovation services

Service No.: S2 -Modelling and simulation environment

- **Human Resources:** There aren't enough experts in İzmir Metropolitan Municipality who can use modelling, simulation, decision and support tools for historic building renovation.

Service Type: Design and renovation services

Service No.: S3 -Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning

- **Human Resources:** There aren't enough experts in İzmir Metropolitan Municipality who can use modelling, simulation, decision and support tools for historic building renovation.

3.4.8.3 Assessment of Services' Outcomes and Further Applications

Includes assessment of the efficiency, expected outcomes and measurements to prove the KPIs of the tools/technology used in the case study, and additional applications of the technology that deliver comparable outcomes and efficiency

The Eleusis pilot demonstrated how participatory and technological tools can be combined to activate cultural heritage in a sustainable and inclusive way. The efficiency of the approach lies in its ability to mobilise diverse stakeholders - municipality, NGOs, residents, and external partners - to co-create both digital and physical solutions. Key tools included participatory questionnaires, co-design workshops, and digital visualisation techniques. These were effective in translating community insights into concrete design outputs to be implemented in public space.

Expected outcomes include the installation of small-scale architectural interventions (Green Tensegrity, pavilion, mobile furniture, temporary structures from recycled materials), complemented by digital layers (virtual exhibition archive, AR applications, projection mapping events). Together these solutions aim to foster local identity, increase accessibility to heritage, and create inclusive spaces for cultural interaction.

KPIs can be measured through: number of participants engaged in co-creation activities; diversity of community groups represented; visibility of solutions in public space; attendance at cultural events; and dissemination reach of hybrid sessions. These metrics demonstrate both social impact and the potential for replication in other heritage contexts.

3.4.8.4 Stakeholder Participation and Engagement

Overview of Stakeholder Roles in the Project Case Study

Gives an overview of the stakeholders involved in the case study project

A multidisciplinary team of architects, museologists, historians, anthropologists, and designers collaborated on the project. Their activities included coordinating design and projection mapping, leading the design of pavilions and temporary structures, engaging stakeholders and the local community, activating cultural heritage programs, and developing digital tools such as augmented reality and virtual archives. The team worked closely with municipal authorities to ensure alignment with local heritage and community priorities.

Challenges Encountered across Stakeholder Consultation, Planning and Execution of the Project

Includes issues related to communication, collaboration, decision-making, or other factors that affected the project's progress

Planning phase: During planning, one of the main challenges was mapping and coordinating a wide variety of stakeholders with very different perspectives - from municipal officials and cultural institutions to schools, artists, and residents. Ensuring that all groups were represented without overwhelming the process required careful prioritisation. Communication between technical experts and non-expert citizens sometimes created misunderstandings, as project terminology was not always easy to translate into everyday language. Furthermore, aligning project timelines with the availability of local schools and municipal bodies proved difficult, leading to delays in scheduling participatory workshops.

Execution phase: During implementation, the biggest challenge was ensuring broad and balanced participation. Youth groups engaged strongly, but older residents and professionals were harder to involve consistently, requiring extra outreach. Another challenge was managing expectations: some stakeholders anticipated immediate physical results, while in reality many solutions were still in the design phase. Hybrid communication (on-site vs. online) also posed coordination difficulties, as not all participants were equally comfortable with digital tools. Despite these hurdles, the pilot maintained engagement by providing clear updates, using creative formats, and continuously adapting methods to ensure inclusivity.

Mechanisms Undertaken to Ensure Effective Stakeholder Participation during the above Phases

Includes strategies or approaches used to engage stakeholders and ensure their input was considered throughout the project

- Stakeholder mapping and analysis: A stakeholder mapping exercise was done early to visualize all project stakeholders on a single roadmap. This provided insight into community needs and guided targeted outreach.
- Bottom-up participatory approach: The project used a co-production methodology so that community members actively shaped design decisions. Methods like interviews and workshops ensured stakeholders' perspectives were integrated.

- Diverse co-creation workshops: Workshops on design, art, architecture and innovation engaged different community groups. These hands-on events let citizens collaboratively define project solutions and see their ideas embodied.
- Inclusive engagement tools: Custom tools (e.g. AR/VR applications, the HeritACT toolkit) were used to involve a broad audience (youth, seniors, people with disabilities) and foster creativity.
- Ongoing feedback and evaluation: After each activity, participants provided input via surveys or interviews. Constant evaluation ensured equity and allowed the team to adjust activities to better meet community needs.

Stakeholder Engagement Issues and Relevant Case Study Learnings and Key Takeaways

Gives a documentation of the challenges faced by the learning partner

No major issues were encountered regarding stakeholder engagement. Since the pilot building, APIKAM, is multifunctional, emphasis was placed on ensuring participation of building users from different service sectors in the Social Labs from the beginning of the project. Stakeholder participation has included experts in architecture, mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, and energy engineering from the provincial culture and tourism directorate, the conservation board, and the municipality; academics from university departments such as architecture, restoration, planning, landscape, and tourism; and relevant individuals from NGOs. As sensor measurements continue, more informed discussions are expected in future Social Labs with participation from experts and companies competent in energy and sensor measurement.

Social Lab Kick-off (29/05/2024): Consisted of 3 sessions with 20 stakeholders. Question-answer activities and table discussions were conducted to evaluate the structure's advantages and disadvantages in depth.

2nd Social Lab (29/01/2025): Included 47 participants and focused on NEB values and technical aspects of the INHERIT project.

3rd Social Lab (30/09/2025): Focused on analysing the visitor experience to increase local and foreign tourist participation. There were 29 participants, including academics and tourism sector experts, to address active use of the building from a broader perspective.

1st Dissemination Activity (2-3/09/2025): Held during the 94th Izmir International Fair. Surveys were conducted with 60 people to gather opinions on social accessibility, active use by diverse audiences, and energy efficiency in heritage structures. Including responses from the 3rd Social Lab, a total of 70 participants provided feedback, which was also shared during the opening presentation. From the Eleusis case, the stakeholder mapping exercise was considered useful. The bottom-up participatory approach and co-production methodology, along with diverse co-creation workshops, were found beneficial and can serve as examples for future lab projects on the courtyard. Inclusive engagement tools such as AR/VR applications can be used to convey the original fire station function of the pilot building and introduce it to a broad audience. Experts in Izmir Metropolitan Municipality can create visual materials for these technologies, raising awareness among occupants and visitors. Ongoing feedback and evaluation observed in the Eleusis case were also found very useful. Feedback is collected before, during, or after events via Google Forms and Mentimeter surveys, and interviews can be used to enable more active participation.

Lessons Learned and Looking Beyond

Includes overall learnings from the study visits as it relates to the pilots, and additional resources from the pilots as it relates to the case study across methodology, technology, context, and outcomes

The experience in this peer-learning exercise was very positive, and hospitality was highly satisfactory. However, the project's relevance to the APIKAM pilot was somewhat limited. The pilot focuses on the renovation of a historic building, while the Eleusis project emphasized temporary public space improvements. Although both projects adhere to NEB values, the technologies used differ. Nevertheless, the methods used in the Eleusis project are considered insightful examples for the design activity planned for the pilot building's courtyard.

As İzmir Metropolitan Municipality, a project named **"Agora Playground Project" Re-Value Project**, with was carried out. The outcomes of this project, along with other initiatives, were presented as a paper during the 19th General Assembly of ICOMOS: Heritage and Democracy in New Delhi, India, in 2017.

In the project, an existing open space opposite the ancient Agora was rehabilitated to create a safe playground for children. The design process was carried out in four stages with academic support. First, an educational workshop was held with nearby secondary school students to introduce the history of İzmir. In the second workshop, **"Thinking and Designing Together,"** twelve selected students shared their favourite games, evaluated the park's condition, and discussed preferred activities such as climbing and hiding.

Based on these results, design proposals were developed and revised through feedback sessions. A stakeholder meeting with local and metropolitan municipality representatives addressed implementation details and the risk of vandalism. To reduce costs and promote sustainability, waste materials such as iron bars and tires were reused. Finally, the playground was implemented collaboratively with children and municipal workers. Unlike previous projects in the area, the Agora Playground has been actively protected by the local community.

3.4.8.5 Photographs from the Study Visit

Figure 24: L- The oldtown square subject to the Eleusis pilot implementation; R- Historic Old Canteen – a one-storey industrial canteen by the sea.

Figure 25: L- IBB presentation with team; C- Walking to the industrial heritage site; R- HeritACT Eleusis pilot presentation of temporary structures from recycled materials

3.5 Results and Key Takeaways of the Peer Learning Scheme

The following is a synthesis of the key takeaways provided by the pilots.

3.5.1 Design and Planning of the Peer Learning Scheme

The INHERIT pilots were of the view that the peer-learning experience was highly valuable, and offered practical insights into low-tech sustainable renovation, while also demonstrating how strong community engagement can drive meaningful heritage transformation. Feedback received on the design of the peer learning scheme indicated that the exercise was very well organised and thoughtfully curated, with the study visits offering a rich mix of topics, including cultural and industrial heritage, stakeholder collaboration, energy efficiency, and digital innovation.

UU mentioned that the activity required extensive preparation, with planning beginning ten months in advance and involving numerous meetings, delays, and uncertainties. Although the visit's topic was only loosely connected to the pilot, it proved highly enriching. The hosts demonstrated exceptional hospitality, organisation, and inclusiveness, providing valuable presentations and discussions. Despite limited thematic relevance, the exchanges fostered strong networking opportunities, particularly with the Turkish INHERIT and Greek HeritACT teams, and revealed potential synergies between projects.

Overall, the visit provided valuable learning opportunities, expanded participants' perspectives, and established a strong foundation for future collaborations. The pilots greatly appreciated the thoughtful planning and effort that made the experience both highly informative and engaging.

3.5.2 Implementation

The pilots' feedback included that the visits were well-organised and allowed for informal but focused exchanges with local experts. REGEA found the combination of theory, lived experience, and physical demonstration was particularly impactful. ELLET also shared similar insights, indicating that the case studies shared were mostly relevant and inspiring. Participation was active, creating a supportive and collaborative atmosphere.

The peer-learning activities were very well organised and truly valuable. For FASADA, the visit to Cyprus provided new insights, practical knowledge, and inspiration to implement similar tools in different contexts. The demonstrations of AR/VR applications and discussions with experts from the Cyprus Institute were particularly effective and well-prepared. If any improvements were to be suggested, it would be to allocate a bit more time for hands-on sessions.

RPR noted how each case study brought a different perspective, making the overall experience very positive. The hosts provided clear insights into their challenges and solutions, which helped participants reflect on how similar approaches could be adapted to their own contexts. For the delegation, including stakeholders from Riga Municipality, the visit was especially inspiring.

3.5.3 Peer Learning and Networking

Overall, the participants felt well-supported and found the exercise helpful to share with their coworkers in the pilot; however, ELLET indicated that while the content generally met the pilot's needs, some topics could not be closely tailored to the participants' specific needs.

The partners at FASADA believed that the visit proved to be an extremely valuable and inspiring experience. The participants had the opportunity not only to explore the case study in detail but also to learn about other projects implemented by the Cyprus Institute that utilise AR/VR technologies. This allowed them to see a variety of applications of these tools, particularly in the context of cultural heritage preservation and energy efficiency in buildings. They were especially impressed by the visual aspect of the renovation scenarios, which makes it easier for a wider group of stakeholders to understand and engage with the proposed solutions. This approach facilitates decision-making, increases public acceptance, and supports fundraising efforts for renovation works. Another important takeaway was the use of AR/VR in education and knowledge dissemination, for example, through an exhibition dedicated to Cyprus's past, present, and future. These technologies also support archaeological research and scientific outreach. A particularly valuable aspect of the visit was learning how the Cypriot team addressed data integration challenges during the export of the BIM model. This knowledge may prove crucial when addressing similar issues in their own pilot project.

RPR expressed interest in seeing how similar INHERIT tools have been applied and tested in other projects across different regions. Showcasing practical examples or pilot results, especially in heritage buildings with similar challenges, would help participants better understand the value and adaptability of the tools. Additionally, hands-on demonstrations of digital tools, such as digital twins and energy forecasting, would be welcome.

CARTIF found the experience to be particularly positive and valuable in terms of knowledge exchange and networking opportunities. That said, identifying a case truly comparable to the Monasterio del Prado, especially in terms of advanced and meaningful use of H-BIM with a focus on preventive conservation, proved extremely challenging. It required a considerable effort to find a peer site with similar technical depth and scope. The pilot partners also acknowledged the significant commitment made by the Learning Partners in allocating time and resources to prepare a visit that involved sharing sensitive and non-public information, without any direct compensation under the INHERIT framework.

CARTIF and BOUYGUES also mobilised internal resources beyond those formally supported by the project to ensure its participation and contribution to this peer-learning experience in support of the initiative's success.

3.5.4 Challenges and Learnings

BOUYGUES noted that it is not easy to speak directly about NEB themes and that new digital tools are not often used in the real world. Current stakeholders may be reluctant to use such tools, so they must be highly effective.

CARTIF mentioned that the management and coordination of the capacity-building programme could be improved. Capacity-building in the context of cultural heritage requires not only coordination skills but also a quality level of specialisation and understanding of heritage-specific methodologies, challenges, and technologies. Addressing these shortcomings would significantly improve the coherence, relevance, and ultimately the impact of the peer-learning programme.

4. Task B: E-learning Modules

As part of the INHERIT e-learning scheme, a series of dedicated e-learning modules and webinars is being developed to disseminate the knowledge generated within the project as well as the experience gained from external activities such as the study visits and the peer learning scheme described above. Designed to address the specific needs of the pilot partners, the curriculum will present key concepts, methodologies, and tools on cultural heritage conservation, tailored to both pilot stakeholders and broader audiences. This chapter gives an overview of the method and implementation adopted to narrow the scope of the e-learning modules. It includes activities such as a mentoring scheme to identify the scope and audience, the mapping of skills, and pairing them with the modules and expected outputs of the project.

4.1 Method

Working towards the design of the e-learning modules and webinars, pilot partners participated in a two-stage workshop, in which they were asked for inputs and opinions about their professional experiences to capture the diverse contexts in which training, capacity building, and peer-learning are needed. In the two stages of the workshop, the participants worked together mapping the skills necessary for the next generation solutions for CH buildings. Later, these insights have been distilled into strengths, needs, and gaps.

The first stage included a ‘personas exercise’ which gathered information through role-play and imagination of the pilots and stakeholders, to gauge the various situations where training, capacity building, and peer-learning are required. This information was then distilled into needs and upvoting. In a second stage, this exercise was further refined with an in-person workshop during the second INHERIT General Assembly, aimed at bringing together soft and technical skills for the e-learning programme. To this end, consortium partners mapped relevant skills that were later divided into the three e-learning modules’ topics.

The next stage of the project foresees the utilisation of INHERIT results to address the previously identified crucial needs and required skills. Project partners are currently detailing the target groups of the project’s outputs and products, clarifying the expected previous knowledge that the users must possess to apply and utilise them, and the level of complexity of their application. To this, more information will be added: a clear description of the output will be provided, with keywords and key insights, including a step-by-step description of the specific method, tool, protocol, digital service, etc. This information is pivotal in translating INHERIT outputs and products into learning material - learning units within learning modules - allowing replicators and interested parties to learn how to deploy and benefit from them, providing them with easy and direct access to the project results. In the first half of 2026, three introductory webinars will disseminate the learning material, one webinar per module. In the context of the INHERIT project, learning units are the individual learning materials developed by the project to facilitate the application and replication of the specific outputs generated by each of the project activities.

4.2 Implementation

4.2.1 Mentoring Scheme: Scope and Audience of the E-learning Modules

As mentioned in the methodology, the first activity aimed to identify and define the key target audiences of the INHERIT capacity-building programme and e-learning modules. The activity was divided into two sections. First, the consortium partners conducted a 'Persona exercise' to brainstorm the different types of users that would be targeted by the learning scheme and capacity-building programme. This exercise was designed not only to define user types but also to generate shared empathy among participants, ensuring that the programme development remained rooted in a deep understanding of user needs and motivations. Secondly, the pilots were grouped in pairs to participate in tailored mentoring calls, led by ICLEI, which were used to identify the relevant skills that the different personas would need for the deployment of energy efficiency measures in cultural heritage buildings.

The first exercise brought together all the INHERIT partners in a session focused on identifying the key target audiences of the capacity-building programme, which was conducted online and was supported by a Miro board. The partners were guided through Miro, engaging in various activities, while also being given the freedom to explore the board and contribute ideas collaboratively. Prior preparation, including preliminary user research and the use of flexible persona templates, ensured that the session remained focused while also being adaptable to the diverse expertise of the participants. This collaborative framework encouraged cross-functional dialogue and strengthened alignment among stakeholders, promoting a shared understanding of the programme's users and their learning needs.

The activity began with a mapping exercise where participants were asked to identify the skills they considered essential for enhancing energy efficiency in cultural heritage. To this end, the participants had to classify such skills into two different categories: social sciences and humanities skills, and technical sciences skills. The participants had 5 minutes to provide inputs. This step supported the creation of a comprehensive view by integrating technical and socio-cultural competencies, ensuring that the personas reflected the multidisciplinary nature of cultural heritage management. The answers from the participants are shown in Figure 26.

Mapping skills

Please add skills that you think are essential for energy efficiency in cultural heritage

Figure 26: Mapping of SSH skills and technical sciences skills identified by project partners.

Once the relevant skills for improving energy efficiency in CH had been mapped, the project partners were asked two questions. First, who works in the CH sector in their respective countries, and second, which professions they believe should be involved in making CH buildings more resource efficient. The participants were again given five minutes to provide answers, as shown in Figure 27.

Who works in cultural heritage sector in your country?

Who should get involved to make heritage more resource efficient?

Figure 27: Mapping of professionals working in CH and professionals who could enhance resource efficiency in CH.

Once the results had been analysed and the most relevant skills and professions mapped, the participants were led to the final activity of the personas exercise: creating the personas. Using the skills from the previous activities, the participants profiled the personas into CH professionals and users who should be targeted by the e-learning modules. To this end, they were provided with blank templates they were asked to fill in with questions such as their age, gender, etc., and more importantly, questions related to their professions and interests in CH, their knowledge, skills, and

their learning needs. The results are shown in Figure 28 below, refer to [Annex D for documentation of Persona workshop](#).

Figure 28: The ‘personas’ illustration developed for the exercise to urge the participants to give diverse inputs; Credits: Agnieszka Ćwikła

By combining empathy-driven insights with structured data analysis, this exercise enabled the partners to construct realistic and actionable personas that could inform the design of user-centred learning materials. This exercise plays a crucial role in grounding the project in the real needs and motivations of diverse stakeholders. Building shared empathy and alignment across the consortium ensures that the capacity-building programme reflects both expert knowledge and community realities. Building owners, conservation experts, public authorities, and local communities may have different perspectives on what sustainability means in the realm of CH renovation and management, and it is the duty of the project to take them all into account and harmonise them as much as possible to ensure that learning materials are user-centred, socially inclusive, and practically applicable.

Once the personas exercise was finalised, the next step in the mentoring scheme was to group the pilots in pairs and hold trilateral meetings led by ICLEI. These were called “mentoring calls” and were used, among other purposes, to further strengthen stakeholder alignment and refine the shared understanding of user profiles, to fine-tune the profiles and skills of the different audiences that are to be targeted by the capacity-building programme.

The pilots were paired according to their suitability and condition, based on the type of renovation being pursued and digital services tested. In this sense, the pairs were the following:

- Spanish pilot (CARTIF)-Polish pilot (FASADA)
- Croatian pilot (REGEA)-Greek pilot (ELLET)
- Latvian pilot (RPR)-French pilot (BOUYGUES¹)
- Swedish pilot (UU)-Turkish pilot (IBB)

¹ The mentoring call with RPR and BOUYGUES had to happen only with RPR, since the French partner had to withdraw from the project and was later replaced by BOUYGUES-LINKCITY through an amendment of the General Assembly.

These mentoring calls, which covered different aspects that will be mentioned later in the deliverable, reserved 10 minutes to conduct an activity that was used to follow up on the personas exercise. This activity gathered all skills mapped during the exercise and, together with some more skills selected by ICLEI through desk research, were presented to the pilots during the mentoring calls for them to vote on each of the five most relevant ones to achieve sustainability and energy efficiency in CH buildings, and in specific, in their own heritage assets.

Figure 29: Overall outcome of all the skills voted after the mentoring calls were conducted.

As mentioned, the pilots voted on the different skills, and in addition, were urged to mention any other skills that they considered important. The pilots generally mentioned that those skills presented were mainly focused on SSH skills, and that there was a lack of technical skills. The results gathered from the personas exercise and the mentoring calls were used to frame the workshop that was carried out in the second INHERIT General Assembly, titled 'Technical and soft skills in Cultural Heritage'.

4.2.2 Technical and Soft Skills in Cultural Heritage

After completing the mentoring scheme, ICLEI analysed the results and gathered different sets of skills from the most voted ones, and then defined the three topics for e-learning modules according to the provisions of the partners. This research and clustering effort was followed by a workshop organised by ICLEI during the second INHERIT General Assembly in Valladolid.

During this workshop, the personas exercise and mentoring scheme were further refined by dividing the resulting skills into technical skills and soft skills, meaning those considering the social and cultural perspectives of the pilot sites. The partners were asked the following two questions:

1. What are the necessary technical skills in energy efficiency practices for cultural heritage buildings that you have utilised or considered important to design and begin implementing the services?
2. What soft skills (i.e. adaptability, active listening, cultural sensitivity, mediation) are crucial for professionals from different fields to successfully collaborate in enhancing energy efficiency in cultural heritage buildings?

After reading the two, the partners had 5 minutes per question to write down the skills they considered important and that fit into either one of the two categories. After completing this part, they were provided with red sticky notes and asked to vote for two skills that they considered had been lacking the most or were most important during the project's implementation up to that point. The outcomes gathered as shown in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Outcomes of the 'Bringing together technical and soft skills for the e-learning programme' workshop.

From the pictures above, a range of skills was voted on, including both hard and soft skills. They ranked, from most voted to least voted, as follows:

Votes for Hard Skills

Votes for Soft Skills

Figure 31: Results of voting conducted on hard skills and soft skills

In addition to the skills gathered from the personas and voting exercise carried out with the pilots, the inputs from both the technical and soft skills tables were classified among three provisional e-learning modules titled: 1) Planning and Management, 2) Development of technical skills, and 3) Adherence to the NEB principles and framework. The results of this last activity are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Skills mapped throughout the duration of the Mentoring Scheme up until the date of the Valladolid workshop.

Sets of skills	E-learning module 1: Planning and Management	E-learning module 2: Development of technical skills	E-learning module 3: Adherence to the NEB framework
Skills gathered from the Mentoring scheme activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource management and operations • Critical thinking • Flexibility/adaptability • Quality control • Communication skills • Presentation, branding, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem-solving skills • Effective use of digital tools and media • Evaluation of social and economic impact • Know-how to innovate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People and customer service • Teamwork • Partnership building • Creativity
Hard skills gathered from the ‘Technical and soft skills in Cultural Heritage’ workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge in energy efficiency measures • Use of historic materials and how they affect energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3D modelling • Simulation • Programming • Analysis of data • Conservation techniques • Use of historic materials and how they affect energy efficiency 	
Soft skills gathered from the ‘Technical and soft skills in Cultural Heritage’ workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitivity to cultural heritage • Communication skills • Proactive attitude • History and cultural knowledge 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitivity to cultural heritage (focused on the values) • Interdisciplinary collaboration • Collaboration (with stakeholders) • Empathy

4.2.3 Pairing Needs and Project Outputs

The goal of the learning material is twofold: on the one hand, it addresses the most urgent needs and gaps in deploying a successful and sustainable renovation and maintenance of CH buildings, integrating technical expertise with cultural and social perspectives. On the other hand, it provides easier access to project outputs, translating them into learning units and thus boosting the replication and exploitation of INHERIT results.

The table below provides an initial breakdown of the learning material generated by the project. The table will be further elaborated and finalised by the end of 2025, and the learning material will be collected and described within the first half of 2026. The learning modules, evolving according to the latest inputs from the development of the project, are now named as follows:

1. Smart planning and management for CH buildings, targeting heritage managers & building operators, local authorities & policy makers, researchers

- 2. Technical competences for next-generation solutions in CH buildings, targeting technology providers and users, researchers
- 3. Beautiful, sustainable, and inclusive CH buildings, targeting local authorities & policy makers, heritage managers & building operators, the construction sector, and researchers

A further breakdown of the learning modules into learning units is given in Table 6.

Table 6: Learning modules and learning units.

Smart planning and management for CH buildings	Technical competences for next-generation solutions in CH buildings	Beautiful, sustainable and inclusive CH buildings
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technical inspection protocols: 1) sensors installation, 2) functional behaviour, 3) heritage compatibility 2. Assessment and monitoring framework 3. Web application for multi-dimensional assessment 4. Hub of measures 5. Financial sustainability and risk assessment methodology 6. Impact and user satisfaction monitoring tool 7. SOAR analysis (strengths, opportunities, aspirations, results) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> s0 (service 0): exchange platform for CH building data s1: interactive AR/VR interfaces for renovation plan s2: modelling and simulation tool for energy efficiency s3: decision support tool to compare renovation options s4: web application for indoor environmental quality and comfort s5: web application for energy forecasting s6: digital twins for 1) Energy efficiency, 2) Pathology detection, and 3) accessibility & inclusiveness s7: web application for crowd and mobility management s8: H-BIM for standardised preventive maintenance s9: GIS-based tool for sustainable heritage maintenance s10: web application for climate risk scenarios assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Social Labs methodology 2. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) method 3. NEB self-assessment online tool 4. ‘NEB values on the ground’ workshop 5. Journal template for monitoring and self-reflection 6. SWOT meets NEB 7. Participation ladder 8. Sustainable Business Model Canvas

4.3 Next Steps

The next phase of this task focuses on the development, structuring, and validation of the learning modules. The learning units, approximately 10-15 per module, will be finalised based on project outputs and the partners responsible for their development. Partners responsible for developing each specific output will provide key information, including the detailed definition of target groups, expected prior knowledge, and the complexity level of each unit (basic, intermediate, or advanced). This information will then be matched with the results of previous activities and, in accordance with established standards, i.e., European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO) and European Qualifications Framework (EQF), to assign an appropriate level.

Starting 2026, a template for each learning module will be prepared, taking into account the learning units it presents, which could be shown in different formats: textual, video, examples, step-by-step

guidelines. The templates will define the structure and format of the learning units, potentially including interactive elements hosted on the website. Some of the aspects that each template might cover are:

- Title, abstract, and keywords
- Target groups and prior knowledge, level of complexity
- Learning outcomes (phrased as subject + active verb + objective/context)
- Clear explanation of relevance and practical application
- Detailed description of the learning unit
- Visual or multimedia support (graphs, schemes, short videos)
- Examples
- Conclusion and links to other learning units and external resources

Learning units will be completed, reviewed, and validated within the first quarter of 2026, and 3 webinars will be prepared in the second quarter, as a general introduction to each module to provide context and guidance for users. The results of this process will be featured in a future project report (D6.2), which will be made available on the project website, as well as the learning material collected and described. As mentioned above, the goal is to provide facilitated access to the knowledge generated by INHERIT, making it widely accessible and tailored to address the most in-demand skills in CH renovation and management.

5. Task C: INHERIT Living Journals

As part of the capacity-building framework, INHERIT emphasised the documentation of the experiences, reflections, and learning processes of pilot partners throughout the implementation of project activities. To this end, living journals were developed as tools for reflection, knowledge sharing, and monitoring project progress. These journals capture achievements, challenges, and lessons learned, supporting self-reflection and informing the design of capacity-building activities such as workshops, study visits, learning modules, and continuous learning.

5.1 Method

In line with the objectives of the capacity building programme, the pilot partners' experiences and learnings from the process were captured in so-called living journals. The results of the process were shared on a rolling basis and were used to design the capacity-building programme (study visits, e-learning modules, webinars). The journals also serve a second purpose: to facilitate self-reflection among pilot partners regarding the journey they have undertaken and to support them in planning future-oriented steps. Reflections captured in the journals have been analysed by ICLEI and are accessible to the whole project consortium.

The journals primarily documented the implementation of the INHERIT pilot's services by the cities, mainly across their achievements, challenges, and lessons learned. In the initial stages, from January to July 2024, the documentation followed a style (Version 1, or V1), wherein preset indicators (areas of change) were provided, and partners were requested to indicate their level of implementation for each area of change every month. The objective of this exercise was to assess, in a monthly manner, which aspects of the pilots' services were most and least feasible to implement, and to observe changes in the long run. In addition, the partners documented the challenges they faced, the advantages of their implementation, any lessons learned, and the next steps for the upcoming month. The next steps, documented by the partners, largely became the pilot's achievements in the following month.

As of July 2024, the format of the journals was revised (V2) to enable pilots to critically reflect on their own achievements, challenges, lessons learned, and next steps, without being tied to indicators that proved too rigid for monthly updates. This eliminated the need to rate the implementation of their projects against pre-set areas of change. This allowed partners to bring in a range of perspectives and updates relevant to the phase of their project's implementation with greater flexibility. In the final iteration of the documentation format (V3), the objective was to reduce the frequency of journaling by resorting to quarterly documentation to ensure that more substantial information on the project's advancement was collected, both qualitatively and quantitatively. A few sections have been revised, and the overall template has been expanded. Specifically, the sections on challenges, lessons learned, and next steps remain unchanged. The achievement section is differentiated into three new sections: transformation stories (what has changed in your pilot site in the past four months), community updates (how pilot partners have

informed or engaged stakeholders or the wider community), and NEB in action (which values were addressed and in what way). V3 was adopted in September-October 2025, with the first issue covering the period from May to June 2025. Journals will continue to be collected quarterly until the end of the project.

5.2 Implementation

5.2.1 Achievements

At the initial stages of the pilots' implementation, the indicators assessed included Information Sharing with stakeholders, Accessibility (physical, psychological, economic), and Diversity (by gender, ethnicity, religion, belief, ability, age, and sexual orientation). Due to the initial stages of the project, information sharing emerged to be a key priority for the pilot stakeholders. As the project progressed over February and March 2024, multi-disciplinarity in the stakeholder group was prioritised, coupled with an inclusion of non-academic and non-formal knowledge to support the project. This stage of the project aligned with the establishment of the local Social Labs² and fostered co-creation with stakeholders. Inclusiveness and openness of the group emerged as priorities across all pilots. However, preference was given to multi-level engagement, which then paved the way for a transdisciplinary approach, rather than participatory processes.

As May and June 2024 approach, the pilots enter a slight lull. The indicators of focus included the existence of a business model and strategic investment plan, while embracing a circular perspective. This also includes plans for the use and reuse of materials and resources, as well as waste management and its transformation, the latter being prioritised by the city of Visby in June. The feedback collected highlights difficulties in adhering to pre-set indicators, given the monthly frequency and the unpredictability of certain timeframes.

For this reason, transitioning from June to July, the documentation style changed to allow for the pilots to reflect on their individual progress, as it aligned with the status of their projects. During this period, pilot cities advanced data collection, assessment, and preparatory actions for their respective INHERIT tasks. CARTIF focused on the collection of key data to determine KPIs, gathering information on gas, electricity, and water consumption, and completing an inventory of parts of the building, along with historical research. IBB completed the SRI (Smart Readiness Indicator) Assessment, sharing the score and report for their case study building. FASADA purchased equipment to measure air quality, heat, electricity, and gas consumption, collected data on annual or multi-annual resource use in two dwellings, and completed part of the building inventory and historical documentation. ELLET finalised procedures for purchasing required equipment (sensors) and prepared for installation, while maintaining successful communication with stakeholders and receiving constructive feedback to support the next project steps.

² Refer to the INHERIT deliverables [D2.1: Social Lab Methodological Handbook](#), high-level requirements and [D2.2: Active societal participation and enabling conditions for the INHERIT heritage-built environment](#)

From September to November 2024, progress in data collection and assessment was a major achievement for the INHERIT pilot cities. Across sites, the pilot partners made progress in gathering energy, environmental, and structural data to support baseline analyses and inform subsequent steps. CARTIF completed point cloud processing of the Monastery of Nuestra Señora del Prado, began assessing its conservation status, and collected HVAC and intervention data. IBB finalised its baseline assessment, determined sensor placements, and completed its procurement. ELLET installed and activated monitoring equipment to track environmental and energy performance, while FASADA developed 3D scans and gathered technical data, collaborating with city energy departments, and REGEA and UU completed the SRI assessments for their pilot buildings. A secondary focus during this period was the planning and organisation of Social Labs and stakeholder engagement activities, with RPR prioritising the conceptualisation, organisation and documentation of its second Social Lab. Following suit, UU, ELLET and FASADA also initiated preparation for their upcoming Social Labs. Active stakeholder communication and involvement were also emphasised by ELEET, IBB, and REGEA. Additional achievements included the development of HBIM models (CARTIF), VR/AR tool design (FASADA), filming and promotional activities (UU, FASADA, IBB), participation in INHERIT learning activities (UU, REGEA), and preparation for key project meetings and events such as the General Assembly in Valladolid.

Moving towards the latest phase from December 2024 to March 2025, the INHERIT pilot partners prioritised the implementation and advancement of Social Labs, with UU, REGEA, IBB, FASADA, and ELLET successfully organising their second Social Labs, which focused on facilitating dialogue on heritage conservation and pilot-specific challenges, while involving key stakeholders. Furthermore, the pilots demonstrated continued progress in data integration and modelling, with CARTIF advancing Revit modelling and the BEP, and IBB completing sensor installation and initiating data transfer. A key highlight for FASADA was its study visit to Cyprus, where it explored potential collaborations with Digital Twin and AR/VR service providers and aligned on next steps. ELLET published the INHERIT 10-point guide³, advanced integration of digital services (GIS-based, IEQ, energy forecasting), and reviewed User Interface strategies.

The following phase, from March to September 2025, was characterised by an overall strengthening of outreach, engagement, and technical consolidation activities across the INHERIT pilot partners. While most of the lessons learned and reflections from study visits are reported in [Chapter 3](#), several other achievements can be identified during this period.

Participation and public engagement experienced a significant boost across pilot sites. ELLET, for example, organised a cultural walk around its pilot site, encouraging participants to observe and reflect on barriers to access and inclusion in a tangible, real-life setting. This initiative fostered a stronger sense of shared purpose, reimagining heritage not as a static built environment but as a living, accessible, and inclusive space integrated within contemporary urban life. The activity also achieved an increase in youth participation, with young people and students who, more than others, demonstrated enthusiasm and a willingness to act. In Gdynia, FASADA contributed to raising the visibility of the INHERIT project and deepening community engagement. The historical walk,

³ Refer to ELLET [“10-Point Guide” for the sustainable conservation of historic buildings](#) (available both in Greek and English)

organised as part of the third Social Lab, together with an article published on the city's official website, successfully enhanced public awareness of the pilot site's cultural value and sparked interest among local authorities in the building and its future use. The development of detailed HBIM models and renovation scenarios provided a clearer vision for restoration, while neighbours and local organisations expressed interest in contributing to upcoming activities, demonstrating an emerging sense of shared ownership and collaboration.

IBB further advanced its cultural programming by updating exhibitions in the museum and courtyard and developing new educational programmes for primary school students and adults. These initiatives strengthened the pilot's role as a space for learning and civic engagement, connecting heritage interpretation with community development. REGEA increased the regional visibility of sustainability and climate action initiatives, most notably through its participation in the Green Point Festival held in Karlovac on June 14, 2025. This event provided a platform to promote the INHERIT project's values and demonstrate the integration of cultural heritage within broader green transition strategies. In the meantime, RPR finalised the development of the energy certificate, energy management plan, and the technical and economic justification for improving the energy efficiency of the heating system at the Ave Sol concert hall building, and CARTIF made significant progress in the development of the HBIM model of the Monastery of Nuestra Señora del Prado and consolidated the environmental monitoring informing transferrable preventive management strategies.

5.2.2 Challenges

A recurring challenge across pilot cities was the effective coordination and communication with stakeholders. During the implementation of the project, beginning in January 2024, all pilot cities highlighted difficulties in engaging stakeholders across various phases, citing issues related to communication barriers, limited time availability, stakeholder fatigue, a lack of responses to cooperation proposals, and strict legislation concerning interventions in historical buildings. BOUYGUES indicated the absence of clear guidelines for communication, making consistent engagement challenging. These issues persisted in the preparation of Social Labs from November 2024 onwards, where coordinating multiple actors, facilitating discussions, and translating discussion points into actionable outputs proved complex. Managing diverse stakeholders, including governmental, academic, and technical representatives, required balancing differing expectations and priorities, often under time and resource constraints.

Data collection emerged as another critical challenge, particularly in March and April 2024 and also from July onwards. Pilot partners, such as FASADA and ELLET, prioritised gathering technical information on their buildings. Difficulties included collecting energy, electricity, and HVAC data, as well as integrating available data into the development of services for building users. Sensor installation posed significant issues for multiple cities, including Athens (ELLET), Izmir (IBB), and Valladolid (CARTIF), with connectivity problems and technical obstacles affecting the recording of environmental parameters. Additionally, technical complexities were also reported, with CARTIF highlighting difficulties in interpreting the point cloud due to the building's intricate and non-orthogonal geometry, as well as the lack of precedents with regard to the usage of HBIM for historic

heritage management in the region - representative of the novelty of these approaches in heritage management.

Additionally, bureaucratic and regulatory obstacles were frequently cited, particularly in relation to approvals for entering pilot sites, accessing historical documentation, and securing permissions for interventions. ELLET and IBB emphasised that heritage preservation regulations could interfere with energy-efficient redevelopment, while IBB specifically noted that approval from the Conservation Council could restrict material choices and renovation techniques. CARTIF highlighted the need for prior institutional approvals to facilitate partner visits and interventions, indicating that compliance with regulatory requirements often slowed project progress.

Several pilot partners also reported constraints in resource availability; from July onwards, FASADA and REGEA, for example, reported limited municipal resource availability, with ELLET expressing challenges with limited financial resources slowing down the installation and management of sensors and the execution of technical measurements.

While Social Labs were prioritised from November 2024 onwards, partners faced some challenges in planning and facilitating these events. Coordination of participants, translating discussion points into actionable next steps, and ensuring productive engagement required additional effort due to prior difficulties in stakeholder communication and limited resources.

The challenges reported are reflective of the complex, multi-dimensional nature of implementing energy-efficient and digitally supported interventions in CH buildings, which require careful coordination, technical expertise, and adaptive strategies to overcome regulatory, technical, and logistical barriers.

5.3 Lessons Learned and Next Steps

A key observation documented by the INHERIT pilot partners is that it is essential to avoid stakeholders' fatigue by not overloading them with requests. Instead, it is better to reach them only with targeted questions or requests for contributions, ensuring efficient communication. Furthermore, while presenting results, the importance of keeping communication simple and straightforward was highlighted. Another key element highlighted was the importance of creativity and flexibility in achieving successful stakeholder engagement. The co-creation process should be tailored to the specific needs of the parties involved. The partners also cited the need for being innovative in their approach to stakeholder involvement by identifying other actors, including local stakeholders, heritage specialists, as well as the private sector, and being prepared in case certain stakeholders were unresponsive - as noted in the case of Gdynia (FASADA) and Athens (ELLET).

The pilot partners also emphasised the importance of having positive stakeholder alignment, as well as a broader stakeholder network to support the project's vision and objectives, as documented by REGEA. A learning point highlighted by the pilot partner RPR was that, in cases where the pilot building did not directly involve building users in project activities, INHERIT developed an innovative approach to address this by involving building users in the project co-creation workshops.

In terms of structural constraints, partners noted the importance of accounting for physical and infrastructural limitations within historic buildings during planning, as well as their ability to generate simple and innovative phases. FASADA highlighted how insufficient design documentation can hinder project preparation, while CARTIF underscored that modelling architectural elements in historic buildings is inherently complex due to their unique, non-modular geometries. The usability of HBIM models for preventive maintenance depends heavily on the quality and completeness of available data, as well as their ability to generate simple, implementable maintenance strategies.

Additionally, UU's experience revealed how public perceptions significantly shape heritage-related projects. Local discussions often centred on what is required to keep the old town alive, with debates emerging around the concept of beauty and differing preservationist viewpoints. The city anticipated that such differing perspectives could lead to resistance, underscoring the need for ongoing dialogue and awareness-building.

Several pilot partners, including UU and CARTIF, observed that the renovation and maintenance of historic buildings are often constrained by time and cost. UU noted that these processes should be simplified and made more affordable, while CARTIF emphasised the inherent complexity and high cost of conserving heritage buildings due to their unique characteristics, materials, and systems. The pilot partners emphasised the importance of expert consultations to gain a deeper understanding of traditional materials, construction methods, and technical requirements. The early and formal inclusion of IT specialists was deemed useful for installing and monitoring sensors, as well as rapidly resolving any maintenance issues. In this regard, early communication proved crucial, facilitating timely coordination with ruling institutions, management of permits, and the anticipation of potential delays in their approvals.

The pilot partners found the Multistakeholder Forum particularly valuable, as it offered insights into the NEB principles and fostered cross-sectoral understanding. ELLET reflected on the importance of thorough preparation, proactive communication, and structured moderation when organising complex, multi-actor events. It also emphasised translating complex technical and policy discussions into accessible, actionable guidance for diverse audiences. Lessons were gained regarding the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration, clear communication channels, and cross-institutional coordination to ensure effective integration of innovative digital solutions. Flexibility and adaptability, especially when supporting developers and integrating digital services, were reinforced as key factors for successful project implementation.

As next steps, pilot partners will continue to document and share their progress, challenges, and insights. Even at this stage, the INHERIT Journals are valuable tools for collecting experiences, supporting learning, and facilitating self-reflection and exchange. They also help highlight how pilot partner activities align with the project's objectives, the NEB values, and the broader impact on communities and heritage, keeping the overall process focused and on track.

6. Key Takeaways from the INHERIT Capacity Building Programme

The INHERIT Capacity Building Programme, with its three core tasks — Peer Learning Scheme, E-learning Modules, and Mentoring Journals — proves to be a valuable, knowledge-transforming exercise, generating practical insights in not only preservation and transformation of CH but also deeper insights into human-centred and life-centred approaches to CH as well as shed light on concepts, methodologies, instruments and exemplar cases of CH conservation. It also aims at The capacity building will include reflection on resources needed for various CH sites, the sense and meaning of CH, and the capability to change the way of working towards more circular, renewable supply chain. The results of the activities that have taken place over the past two years convey a key message: learning and knowledge exchange through collaboration, training, and mentoring have a profound impact on achieving successful results. It demonstrated and offered learning on a rich mix of topics, expertise, technology, and case studies, linking cultural and industrial heritage, stakeholder collaboration, energy efficiency, and digital innovation. The structured matchmaking and execution of the peer learning study visits enabled meaningful interaction with local experts and facilitated an exchange of theoretical and applied knowledge. The E-learning workshops were successful in harvesting the technological, financial, and technical resource requirements of the pilots for executing the energy efficiency projects. This will form the foundational basis of designing the E-learning modules in the next phase. The Mentoring journals ensured regular documentation of progress carried out by the pilots and, in itself, is a method to review and keep track of the actions, which can be useful beyond the project's cycles as well. This combination of learning formats contributed to a strong culture of collaboration among INHERIT partners, thus creating an open space for reflection, experimentation, and replication.

The impact and successful outcomes of the Capacity Building programme can be identified in these areas:

Societal Impact and engagement of stakeholders

A key outcome of the peer learning visits by the pilots is the recognition that community and stakeholder engagement must be strategic, creative, and flexible. The Learning Partners emphasised the importance of involving stakeholders at appropriate project stages, particularly once plans and results are concrete, to ensure clear communication and efficient collaboration. Positive stakeholder alignment, broad networks, and inclusion of academic and technical expertise were essential to achieving shared ownership of project goals and fostering long-term commitment to sustainable heritage management.

Thinking Beyond INHERIT: Synergies, Networks, Opportunities

The INHERIT capacity-building and peer learning activity successfully demonstrated how transnational collaboration for knowledge exchange has the potential to build synergies between research and practice, thereby informing policy in the long run. The participating Learning Partners mobilised their personal as well as institutional capacities to contribute beyond formal project obligations. This not only reflects a shared commitment to conservation practices but also highlights

the role it can play in collective advancement in the discourse. The project's ongoing development of e-learning modules and webinars will ensure that the knowledge generated is assessed and disseminated across diverse audiences. This is to ensure a wider outreach and promotion of successful approaches to replication and adaptation in different cultural, climatic, and socio-economic contexts.

The Future of Cultural Heritage Conservation through Next Generation Solutions for Sustainable, Inclusive, Resource-efficient, and Resilient Cultural Heritage

Historic buildings and the built environment, with its heritage, cultural, architectural, and social values, represent a significant proportion of Europe's built stock and thus present themselves as one of the key areas for energy transition and efficiency initiatives. In the long term, INHERIT envisions a future in which energy efficiency is fully integrated into the conservation, adaptation, and management of built heritage. This vision is supported by continuing professional development and peer learning, innovative digital education through e-learning modules, and strong multi-stakeholder cooperation. The knowledge ecosystem created through INHERIT, which combines local practice, digital learning, and policy alignment, will enable replication, upscaling, and integration into European standards and frameworks.

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12. United Nations Environment Programme (2024). *Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction: Beyond foundations: Mainstreaming sustainable solutions to cut emissions from the buildings sector*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.59117/20.500.11822/45095>

Other useful links, provided by Pilots, are inspirational projects having relevance to the objectives of the project. This deliverable of the INHERIT project does not have any direct or indirect connections to the following initiatives and is only for informational purposes.

1. 3ENCULT project, available at: <http://www.3encult.eu/en/project/welcome/default.html>
2. Build Up, The European portal for energy efficiency and renewable energy in buildings, available at: <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/en/resources-and-tools/case-studies>
3. HERITAGE-PRO project learning modules, available at: <https://heritage-pro.eu/training-module/training-modules/>
4. HiBER project Atlas, available at: <https://hiberatlas.eurac.edu/de/willkommen-bei-uns-1.html>
5. Powering the METAmorphosis of BUILDings towards a decarbonised and sustainable energy system <https://www.meta-build.eu/>
6. Affordable and digital solutions to Build the next generatiON of smart EU buildings <https://buildon-project.eu/>
7. Using BIM in a renovation project <https://www.bim-speed.eu/en>
8. Digitising and transforming the European construction industry <https://www.ashvin.eu/>
9. P2Endure focuses on plug-and-play, energy-efficient building renovation using prefabricated systems, 3D printing, and BIM <https://www.p2endure-project.eu/en>
10. <https://www.culturalheritageimaging.org>: This tool uses a digital twin to monitor the condition of heritage buildings, conduct energy analyses, and simulate the impact of planned interventions.
11. HAPPEN “Pilots and Living Labs” section (Athens University Museum) <https://medzeb-happen.eu/pilots/>
12. <https://www.iccrom.org/events/hbim-methodology-and-digital-tools-cultural-heritage-conservation>
13. EU 3D-ICONS: portal focused on the 3D documentation of cultural heritage sites across Europe, offering tools and practices that combine photogrammetry, GIS, and BIM for public and professional use: <http://3dicons-project.eu>
14. OpenHeritage: Organizing, Promoting and ENabling HERitage Reuse through Inclusion, Technology, Access, Governance and Empowerment. OpenHeritage identifies and tests the best practices of adaptive heritage re-use in Europe. <https://openheritage.eu/>

8. Annexes

8.1 Annex A: Call for Learning Partners and Application Form

The following is the text published as an application form for an Open call for Learning Partners for the INHERIT Peer Learning Scheme.

Call for partners to enter peer learning activities and host INHERIT pilots

Are you a professional institute, organisation, researcher, expert in preservation of Cultural Heritage and have executed the NEB principles in your work? Do you have the technical expertise and know-how of innovation and technological advancement in various means of preservation of historic buildings, for e.g.: adaptive reuse, refurbishment, energy efficiency and monitoring, H-BIM, digital twins, AR-VR for monitoring to name a few? Or are you experienced in engaging stakeholders and communities in technological transformation of heritage sites towards sustainability and/or circularity? Are you eager to share the knowledge and insights learnt during the execution of your projects? Are you willing to contribute towards this exercise to develop, stimulate and facilitate synergies and peer-learning and build your network of NEB enthusiasts?

Step into the role of a learning partner, guiding the path toward sustainable, inclusive, and aesthetic enhancement goals of the New European Bauhaus; Showcase the remarkable potential of energy efficiency in your projects and garner recognition within the community of learning for cultural heritage sites; Inspire and foster meaningful dialogue with INHERIT pilots across Europe, igniting positive change together.

This call invites practitioners, institutions, and organizations to share their work and participate in a **non-monetary learning program**. Meet the INHERIT pilots, demonstrate futuristic approaches for a sustainable future, and share your unique insights. The learning program aims to engage in capacity development programs and foster knowledge exchange, cooperation, and collaboration to enhance learning outcomes. The program envisions inspiring partnerships among professionals, institutions, and organizations.

INHERIT in short

Preservation of cultural heritage has been experiencing a revolution through evolving concepts, dialogue, and the introduction of technological innovation. In conjunction with this, the project 'INHERIT: Next Generation Solutions for Sustainable, Inclusive, Resource-efficient and Resilient Cultural Heritage' was launched with an aim to generate strategies and pilots for sustainable, inclusive, resource-efficient, and resilient Cultural Heritage. The project also aims to further foster the ethics and goals of the European Green Deal and the New European Bauhaus (NEB) through cultural heritage as a driver.

The overall vision of INHERIT is to create a systematic methodology, accompanied by leading-edge Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), such as Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and (big) data analytics, and associated social/behavioural practices, towards sustainable, inclusive, and resource-efficient CH solutions. INHERIT will enable socially innovative and economically viable interventions at different urban levels (buildings, city/ neighbourhood), covering all relevant aspects of the heritage-built environment's life cycle:

- i. Preservation and maintenance
- ii. Design and renovation
- iii. Monitoring, operation, and management

What are the perks of joining this program?

- Become part of the larger community of learning partners exploring the application of the New European Bauhaus framework for cultural heritage buildings
- Garner visibility in the field of NEB and innovative solutions for sustainable, next-generation solutions for cultural heritage buildings
- Contribute to the capacity building program, which will be translated into a policy document for future practices for guidance and replicability
- Access the e-learning modules on energy efficiency in heritage sites
- Share your experiences as invited experts during INHERIT learning events and dedicated Breakfast@Sustainability facilitated by ICLEI Europe

What will your role be?

- ≠ Host two INHERIT pilots for one-day study visits (based on the needs and learning inputs, the program of the visits developed by ICLEI Europe and aligned with the pilots, the hosts, and objectives)
- ≠ Share lessons learnt from your NEB projects, early adaptations, experiments to replicate the outcomes, reflect on the process, constructive discussions, and feedback
- ≠ Network with the INHERIT partners and other related projects to build on the ecosystem of NEB experts in the field of cultural heritage and resource efficiency

Costs involved:

Learning program is an invited partnership as a pro-bono program. The project will cover travel expenses of the INHERIT pilots to visit the hosting partners with **no additional costs** or expenditures for the hosting partners.

Themes of the learning program to be addressed during the study visits (subject to change based on the needs):

The main aims for study visits are:

- enhancing knowledge exchange,
- fostering collaboration,
- promoting best practices.

More specifically the study visits will address the following themes aligned with the specific needs of the hosts and the learning partners:

Theme 1: Human-centred and life-centred approaches to CH

The human-centred approach focuses primarily on the aspects of participation and engagement of communities, local regeneration, and social innovation; assess and address the socio-economic impacts of the interventions; facilitate accessibility through ergonomic principles (E.g., barrier-free

access, elderly-friendly). The life-centred approaches cater to nature-based solutions coupled with interventions in historic buildings. These provide chances to integrate environmentally sustainable elements into the preservation of cultural heritage and associated mutual advantages (E.g., introduction of terrace gardens, façade gardens), use of eco-friendly and natural materials for retrofitting, to name a few.

Theme 2: Resource efficiency and circularity

Resource efficiency and circularity in cultural heritage, aligned with the principles of the New European Bauhaus, involve optimizing resource use and promoting a circular economy within heritage preservation. This entails minimizing waste, maximizing material lifespan, and embracing sustainable practices throughout the lifecycle of cultural heritage assets. By integrating these principles, conservation efforts can reduce environmental impact, conserve resources, and promote the sustainable management of cultural heritage.

Theme 3: Capacity for innovative, transdisciplinary, and contemporary approaches

Advancing technology in historical preservation entails utilizing state-of-the-art tools to strengthen conservation endeavours and efficiently integrating innovative technologies across different disciplines to enhance conservation methods such as AI-based algorithms, big data analytics (Including historical and archival findings, remote sensing and satellite measurements), Heritage Building Information Models (H-BIM), digital twins, use of interactive screens, Augmented Reality/ Virtual Reality AR/ VR interfaces, digital twin for heritage facilities' real time monitoring amongst others, demonstrating energy efficiency through use of sensors and monitoring. Furthermore, the capacity for social innovations is relevant, including bottom-up initiatives, empowering new governance models, co-creation, and co-implementation of change.

INHERIT Pilots:

Want to learn more about the INHERIT pilots, challenges and goals? (Link to pilots File: [Link 1_Pilots](#))

Timeline and task stages

- Launch of call: 11th April 2024
- Closing date: 20th May 2024
- Selection of the hosts: 30th June 2024
- Design of study visits: July 2024
- Developing tailored programmes, matching pilots with the hosts: August - October 2024
- Study visits, feedback rounds: November 2024 - June 2025
- Webinars and networking events for pilots, learning
- partners and other stakeholders: March 2025 onwards

Who can apply?

A minimum of 4 partners across Europe will be selected to host study visits (for two INHERIT pilots), share experiences, and learn based on the following criteria:

- **Case typology:** Public buildings having uses such as administrative offices, museums and archives, concert halls, commercial buildings, and/ or residential buildings, social housing, and/or adaptive reuse projects, contributing to at least one of the three themes of the learning program
- **Type of entities applying:** NEB local incubations, other pilots in NEB-related Horizon projects, NEB Prizes winners or participants (2021, 2022, 2023), projects, organisations

with experience with the NEB. Beyond this, architecture and engineering professionals, experts, researchers, institutions dealing with and having expertise and delivering successful projects, which may include historic preservation, adaptive reuse, cross-cutting technology and energy efficiency, digital tools and technologies, and relevant skills and expertise in cultural heritage

- **Project type and status:** Completed projects and/ or ongoing near completion projects

How to apply

Interested candidates to join the learning program are required to submit an online application form, including supporting documentation. The language of the applications is English. The deadline for submissions is 20th May 2024 at 17.00 CEST.

The guidelines for applicants describe the application and selection process in detail, explaining what information and documents are required in the application form.

Please consult the FAQ section below for potential applicants for further information. The call helpdesk can be contacted with any questions regarding the application process and the selection criteria.

Application form

Introduction and consent

Submit your application to join the INHERIT community as a learning partner to host study visits by entering your data and preferences until 20th May 2024 at 17.00 CEST (Date extended at two accounts)

Before giving your consent to the use of your data, please read the Data Protection Policy for this call on this link

Informed Consent Form

Use of common personal data

By clicking 'submit' I agree to INHERIT processing the data received through this registration form for the purpose of the organisation of the Open Call for Learning partners to join the INHERIT community and relevant project' activities.

Contact information

First name

Last name

Job title

Organisation

Region/ City

Country

Interest in the 'INHERIT learning program'

INHERIT aims to generate strategies and pilots for sustainable, inclusive, resource-efficient, and resilient Cultural Heritage. Rank the following interventions as per your organisation/ individual expertise or projects' highlights:

THEME 1: Human-centred and life-centred approaches to CH

Elaborate on how your project engages with communities, fostering social innovation and local regeneration, while ensuring accessibility and inclusivity for all. Show how you integrate nature-based solutions into your preservation efforts, leveraging eco-friendly materials and innovative techniques to harmonise cultural heritage with environmental sustainability.

THEME 2: Resource efficiency and circularity

Showcase how your project promotes resource efficiency and circularity in cultural heritage, inspired by the New European Bauhaus. Emphasise minimising waste, maximising material lifespan, and integrating sustainable practices, and addressing life cycle cost (LCC). Highlight innovations such as durable, locally sourced materials, modular construction, and renewable energy infrastructure, while minimising costs through waste reduction and material reuse

THEME 3: Capacity for innovative, transdisciplinary, and contemporary approaches

Elaborate how your project harnesses advancing technology in historical preservation by leveraging state-of-the-art tools to strengthen conservation efforts and improving energy efficiency management through AI, technologies: Digital twin for heritage facilities' real time monitoring, Use of AR/VR interactive screens and interfaces, application of alternative energy resources for improving energy efficiency and building performance, employing AI-based algorithms and big data analytics, utilising Heritage Building Information Models (H-BIM), and others.

Key area of intervention and most applicable for demonstration for INHERIT pilots:

The INHERIT Call for learning partners envisages demonstration through site visits to the following areas. Highlight and prioritise which aspects amongst the following can be most applicable for demonstration and site visit by the pilots:

- i.* Preservation and maintenance targeting energy efficiency
- ii.* Monitoring, operation, and management
- iii.* Social and environmental innovation
- iv.* Contribution to policy recommendations

Pilot case most applicable to the proposed case study for peer learning:

Each pilot of the total eight has a varied context, uses, and requirements for the project execution. Select as per your proposed case for study visit, 2 pilots who would benefit the most from this learning program.

- City administration, Jastrebarsko, Croatia
- Le pritemps de Metz, Metz, France
- ELLET, Athens, Greece
- The concert hall Ave Sol, Riga, Latvia
- Social housing, Gdynia, Poland
- Monastery Nuestra Senora del Prado, Castille and Leon, Spain
- City of Visby, Sweden
- Amet Piristina Izmir archives, Izmir, Turkey

From which of the 8 pilots you could imagine to learn the most. Please select two:

- City administration, Jastrebarsko, Croatia
- Le pritemps de Metz, Metz, France
- ELLET, Athens, Greece
- The concert hall Ave Sol, Riga, Latvia
- Social housing, Gdynia, Poland
- Monastery Nuestra Senora del Prado, Castille and Leon, Spain

- City of Visby, Sweden
- Amet Pirstina Izmir archives, Izmir, Turkey

Motivation to become a learning partner

What can you and your organisation contribute to this peer-learning program? Why do you want to join this program as a learning partner?

Proposed case study (Mandatory)

Describe the case study proposed for the peer-learning program and highlight the interventions which align with the goals of this project

Proposed alternative case study (Optional)

Describe the case study proposed for the peer-learning program and highlight the interventions which align with the goals of this project

Challenges for sustainable cultural heritage

Describe what are the main challenges faced by cultural heritage in the process of sustainability, circularity and energy efficiency and that will be shared with the pilots in the learning process

Learning objectives as a learning partner

Describe how becoming a partner in this learning program would be of value to you and your organisation's current and future endeavours

Preferred time of study visit

Please indicate the most preferred months (November 2024-June 2025) time which will be beneficial for the study visit and the suitable duration (between 1-2 days)

8.2 Annex B: Assessment of Relevance and Matchmaking Process for all Learning Partners and Pilots

The following shows the matchmaking of services between the INHERIT Pilots and the Learning Partners involved in this task. The following matchmaking was a result of an exercise carried out to correlate each of the Pilot's and Partners' services and find the most suitable case study that could benefit the INHERIT Pilots. Each pilot was matched with at least one (or more) partners and was given the opportunity to democratically select and finalise the peer learning location based on interest, learning opportunity, travel budget, and resources, as well as the needs of the Pilot organisations and the associated local authorities.

Matrix of services proposed for INHERIT Pilots:

INHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	INHERIT Pilots							
			Pilot 1: REGEA: Jastrebarsko, Croatia	Pilot 2 : BOUYGUES: Noisiel, France	Pilot 3 : ELLET: Athens, Greece	Pilot 4 : RPR: Riga, Latvia	Pilot 5: FASADA: Gdynia, Poland	Pilot 6 : CARTIF: Valladolid, Spain	Pilot 7: UU: Visby, Gotland, Sweden	Pilot 8 : IBB: Izmir, Turkey
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1	-	-	-	-	✓	✓		-
	Modelling & simulation environment	S.2	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	✓	✓
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Monitoring, Management operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimization	S.4	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-	-
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5	✓	-	✓	-	-	-	✓	-
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	✓
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	✓	-
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓

Matrix of services adopted at proposed case studies by learning partners:

INHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	Learning Partners					
			Partner 1: Zero Waste House - Žalec, Slovenia	Partner 2: Green Tensegrity Installations - HeritACT/ University of Patras - Greece	Partner 3: Paphos Gate - The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus	Partner 4: Old IronWorks - Institut Iskriva, Slovenia	Partner 5: Baraccano Historical Complex - University of Bologna, Italy	Partner 6: Cisco Headquarters - ULTEAM, Arte Charpentier, France
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0	-	-	✓	✓	✓	-
Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1	-	✓	✓	✓	-	-
	Modelling & simulation environment	S.2	-	-	-	-	-	✓
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	✓	-	✓	-	✓
Monitoring, management, operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimization	S.4	✓	-	-	-	-	✓
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5	-	✓	-	-	-	-
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6	-	✓	✓	-	-	-
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7	-	-	-	✓	-	-
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8	✓	-	✓	-	✓	-
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9	-	-	-	-	✓	-
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10	✓	-	-	-	-	-

Assessment for Pilot 1: City Administration Headquarters - Jastrebarsko, Croatia; Coordinator: REGEA

REGEA matched with Zero Waste House, Slovenia

INHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	Pilot 1: REGEA: Jastrebarsko, Croatia	Partner 1: Zero Waste House - Žalec, Slovenia	Partner 2: Green Tensegrity Installations - HeritACT/ University of Patras, Greece	Partner 3: Paphos Gate - The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0	✓	-	-	✓
Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1	-	-	✓	✓
	Modelling & simulation environment	S.2	-	-	-	-
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	✓	✓	-
Monitoring, Management, operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	S.4	✓	✓	-	-
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5	✓	-	✓	-
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6	-	-	✓	✓
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7	-	-	-	-
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8	-	✓	-	✓
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9	-	-	-	-
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10	✓	✓	-	-

Assessment for Pilot 2: Cité du goût - Noisiel, France ; ; Coordinator: BOUYGUES

BOUYGUES matched with ULTEAM, Arte Charpentier, France

INHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	Pilot 2 : BOUYGUES: Noisiel, France	Partner 6: Cisco Headquarters - ULTEAM, Arte Charpentier, France	Partner 1: Zero Waste House - Žalec, Slovenia	Partner 2: Green Tensegrity Installations - HeritACT/ University of Patras - Greece
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0		-	-	-
Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1		-	-	✓
	Modelling & simulation environment	S.2	✓	✓	-	-
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	✓	✓	✓
Monitoring, management, operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	S.4	✓	✓	✓	-
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5		-	-	✓
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6		-	-	✓
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7		-	-	-
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8		-	✓	-
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9		-	-	-
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10	✓	✓	✓	-

Assessment for Pilot 3: ELLET building in Tripodon street - Athens, Greece; Coordinator: ELLET

ELLET matched with Institut Iskriva, Slovenia

INHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	Pilot 3 : ELLET: Athens, Greece	Partner 4: Old Iron Works - Institut Iskriva, Slovenia	Partner 1: Zero Waste House - Žalec, Slovenia	Partner 2: Green Tensegrity Installations - HeritACT/ University of Patras - Greece
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0	✓	✓	-	-
Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1		✓	-	✓
	Modelling & simulation environment	S.2		-	-	-
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	✓	✓	✓
Monitoring, management, operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	S.4	✓	-	✓	-
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5	✓	-	-	✓
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6		-	-	✓
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7	✓	✓	-	-
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8		-	✓	-
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9	✓	-	-	-
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10		-	✓	-

Assessment for Pilot 4: Ave Sol Concert Hall - Riga, Latvia; Coordinator: RPR

RPR matched with Institut Iskriva, Slovenia

INHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	Pilot 4 : RPR: Riga, Latvia	Partner 4: Old Iron Works - Institut Iskriva, Slovenia	Partner 1: Zero Waste House - Žalec, Slovenia	Partner 2: Green Tensegrity Installations - HeritACT/ University of Patras - Greece
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0	✓	✓	-	-
Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1	-	✓	-	✓
	Modelling & simulation environment	S.2	✓	-	-	-
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	✓	✓	✓
Monitoring, Management, operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	S.4	✓	-	✓	-
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5	-	-	-	✓
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6	-	-	-	✓
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7	-	✓	-	-
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8	-	-	✓	-
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9	✓	-	-	-
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10	-	-	✓	-

Assessment for Pilot 5: Social Residential Building in Gdynia - Gdynia, Poland; Coordinator: FASADA
 FASADA matched with The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus

INHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	Pilot 5: FASADA: Gdynia, Poland	Partner 3: Paphos Gate - The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus	Partner 2: Green Tensegrity Installations - HeritACT/ University of Patras - Greece	Partner 4: Old Iron Works - Institut Iskriva, Slovenia
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0	✓	✓	-	✓
Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Modelling & simulation environment	S.2	-	-	-	-
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	-	✓	✓
Monitoring, management, operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	S.4	-	-	-	-
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5	-	-	✓	-
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6	✓	✓	✓	-
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7	-	-	-	✓
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8	✓	✓	-	-
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9	-	-	-	-
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10	-	-	-	-

Assessment for Pilot 6: Monastery 'Ntra. Sra. del Prado' - Valladolid, Spain; Sweden; Coordinator: CARTIF

CARTIF matched with University of Bologna, Italy

INHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	Pilot 6 : CARTIF: Valladolid, Spain	Partner 5: Baraccano Historical Complex - University of Bologna, Italy	Partner 2: Green Tensegrity Installations - HeritACT/ University of Patras - Greece	Partner 3: Paphos Gate - The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0	✓	✓	-	✓
Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1	✓	-	✓	✓
	Modelling & simulation environment	S.2	-	-	-	-
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	-	✓	-
Monitoring, management, operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	S.4	-	-	-	-
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5	-	-	✓	-
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6	✓	-	✓	✓
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7	-	-	-	-
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8	✓	✓	-	✓
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9	-	✓	-	-
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10	-	-	-	-

Assessment for Pilot 7: City of Visby, UNESCO World Heritage Site - Gotland, Sweden; Coordinator: UU

UU matched with HeritACT/ University of Patras - Greece

NHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	Pilot 7: UU: Visby, Gotland, Sweden	Partner 2: Green Tensegrity Installations - HeritACT/ University of Patras - Greece	Partner 4: Old IronWorks - Institut Iskriva, Slovenia
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0	✓	-	✓
Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1		✓	✓
	Modelling & simulation environment	S.2	✓	-	-
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	✓	✓
Monitoring, management, operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	S.4	-	-	-
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5	✓	✓	-
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6	-	✓	-
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7	-	-	✓
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8	-	-	-
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9	✓	-	-
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10	✓	-	-

Assessment for Pilot 8: Ahmet Pirıştina İzmir City Archive and Museum (APİKAM) - İzmir, Türkiye;
Coordinator: IBB

IBB matched with HeritACT/ University of Patras - Greece (Changed plans) and Institut Iskriwa, Slovenia (initial plan)

INHERIT Services: Categories and Description		Service no.	Pilot 8 : IBB: İzmir, Turkey	Partner 2: Green Tensegrity Installations - HeritACT/ University of Patras - Greece	Partner 4: Old IronWorks - Institut Iskriwa, Slovenia	Partner 3: Paphos Gate - The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus
Heritage building lifecycle	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	S.0	✓	-	✓	✓
Design and renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	S.1	-	✓	✓	✓
	Modelling & simulation environment	S.2	✓	-	-	-
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	S.3	✓	✓	✓	-
Monitoring, management, operation	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	S.4	-	-	-	-
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	S.5	-	✓	-	-
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	S.6	-	✓	-	✓
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	S.7	✓	-	✓	-
Preservation and maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	S.8	-	-	-	✓
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	S.9	-	-	-	-
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	S.10	✓	-	-	-

8.3 Annex C: Documentation Format for Peer Learning Study Visit

The following is a questionnaire designed to document the peer learning study visits.

Questionnaire for documentation with guidelines and details of submission

The purpose of this questionnaire is to document key insights, discussions, and knowledge shared during your study visit to the case study site. It serves as a structured tool to help guide your observations and reflections while ensuring the comprehensive capture of learning experiences. The responses collected will contribute to Deliverable D 6.1, which focuses on identifying synergies, mapping inspiration, and learning from other actors within the INHERIT capacity building programme. Your inputs will help shape future peer-learning activities and capacity-building efforts.

The questionnaire is divided into five main sections:

- **Section A: Methodology:** Understanding the thematic and methodological approaches applied in the case study.
- **Section B: Technology:** Identifying relevant technological applications and their effectiveness.
- **Section C: Efficiency and Outcomes:** Evaluating the efficiency of tools and technologies used.
- **Section D: Participation and Stakeholder Engagement:** Exploring the involvement of stakeholders in the case study.
- **Section E: Other Information:** Documenting additional insights, photographs, and references.

How to Fill Out the Questionnaire

- **Read Carefully:** Review each section of the questionnaire before beginning to ensure you understand the scope and type of information required.
- **Provide Concise Yet Detailed Responses:** Where applicable, use 100-200 words to elaborate on key aspects.
- **Use the Rating Scales:** When asked to rate themes or technologies, use the provided scale (1 = low, 5 = high) and provide a brief justification.
- **Refer to Observations:** Ensure that your responses reflect direct observations, discussions with the case study hosts, and any supporting documentation provided during the visit.
- **Attach Supporting Materials:** Where relevant, upload photographs, links, and other references that illustrate your findings.
- **Take Prints for Convenience:** You can print the questionnaire and take it with you during the visit to jot down key points. For convenience you can document in your native language. Later, translate, refine and complete your responses for final submission in English.

Important Tips for Completing the Study Visit Questionnaire

- **Be Objective and Specific:** Focus on factual descriptions and measurable impacts rather than personal opinions unless explicitly requested.
- **Highlight Key Learnings:** Identify unique or particularly impactful aspects of the case study that could be applicable to other projects.
- **Compare with Your Own Pilot:** Relate observations to your own work where possible, considering applicability, challenges, and potential adaptations.
- **Ensure Completeness:** Fill in all questions and required fields to create a comprehensive documentation of the visit.
- **Submit on Time:** Ensure the questionnaire is submitted promptly after the visit to maintain accuracy and relevance.

Mode of Submission

- **Editable Word Document:** Complete the questionnaire in the provided Word document format, ensuring all information is filled in. Format: word file. Make a copy of this file to your respective folder: INHERIT_T6.1_Learning scheme_Documentation survey for study visits.docx
- **High-Resolution Photographs:** Attach and upload photographs with correct number/caption in the designated folders assigned to you on SharePoint. Format: jpeg, jpg
- **Sharepoint folder:** Study visits and documentation
- **Supporting Documents:** Scan and upload any additional supporting documents relevant to the study visit. Format: jpeg, jpg. pdf.
- **Name and Details:** Ensure all names, designations, and relevant details are properly filled in the main Word document.
- **Deadline Compliance:** Submit the completed questionnaire and associated materials by the 3 weeks after the visit is carried out, to ensure timely processing and inclusion in the learning programme.
- **Confirmation of Submission and feedback:** We will review the materials submitted to us, in case we have any concerns, we will reach out to the pilots for more information.

If you have any further questions regarding the submission process, please contact ICLEI team
 By following these guidelines, your contributions will enhance the knowledge exchange process and support the broader objectives of the INHERIT learning programme. Thank you for your efforts towards making this leaning scheme and capacity building scheme a success!

General Information and overview of the study visit:

Add Details:

- Pilot name:
- Dates and time of visit:
- Visit location:
- Contact of visiting persons (Name, Email, Designation):

1. Describe the site information provided by the host, including details such as the building's type, purpose, age, materials used, any unique features, challenges faced, and the owner's needs. Aim for 200 words.
2. Location map of the building (coordinates, you can attach a google map) *Attach Map (.jpg or .pdf)*

Section A: Methodology (Related to NEB)

3. Which of the following themes best aligns with this case study? In 100-200 words, describe the most impactful learning experience you gained from this theme, highlighting its inspiration or practical usefulness, explaining your ratings. Rate the relevance of these themes to your pilot.

Theme	Rate relevance to your pilot (1-low, 5 high)	Explain in max. 100 words
THEME 1: Human-centred and life-centred approaches to Cultural Heritage. This theme emphasizes sustainable interventions in cultural heritage through community engagement, accessibility, and nature-based solutions to preserve and enhance the built environment while addressing social, economic, and ecological impacts.	(Add response here)	(Add response here)

THEME 2: Resources efficiency and circularity. Focused on promoting circular economy principles, this theme advocates for sustainable conservation practices by optimizing resource use, reducing waste, and integrating renewable energy solutions and durable materials in cultural heritage preservation.	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
THEME 3: Capacity for innovative, transdisciplinary, and contemporary approaches. This theme highlights the role of technological innovation and transdisciplinary collaboration in conservation, leveraging cutting-edge tools like AI, big data, and digital models to enhance the preservation and sustainability of cultural heritage.	(Add response here)	(Add response here)

4. Which New European Bauhaus (NEB) pillars are most relevant to this case study? Please rate them on a scale of 1 (low) to 5 (high) and provide a brief description (100 words) explaining your ratings. Rate the relevance of these themes to your pilot.

Theme	Rate relevance to your pilot (1-low, 5 high)	Explain in max. 100 words
Sustainability Emphasizing creation of environmentally sustainable designs that promote the efficient use of resources and reduce ecological impact.	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
Inclusion Prioritizing accessibility, ensuring that cultural and social diversity is reflected in designs that are welcoming and beneficial to everyone.	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
Aesthetic/ Beauty 15. To foster innovative, beautiful, and inclusive designs that harmonize with their surroundings while enhancing the quality of life for all.	(Add response here)	(Add response here)

5. Which steps in the execution process of this case study did you find most inspiring and relevant to your pilot project? Do you think these steps are easy to replicate or difficult to apply? Explain in 100-200 words. (Add response here)

Section B: Technology

6. During your visit to the study site, which services did you observe being demonstrated? Please describe the relevant services in max. 100 words. **ONLY RELEVANT**

Type	Service no.		Write your observation of services during the case study as demonstrated (Max. 100 words)
Data collection & sharing	S0	Heritage buildings smartification & data exchange	(Add response here)
Design & renovation services	S1	Interactive screen use and AR-VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction	(Add response here)
	S2	Modelling and simulation environment	(Add response here)
	S3	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	(Add response here)
Monitoring, operation & management services	S4	IEQ and thermal comfort optimization	(Add response here)
	S5	Energy forecasting and intelligent management	(Add response here)

	S6	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring and management	(Add response here)
	S7	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	(Add response here)
Preservation & maintenance services	S8	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	(Add response here)
	S9	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	(Add response here)
	S10	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	(Add response here)

7. How do you assess the use of this technology in your pilot project? Name the service and evaluate its application (Describe) in 100 words. (Easy/ Difficult/ is there a Challenge/ Does it need modification) **ONLY RELEVANT**

Type	Service no.		Write your observation of services observed and their relevance to your pilot (Max. 100 words)	Assess the application of this technology in your pilot (Easy/ Difficult/ Challenge/ Needs modification)
Data collection & sharing	S0	Heritage buildings smartification & data exchange	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
	S1	Interactive screen use and AR-VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
Design & renovation services	S2	Modelling and simulation environment	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
	S3	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
	S4	IEQ and thermal comfort optimization	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
Monitoring, operation & management services	S5	Energy forecasting and intelligent management	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
	S6	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring and management	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
	S7	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
	S8	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
Preservation & maintenance services	S9	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	(Add response here)	(Add response here)
	S10	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	(Add response here)	(Add response here)

8. From the above response, please elaborate what are the needs of application of the relevant technology to your pilot. Based on your previous response (Q no.7), could you elaborate on the specific needs for applying the relevant technology to your pilot project? Please describe the needs for each service, including any challenges, modifications required, or areas where the technology could enhance the overall process. Add rows to describe one of more services

Requirements	Service no.	Explanation
Economic resource		
Technical resource		
Manpower resource		
Support of local government		
Other		

Section C: Efficiency and outcomes

9. Describe the assessment (the efficiency, expected outcomes, measurements to prove the KPIs) of the tools/technology used in the case study, based on the information provided by the host or partner. Focus on the facts and details as they were explained during the visit.
10. How would you apply this technology in your pilot project? Are there any modifications needed to achieve the expected outcomes when using this technology?
11. Based on your professional experience, are you aware of a similar technology or application that delivers comparable outcomes or efficiency? If so, please share any relevant websites or documents.

Section D: Participation and stakeholder engagement

12. Does the case study involve stakeholders? If so, please name the stakeholders that were mentioned and the role they played or the expertise they brought to the project.
13. What measures were taken to ensure effective stakeholder participation during the planning and execution of the project? Please describe any strategies or approaches used to engage stakeholders and ensure their input was considered throughout the project.
14. What challenges were encountered during the stakeholder consultation, planning, and execution of the project? Please highlighting any issues related to communication, collaboration, decision-making, or other factors that affected the project’s progress.
 - a. Planning phase
 - b. Execution phase
15. Does your pilot project face any stakeholder engagement issues? Are there any lessons learned from this case study that could be applicable or relevant to your pilot. Highlight key takeaways that could improve stakeholder involvement in your own project.

Section E: Other information

16. Please upload photographs that reflect your learning experience during the case study, along with captions describing each image. Include the image name when uploading.
17. Do you have examples similar to this case study that resonated with the methodology, technology, context and expected outcomes, in your practice or region or knowledge. Describe in short, share links, documents providing more information if available.
18. How was your experience in this peer-learning exercise? Please provide feedback on what went well and any challenges you faced
19. Rate the following aspects with regards to this task, on a scale of 1(low) to 5(high):

	Rate	Any comments
Planning and execution		
Case study selection		
Collaboration opportunities		
Learning and knowledge exchange		
Content relevance		
Clarity of instructions and objectives		
Engagement and participation		
Support and resources		
Professional development impact		
Overall satisfaction		

18. Do you have any suggestions for improving the peer learning activities or capacity building program? Please share your thoughts.
19. Do you still have unanswered questions? Let us know!

8.4 Annex D: Documentation of the Persona Workshop

Persona 1 - Harriet

AGE: 50
GENDER: F
LOCATION: (specific or small/big municipality): big municipality
AREA: heritage authorities (legal issues, regulations)
PAIN POINTS: she has to say "no" to many innovative projects, heritage is behind the energy efficiency

Reasons to work in the CH field

Focus on personal and professional reasons

Knowledge and skills

What does she/he know? What is she/he good at?

Learning needs

What doesn't she/he know? What she/he wants or needs to learn?

Persona 2 - George

AGE: 28
GENDER: M
LOCATION: (specific or small/big municipality): smaller municipality
MOTIVATION: muzeum (heritage building, with significant heritage collection)
PAIN POINTS: lack of resources and capacity to follow the green and digital transition (?)

Reasons to work in the CH field

Focus on personal and professional reasons

Knowledge and skills

What does she/he know? What is she/he good at?

Learning needs

What doesn't she/he know? What she/he wants or needs to learn?

Persona 3 - Anna

AGE: 35

GENDER: F

LOCATION: (specific or small/big municipality) Small municipality- works in finance department

MOTIVATION: has inherited a 1500s mansion, loves history

PAIN POINTS: difficulty in finding funding avenues for cultural heritage preservation, limited funds, cannot divert to historic preservation department

Reasons to work in the CH field

Focus on personal and professional reasons

Knowledge and skills

What does she/he know? What is she/he good at?

Learning needs

What doesn't she/he know? What she/he wants or needs to learn?

Persona 4 - Juan

AGE: 52

GENDER: Male

LOCATION: Country-side

MOTIVATION: Farmer, tired of just farming and looking for something else to do (?). Interested in preserving old buildings and local, rural cultural buildings

PAIN POINTS: Limited time to devote to this most of the months of the year, more of a side job that he can focus on in the winter months.

Reasons to work in the CH field

Focus on personal and professional reasons

Knowledge and skills

What does she/he know? What is she/he good at?

Learning needs

What doesn't she/he know? What she/he wants or needs to learn?

Persona 5 - Maria

AGE: 26

GENDER: Female

LOCATION: big municipality

MOTIVATION: young architect who wants to re-use and develop historic buildings

PAIN POINTS: Lacks experience and have a hard time to convince older colleagues about innovative projects

Reasons to work in the CH field

Focus on personal and professional reasons

Knowledge and skills

What does she/he know? What is she/he good at?

Learning needs

What doesn't she/he know? What she/he wants or needs to learn?

Persona 6 - Ola

AGE: 61

GENDER: F

LOCATION: (specific or small/big municipality) **Big municipality**

MOTIVATION: PhD in cultural heritage management, university professor

PAIN POINTS: innovation and critical thinking is not always welcome in industry interactions

Reasons to work in the CH field

Focus on personal and professional reasons

Knowledge and skills

What does she/he know? What is she/he good at?

Learning needs

What doesn't she/he know? What she/he wants or needs to learn?

Persona 7 - Arman

AGE: 42

GENDER: Male

LOCATION: rural

MOTIVATION: Works as a carpenter, wants to work more with traditional buildings

PAIN POINTS: Difficult to get clients and authorities to try more ecological insulation systems, like bio-based insulation materials

Reasons to work in the CH field

Focus on personal and professional reasons

Knowledge and skills

What does she/he know? What is she/he good at?

Learning needs

What doesn't she/he know? What she/he wants or needs to learn?

Persona 8 - Najwa

AGE: 41

GENDER: FEMALE

LOCATION: URBAN

MOTIVATION: independent researcher interested in architecture, archeology, museums and AR -VR technologies

PAIN POINTS: not enough exciting work done around her

Reasons to work in the CH field

Focus on personal and professional reasons

Knowledge and skills

What does she/he know? What is she/he good at?

Learning needs

What doesn't she/he know? What she/he wants or needs to learn?

